

Chapter 5 Realizing a sustainable world for nature and people: transformative strategies, actions and roles for all

Supplementary Materials

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Annex 5.1. Global review of literature: Analysis for strategies and actions

Table SM.5.1. Occurrence of terms for strategies and actions in the assessment corpus and in the case corpus. Frequency of occurrence of terms relating to actions for transformative change (by Strategy). The search calculated the number of hits of 566 terms for instruments (organized in 26 actions and 5 Strategies) in the title and abstract of the 4,654,669 documents in the assessment corpus ¹ and 45,037 in the case corpus².

	Action	Nb in Assessment corpus	Nb in case corpus	% in Assessment corpus	% in case corpus
Strategy 1: Conserving and regenerating places of value to nature and people					
Action 1.1	Recognizing and conserving Indigenous Peoples and local communities	11600	473	2.76	4.39
Action 1.2	Enhancing rights-based approaches	6337	276	1.51	2.56
Action 1.3	Basing conservation on diverse values of nature	86950	3166	20.68	29.42
Action 1.4	Shifting from extractive to regenerative systems	16025	326	3.81	3.03
Action 1.5	Advancing integrated spatial planning	16168	523	3.84	4.86
Total Strategy 1		116994	3535	27.82	32.84
Strategy 2: Driving systemic change in the sectors most responsible for biodiversity loss and nature's decline					
Action 2.1	Regulating resource extraction.	28774	855	6.84	7.94
Action 2.2	Embedding technology in transformative frameworks	81096	1888	19.28	17.54
Action 2.3	Financing for global sustainability	4987	240	1.19	2.23
Action 2.4	Supporting civil society initiatives	13214	372	3.14	3.46
Total Strategy 2		125448	3190	29.83	29.64
Strategy 3: Transforming economic systems for nature and equity					
Action 3.1	Mainstreaming innovative economic tools	6734	211	1.60	1.96
Action 3.2	Supporting just transitions	38512	1299	9.16	12.07
Action 3.3	Reforming financial systems	6166	203	1.47	1.89
Action 3.4	Adopting new metrics of success	4194	108	1.00	1.00
Total Strategy 3		54609	1708	12.99	15.87
Strategy 4: Transforming governance systems to be inclusive, accountable and adaptive					

¹ Corpus of literature on transformative change (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251349>)

² Case studies database with transformative potential and pitfalls (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260233>)

	Action	Nb in Assessment corpus	Nb in case corpus	% in Assessment corpus	% in case corpus
Action 4.1	Strengthening biodiversity in integrated governance	7144	299	1.70	2.78
Action 4.2	Engaging diverse actors in inclusive governance	10029	568	2.38	5.28
Action 4.3	Securing collaboration and accountability in multilateral governance	18121	962	4.31	8.94
Action 4.4	Strengthening learning through informed, accountable and adaptive governance	6355	365	1.51	3.39
Total Strategy 4		40278	1926	9.58	17.89
Strategy 5: Shifting societal views and values to recognize and prioritize the fundamental interconnections between humans and nature					
Action 5.1	Increasing nature connectedness	9737	260	2.32	2.42
Action 5.2	Shifting culture through new narratives	7495	210	1.78	1.95
Action 5.3	Changing social norms	83710	1747	19.91	16.23
Action 5.4	Facilitating transformative learning	27501	1242	6.54	11.54
Action 5.5	Co-creating knowledge	4055	232	0.96	2.16
Total Strategy 5		129054	3455	30.69	32.10

Figure SM.5.1. Temporal analysis of occurrence of actions before and after 1992 in the assessment corpus. Relative frequency of occurrence of terms relating to actions for transformative change before and after 1992 (by strategy). The search calculated the number of hits of 566 terms for instruments (organized in 26 actions and 5 strategies) in the title and abstract of the 4,654,669 documents in the assessment corpus.

Analysis of co-occurrence of terms relating to actions for transformative change. The search calculated the number of hits of 566 terms for instruments (organized in 26 actions and

5 strategies) in the title and abstract of the 4,654,669 documents in the assessment corpus. Nodes are coloured by strategy; the size of the nodes indicates the number of works in each node, while the thickness of the lines indicates the proportion of overlapping works of the maximum possible.

Relative frequency of occurrence of terms relating to actions for transformative change before and after 1992 (by strategy). The search calculated the number of hits of 566 terms for instruments (organized in 26 actions and 5 Strategies) in the title and abstract of the of the 45037 documents in the case corpus. Nodes are coloured by strategy; the size of the nodes indicates the number of works in each node, while the thickness of the lines indicates the proportion of overlapping works of the maximum possible.

Figure SM.5.2. Co-occurrence analysis of actions in the assessment corpus. The interactive online figure can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373914>. To view the figure, please download the html and view it locally in your browser.

Table SM.5.2. Occurrence of terms for sectors and actor groups in the assessment corpus and in the case corpus. Frequency of occurrence of terms relating to actor groups in transformative change (by actor category). The search calculated the number of hits of 316 terms for actors (organized in 17 actor groups and 4 actor categories) in the title and abstract of the 4,654,669 documents in the assessment corpus and 45,037 in the case corpus.

Actor group	N case corpus	N Assessment corpus	% case corpus	% Assessment corpus
Actor category 1: Civil society				
Civil society organizations	399	9051	0.51	0.29
Environmental movements/activists	247	7270	0.31	0.23
Indigenous Peoples	972	35110	1.24	1.12
Individual citizens	6237	251344	7.95	8.00
Local communities	4933	176634	6.29	5.63
NGO	672	7907	0.86	0.25
Actor category 2: Private sector				
Business	12082	428326	15.40	13.64
Donor/foundations	1651	74646	2.10	2.38
Financial actors	2648	89666	3.37	2.86
Actor category 3: Government				
Intergovernmental organizations	637	25200	0.81	0.80
Justice system	950	49483	1.21	1.58
Local/regional government	2390	73328	3.05	2.34
National government	4284	180558	5.46	5.75
Actor category 4: Communicators and knowledge holders				
Education community	7786	306548	9.92	9.76
Media and communication	3125	119934	3.98	3.82
Networks	1347	28269	1.72	0.90
Scientific community	28109	1276828	35.82	40.66

Figure SM.5.3. Temporal analysis of occurrence of actor groups before and after 1992 in the assessment corpus. Relative frequency of occurrence of terms relating to actor groups in transformative change before and after 1992 (by actor group). The search calculated the number of hits of 316 terms for actors (organized in 17 actor groups and 4 actor categories) in the title and abstract of the 4,654,669 documents in the assessment corpus.

Figure SM.5.4. Co-occurrence analysis of actors in the assessment corpus. The interactive online figure can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373933>. To view the figure, please download the html and view it locally in your browser.

Analysis of co-occurrence of terms relating to actors in transformative change. The search calculated the number of hits of and 316 terms for actors (organized in 17 actor groups and 4 actor categories) in the title and abstract of the of the 4,654,669 documents in the Transformative change assessment corpus of literature. Nodes are coloured by actor category; the

size of the nodes indicates the number of works in each node, while the thickness of the lines indicates the proportion of overlapping works of the maximum possible.

Figure SM.5.5. Co-occurrence analysis of actors in the case corpus. The interactive online figure can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373942>. To view the figure interactively, please download the html and view it locally in your browser.

Analysis of co-occurrence of terms relating to actions for transformative change. The search calculated the number of hits of 316 terms for actors (organized in 17 actor groups and 4 actor categories) in the title and abstract of the 45,037 documents in the case corpus. Nodes are coloured by actor category; the size of the nodes indicates the number of works in each node, while the thickness of the lines indicates the proportion of overlapping works of the maximum possible.

Annex 5.2. Strategy 1

The 2050 Vision for Biodiversity aims to achieve a world living in harmony with nature. The IPBES Global Assessment found that this vision is still possible if economic, social and governance systems are redesigned (IPBES, 2019a). Indigenous Peoples and local communities steward almost 80% of the world's remaining biodiversity on an estimated 22% of the earth's surface (Tauli-Corpuz et al., 2016; World Bank, 2003, 2011). In this context, collaboration with Indigenous Peoples and local communities has been identified as potentially the “best hope” for biodiversity conservation (Levis et al., 2024). This strategy recognizes a key action is to conserve what is working and recognize the governance and tenures of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in the earth's remaining places of rich biological and cultural diversity.

Action 1.1: Recognizing and conserving “territories of life”

The pathway to establishing Indigenous Peoples' and Community Conserved Territories and Areas will be as diverse as the cultures that steward these places. The ICCA Consortium defines territories of life as “territories and areas conserved by Indigenous Peoples and local peoples/custodians” (Sajeva et al., 2019). This name is understood as an abbreviation for a phenomenon that has many expressions and names in cultures and locations around the world, including: *wilayah adat*, *himas*, *agdals*, *territorios de vida*, *territorios del buen vivir*, *tagal*, *qoroq-e bumi*, *yerli qorukh*, *faritra ifempivelomana*, *qoroq*, Ancestral domains, country, community conserved areas, *territorios autonomos comunitarios*, sacred natural sites³, locally managed marine areas and many others. “Territories of life” as defined by ICCA share three characteristics: 1) a specific community that maintains strong and deep-seated links with a specific territory or area; 2) community is a key actor in the process of decision-making relative to the territory or area and its resources; and 3) governance system contributes to the responsible and sustainable management of the ecosystems and of the community's tangible and intangible heritage (ICCA Consortium, 2021; Sajeva et al., 2019; Zanjani et al., 2023).

Widespread recognition of self-determined Indigenous territorial governance and of the customary tenures of Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' territories offers a pathway for conservation of the critical biocultural heritage held in many countries (Zanjani et al., 2023). On-the-ground examples of Indigenous Peoples and local communities-led conservation initiatives can range from large contiguous land and water conservation areas based in complex Indigenous governance systems (Paul et al., 2023; Riddell, 2015) to smaller-scale and loosely connected conservation area networks governed by community-level institutions (Duker & Klanarongchao, 2022). Many of these territories currently operate in opposition to or are unsupported by state institutions, while others such as Indigenous Guardians programmes and Indigenous Protected and Conserved Areas in Canada and Australia are supported by states, albeit not without some tensions (Artelle et al., 2019; Mansuy et al., 2023; G. Reed et al., 2020; Youdelis et al., 2021).

Indigenous Peoples lead to higher levels of transformative potential in the ecological, economic and social dimensions of nature's contributions to people. There are 100 cases of the case study

³ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

database (n=391) in which the title and/or promoters of the initiative with transformative potential were Indigenous Peoples.

One example of Indigenous Peoples and local communities involvement in conservation is the South Rift Association of Land Owners, a community-based and community-driven land trust in Kenya established in 2004 to unite 16 Maasai communities in the management and security of their landscape. SORALO's approach is founded upon two Maasai cultural concepts: Enkop'ang "our good land, our common identity, our common pride" and Erematare "stewardship and care over common resources" (Macharia et al., 2021; Ontiri & Robinson, 2018; Sircely et al., 2022; S. Sundstrom et al., 2012; Tyrrell et al., 2022; Western et al., 2015). Nigeria several communal and culturally relevant sites that ensure either directly or passively the transformative conservation of biodiversity provides another example of Indigenous Peoples involvement in conservation (Ayotunde & Edet, 2009; Oladeji et al., 2021; Oladeji, 2015).

Nationally, Canada has committed to 30 by 30 through Indigenous Protected and Conserved Areas - defined by the Indigenous Circle of Experts in Canada as "lands and waters where Indigenous governments have the primary role in protecting and conserving ecosystems through Indigenous laws, governance and knowledge systems" (The Indigenous Circle of Experts, 2018). For example, the Thaidene Nene IPCA is an area over 26,000 km² designated under Dene Law by the Łutsël K'é Dene First Nation and via establishment agreements with Parks Canada and the Government of the Northwest Territories (King et al., 2023).

In the Great Bear Rainforest, ecosystem-based management and large-scale conservation of 64,000 km² of coastal rainforests (Owen et al., 2023) was enabled through recognition and creation of new financing mechanisms (Curran, 2018; Riddell, 2015) including the first model (J. Persson et al., 2021) for "Project Finance for Permanence" (Le Gal et al., 2020). IPCAs have been declared by dozens of Indigenous Nations across Canada, though most remain unrecognized under crown laws and therefore face ongoing extractive pressures (Artelle et al., 2019; Mansuy et al., 2023; Youdelis et al., 2021). However, in 2022 the Government of Canada allocated CAN\$800 million to advance four marine and terrestrial Indigenous conserved areas in the Great Bear Sea, Qikiqtani, the Northwest Territories and Omushkego Wahkohtowin which would conserve over one million square km and uphold territorial rights and governance (Government of Canada, 2023) and signed a CAN\$1 billion Nature Agreement with First Nations and the Government of British Columbia.

Box SM.5.1. Future Application: Centering Indigenous Peoples' and Rights in Nature-based Solutions.

Indigenous Peoples and local communities have been harmed and face ongoing threats from the same underlying drivers of biodiversity loss, through land dispossession and industrial degradation driven by historical relations of colonialism⁴ and their current expression in modern systems. These threats have historically come from extractive pressures, yet in the present and future, they are increasingly likely to come from climate transition pressures (Owen et al., 2023) and the dispossession risks faced by Indigenous Peoples and local communities as nature-based climate finance projects expand globally (Bayrak & Marafa, 2016; Tauli-Corpuz, 2017; Tzay, 2024). For example, more than half of the anticipated critical

⁴ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

minerals needed for energy transition are located on or near Indigenous or peasant lands, posing significant threats to biodiversity values and human rights (Owen et al., 2023). Indigenous territories are also critical carbon sinks (Carlson et al., 2015; Walker & Schlacher, 2014), with Indigenous Peoples stewarding nearly one-fifth (218 gigatons) of the total carbon sequestered by tropical and subtropical forests (Rights and Resources Initiative, 2020).

Transformative actions are needed to ensure that the climate transition can “multi-solve” (de Paula, 2021) and not exacerbate existing biodiversity loss and harms to human rights. Yet, new forms of nature finance are needed to support Indigenous Peoples and local communities conservation practices and there are many considerations including safeguarding rights and recognizing tenures that could be embedded in nature-based solutions (G. Reed et al., 2024; C. Vogel et al., 2022). Respecting Indigenous Peoples and local communities human rights and establishing holistic economic and socio-cultural valuations of nature and ecosystem services through emerging forms of nature finance may be one path to address inequities and support Indigenous Peoples and local communities’ stewardship in their territories. However, for this to be transformative, nature-based solutions would be inclusive of Indigenous knowledge systems and local knowledge systems, avoiding reproducing extractive land relations or marketplace ideologies (G. Reed et al., 2024; Stoeckl et al., 2021; G. Vogel et al., 2020). If nature-based solutions and nature finance can centre and advance Indigenous Peoples and local communities’ rights, through respect for UNDRIP, FPIC and UNDROP, basing solutions on Indigenous and local community worldviews, practices and holistic economic frameworks, then this action could support more bioculturally holistic approaches to both climate action and biodiversity conservation (Nitah S, 2022; G. Reed et al., 2022; Stoeckl et al., 2021; J. Vogel et al., 2021).

Ensuring greater Indigenous Peoples and local communities’ tenure rights often foster nature rights and biodiversity (Fa et al., 2020; Garnett et al., 2018; IPBES, 2023a; United Nations, 2021b, 2021a). The protection of Indigenous Peoples and local communities’ rights, knowledge and customary tenure can support positive biodiversity outcomes (Carino & Ferrari, 2021; Chigbu et al., 2019; Tauli-Corpuz et al., 2020). However, initiatives that are able to continue to support livelihoods, such as for example of forest-dependent communities, while complying with national and international human rights frameworks and considering disparate gender impacts of conservation, have thus far been inconsistent (Agarwal, 1997; Christensen, 2008; J. Miller et al., 2011; Redford & Fearn, 2013; Songorwa, 1999; Sunderland et al., 2007; Wells & McShane, 2004). It becomes more important than ever to create synergy between livelihoods and culture, conservation (J. Persson et al., 2021) and the protection of human rights to support transformation (N. J. Bennett et al., 2024; Erinoshio et al., 2022). The following option focusing on protecting rights offers important legal strategies to complement the conservation of Indigenous Peoples and local communities’ territories.

Further actions to support recognition and conservation of the territories of Indigenous Peoples and local communities could be supported through linked mechanisms for global conservation monitoring and adaptive learning to evaluate progress of countries, donors and conservation interventions in recognizing and respecting Indigenous Peoples’ and local communities’ rights, along with reporting processes to ensure transparency, learning and redress (Tauli-Corpuz et al., 2020), which is also supported by efforts to comprehensively track ICCAs, such as through www.iccaregistry.org (World Conservation Monitoring Centre, 2024). Enforcement and

accountability could be supported by establishment of an independent mechanism for global conservation grievances that could enable access to legal supports (Makagon et al., 2014) and ‘truth and reconciliation initiatives’ for PAs which could address challenges at local and national scales (Morgera, 2019; Tauli-Corpuz et al., 2020). Additional innovative approaches and tools to advance inclusion, co-management and power-sharing for conservation initiatives include tools for dialogue such as the Whakatane Mechanism, Indigenous-led codes of ethical conduct in conservation (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2004) to recognize and respect rights and Institutions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities while supporting policies to define and negotiate resource sharing rights (Garnett et al., 2018).

Action 1.2: Enhancing legal protection for biodiversity

Changes in the legal protection of biodiversity (Gellers, 2021) are important mechanisms for biodiversity-positive transformative change. Since 2017, there has been international recognition that healthy ecosystems are essential to the protection of internationally recognized human rights - such as life, health, food, water and culture (Knox, 2017; Heinämäki, 2020; Knox, 2018b) and the right to a healthy environment (N. J. Bennett et al., 2024; UNGA, 2022), and children’s human right to a healthy environment (J. Knox, 2018a; Morgera, 2024; Shields et al., 2023; UNCRC, 2023), as well as Indigenous Peoples’ and local communities’ rights related to their territories and knowledge systems (Heinämäki, 2020), including healthy terrestrial and marine biodiversity and ecosystems (Boyd, 2020; Bennett et al., 2024).

1. Protecting human rights

Protecting human rights means ensuring freedom of expression, association and peaceful assembly and protest in relation to biodiversity, as well as protecting the rights to life, health, education, housing, livelihoods and culture that are dependent on healthy biodiversity (J. H. Knox, 2017). States that put into place this protection have heightened levels of protection for the human rights of Indigenous Peoples, peasants and small-scale fishers and other communities with historical and continued connections to places and direct reliance on natural resources and for groups in vulnerable situations (women, children, older persons, persons with disabilities, displaced persons) (J. H. Knox, 2017). Community rights-based conservation that protects biodiversity while respecting the tenure and human rights of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Rights and Resources Initiative, 2020) has resulted in ecosystems receiving greater protection such as in Benin, where the Inter-ministerial Order No. 121 of 2012 protected sacred natural sites from extractivism⁵ (Dancer, 2021).

In addition, the human right to a healthy environment entails the obligation for States to adopt and effectively monitor substantive, proportional and non-retrogressive laws, policies, institutions and management on clean air, a safe climate, healthy ecosystems and biodiversity, safe and sufficient water, non-toxic environments and healthy and sustainable food (D. R. Boyd, 2018). As a result, decisions by public authorities need to prevent unjustified, foreseeable infringements of human rights’ arising from biodiversity loss and degradation, as well as from

⁵ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

biodiversity conservation and sustainable use (J. H. Knox, 2017). The human right to a healthy environment also means that the states must mobilize the maximum available resources for fulfilling their obligations related to biodiversity, including in the context of international cooperation (D. Boyd, 2022; J. H. Knox, 2017). The human right to a healthy environment also entails obligations on ensuring public access to information, public participation in decision-making and access to justice and effective remedies (J. Knox, 2018b). This allows national courts to scrutinize whether governments have taken sufficient action to protect biodiversity and human rights and whether they have sufficiently considered the needs of the most vulnerable to biodiversity loss or degradation. Finally, human rights, including the human right to a healthy environment, entail obligations for States to effectively regulate and monitor the activities of the private companies that may negatively impact on biodiversity and responsibilities for companies themselves to respect human rights that are dependent on healthy biodiversity through explicit human rights policies, due diligence procedures and company-level grievance mechanisms (Heinämäki, 2020; J. Knox, 2018b).

This provides an existing global framework for reducing disproportionate impacts on the human rights of the most vulnerable – a phenomenon discussed in the literature as environmental injustices (N. J. Bennett et al., 2022), empowering groups in vulnerable situations (N. J. Bennett et al., 2023), enhancing compliance with biodiversity law (Koh et al., 2022) and enhancing the accountability of public authorities and private companies (N. J. Bennett et al., 2024; Morgera, 2018). It also changes the perception of the importance of biodiversity for the realization of multiple policy goals, which is significant as policy attention to biodiversity fluctuates (Morgera, 2018; Reber et al., 2022). Human rights, including the right to food, also provide protection for Indigenous Peoples and local communities' customary tenure systems (De Schutter et al., 2012; Fakhri & Puig, 2024). The literature indicates that recognizing the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity also as a matter of human rights can help prioritize public funding towards biodiversity (D. Boyd, 2022) and support States in protecting biodiversity against the vested interests of foreign investors (D. Boyd, 2023, 2024). While legal recognition does not automatically imply successful implementation (D. R. Boyd, 2011), there is a growing literature on the role of human rights in supporting transformation in biodiversity governance (Ituarte-Lima, 2023; Lombard et al., 2022; Morgera, 2024; Switzer et al., 2022; Webster & Morgera, 2021).

A promising strategy to help reduce environmental injustices is, thus, to require by law immediate measures to prevent or minimize foreseeable negative human rights impacts arising from the loss or degradation of biodiversity. For instance, in South Africa offshore oil and gas exploration via seismic surveys were blocked by courts due to biodiversity and climate change concerns, on the basis of the negative impacts on the cultural rights and livelihoods of Indigenous Peoples and small-scale fishers (McGarry, 2023; *Sustaining the Wild Coast NPC and Others v Minister of Mineral Resources and Energy and Others*, 2022).

2. Expanding rights-based frameworks with nature rights

Transformative change requires equitable and inclusive governance through rights-based approaches (Franks, 2021) that shift from a human-centred focus. Earth system law seeks to remedy these shortcomings (Auz, 2022) by introducing a systems approach to environmental law

and governance (Mai & Boulot, 2021) that also includes non-human entities⁶ (Gellers, 2021). Earth jurisprudence is another approach that adopts an inclusive and system based theoretical perspective which combines earth and social justice (Koons, 2009). It has been advanced under the UN theme of ‘Harmony with Nature’ (Dancer, 2021) and is expressed in the Universal Declaration of the Rights of Mother Earth that calls for a more eco-centric approach to environmental law and governance (Cullinan, 2010). The interconnectedness of humans and nature is also emphasized by Earth Democracy that embraces the Indian concept of ‘Earth Family’ (Navdanya international, 2018). It recognizes the rights of nature, which are connected to human rights (Shiva, 2021).

Rights of nature is an emerging legal paradigm in some countries and localities based on diverse values that can support pluralist ecological jurisprudence (Guayasamin et al., 2021; Hsiao, 2012; Magallanes, 2018; Wesche, 2021) and overcome western and neoliberal legal models that emphasize individual over collective wellbeing (O’Donnell et al., 2020). They entail recognizing a natural entity as a living entity with rights equivalent to human rights (Hsiao, 2012) in national constitutions or legislation, as well as assigning them human guardians. In some places, human guardians have obtained legal rights for rivers, e.g., in New Zealand for the Whanganui River based on the 2017 ‘Te Awa Tupua Act’, (Collins & Esterling, 2019; Hsiao, 2012; Wesche, 2021), in Ecuador, for the Vilcabamba River (2008-2011), in Colombia for the Rio Altrato in 2017 (Wesche, 2021) and in India for the Ganga and Yamuna rivers (Chaturvedi, 2019). Based on constitutional rights, the Ecuadorian Constitutional Court judged that the Los Cedros forest's rights have been violated based on which mining permits in the forest were revoked (Kinkaid, 2019). Similar approaches have been applied in the United States of America by the Rights of Natural Communities in the City of Pittsburgh and by the City of Santa Monica, California (Magallanes, 2018).

The rights of nature exist in various Indigenous worldviews, traditional societies and world religions, but -through the process of modernization and colonialization- this legal paradigm has been overshadowed by framings of nature as a resource. The association of nature with human rights (Challe, 2021; Cullinan, 2023) that combines the nature for nature and nature as culture perspectives is a common framing among many Indigenous Peoples and local communities, land-based cultures and some religions (Surma, 2021) where nature has over generations, been ascribed rights (e.g., sacred groves, abstinence from exploiting fishing during periods of regeneration, unwritten prohibition of hunting young animals or harvesting immature seeds/seedlings) (Marshall et al., 2019). Where they persist, they have been effective in protecting and maintaining biodiversity (Kumar et al., 2022; Ray et al., 2014; Sharma & Kumar, 2020). The Rights of Nature, when combined with customary instruments of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, can strengthen collective rights and promote equitable natural resource management (Kelemen et al., 2022).

Assigning nature rights (1) increases awareness about the legal status of the natural entities, (2) provides an additional legal basis for public authorities and courts to decide against activities that harm ecosystems and biodiversity and (3) potentially transforms the legal context. The human rights of Indigenous Peoples and local communities and the rights of nature can be mutually beneficial (Etchart, 2022; Garnett et al., 2018; Gilbert, 2022; Tanasescu, 2020) and can support the implementation of environmental law (DARPÖ, 2021). While recognizing rights of

⁶ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

nature can trigger change, such change is place-based, takes time (Kinkaid, 2019) and its immediate impacts focus on improving policy making, enhancing environmental awareness, strengthening the standings of the Ministry of the Environment and local communities (Collins & Esterling, 2019). Implementing rights of nature in settings of weak governance and limited resources is likely not to achieve the expected positive impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity (Collins & Esterling, 2019). In developing country contexts, financial resources for "nature guardians" to follow-up on court decisions are lacking. (O'Donnell, 2018) highlights that assigning legal rights to the Ganges and Yamuna rivers moves environmental law from public law towards private law.

Legal recognition of the rights of nature through the instrument of legal personhood (Earth Law Centre, 2021; Hsiao, 2012) has been done under different legal systems worldwide (ICEL, 2021) such as constitutions, national legislation, local and tribal laws including litigation (The Anima Mundi Law Initiative, 2021). It demonstrates a Nature for Nature perspective. Examples include the 2008 Montecristi Constitution of Ecuador, which recognized the Rights of Nature, or Pacha Mama (Cano Pecharroman, 2018; Kinkaid, 2019; Prieto, 2021). For more examples, see table SM.5.8 below.

Table SM.5.3. Countries in which the rights of nature are recognized at different levels.

Country	Examples of recognition of rights of nature
Bangladesh	All rivers are considered living entities with rights as legal persons (Margil, 2014).
Bolivia	It passed the Law on the Rights of Mother Earth in December 2010 and the Framework Law on Mother Earth and Holistic Development for Living Well in 2012 (Boyd, 2018).
Brazil	Several local communities in Brazil have enacted rights of nature laws including the municipality of Paudalho (Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights, 2024)
Canada	In 2021, the Innu Council of Ekuanitshit and the Minganie Regional County Municipality made twin resolutions that recognized the legal rights of Canada's Magpie River (Cárdenas & Mestokosho, 2023; Conseil des INNU de EKUANITS, 2021; Le Monde, 2022; Millán, 2023). The river bears nine rights and can be legally represented by guardians responsible for ensuring that these rights are respected (Challe, 2021).
Colombia	The Constitutional Court recognized the legal rights of the Atrato River in 2017. This has been extended to about 10 other ecosystems, including the entire Colombian Amazon (Earth Law Centre, 2021). Similar to New Zealand, the court ordered the government to create a guardian for the river composed of one state representative and one Indigenous representative to safeguard the river's rights (Boyd, 2018).
Ecuador	In 2008, it became the first country to recognize the Rights of Nature (Pachamama) in its Constitution (Earth Law Centre, 2021). This was then incorporated into several laws and policies, including the criminal and environmental code (Boyd, 2018).

Country	Examples of recognition of rights of nature
India	The River Ganga, River Yamuna and the Himalayan glaciers of Gangotri and Yamunotri were declared legal entities by the High Court (Earth Law Centre, 2021). In addition, Mother Nature was declared a living being with constitutional rights by the High Court (Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights, 2024). In that case, the court invoked its ‘parent of the nation’ (parens patriae) jurisdiction to direct the relevant government to take steps to guard Mother Nature (Surma, 2021).
Mexico	In Mexico City and the States of Guerrero and Colima have recognized the Rights of Nature (Earth Law Centre, 2021).
New Zealand	Through the Te Awa Tupua (Whanganui River Claims Settlement) Act 2017, the Whanganui River is recognized as a legal person (Surma, 2021). Also, two guardians of the river were appointed. One from the Maori Indigenous Peoples and another from the government, (Challe, 2021). Other examples include Mount Taranaki (Earth Law Centre, 2021) and the Urewera forest (through the Te Urewera Act 2014) that are also legal persons (Boyd, 2018).
Northern Ireland	In 2021, the Derry City and Strabane District Council and the Fermanagh and Omagh District Council approved motions on the rights of nature (Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights).
Panama	In 2022, Panama enacted Law No. 287 -Chapter II-Rights of Nature, recognizing the rights of nature within the nation’s legal system (Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights).
Philippines	The Supreme Court Rules of Procedure for Environmental Cases established the writ of kalikasan (nature) that is intended to protect nature’s intrinsic value without the legal requirement for proving harm to people (Boyd, 2018).
Uganda	Recognized the Rights of Nature in their Environmental Act 2019 (Earth Law Centre, 2021).
United States	In 2010, the City Council of Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania unanimously passed an ordinance recognizing the Rights of Nature (Challe, 2021). In 2017 Lafayette, Colorado enacted municipal rights of nature laws (Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights, 2024). In 2019, the city of Toledo, Ohio adopted the Lake Erie Bill of Rights that gave the lake rights of its own (Challe, 2021). In November 2020, the voters of Orange County, Florida, approved of the first rights of nature law in the state (Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights, 2024).

However, questions remain about the lasting impacts of recognizing nature’s rights, as their success depends on court decisions, which can vary from case to case. Further, under-researched question concern how other environmental policy and law instruments such as environmental impact assessments interact with the rights of nature; and whether rights of nature also raise “responsibilities” of nature. There are also doubts in the literature about whether nature’s rights

may be a more effective approach to protect biodiversity than other legal approaches (Bétaille, 2019; Guim & Livermore, 2021; Jansen, 2024). Another question is whether nature's rights and ocean's rights require differentiated protection (Nadow et al., 2023; Pyć, 2023). Indigenous leaders of New Zealand, Tahiti and the Cook Islands signed a treaty that recognizes whales' legal personhood and Māori leaders and other leaders from throughout the Pacific have proposed a resolution recognizing legal personality to whales as ocean ambassadors at the United Nations. An example of its enactment is the declaration by the Brazil Supreme Court that the Paris Agreement on climate change is a human rights treaty that should supersede national law (UNEP, 2022).

3. Adding the prevention of the crime of ecocide

There has also been a growing movement to criminalize ecocide to advance the idea that the Earth is intrinsically worthy of protection (Surma, 2021). The recognition of ecocide as an environmental crime can thus provide an additional layer of enhanced accountability (Higgins et al., 2013; Killean & Short, 2023; Lindgren, 2018; Yadav et al., 2022) and challenge vested interests (Larsen, 2012) extractivism and militarization (Dunlap & Brock, 2022). Nationally, laws on ecocide have been passed in 11 countries and similar legislative proposals are being considered by another 27 countries (J. Gill, 2023). The European Union recently agreed to criminalize environmental harms comparable to ecocide (Stop Ecocide International (SEI), 2023). Ecuador's Penal Code includes "crimes against the environment and nature or Pacha Mama and crimes against biodiversity" (Article 245). France's 'Climate & Resilience Act' (2021) punishes ecocide (Article 231-3), with up to 10 years imprisonment for those committing offences which "cause serious and lasting damage to health, flora, fauna or the quality of the air, soil or water." There is also a movement to recognize ecocide as an international crime, with a view to placing ecocide on the same level as genocide or crimes against humanity (Independent Expert Panel, 2021). While ecocide is recognized as an option to "stigmatize the most egregious environmental wrongdoing", its definition and effectiveness remain a matter of debate (J. Robinson, 2022).

Action 1.3: Basing conservation on diverse values of nature to achieve inclusive biodiversity protection

Protected Areas (PAs) are increasingly being expanded across the globe, with the goal to achieving KM-GBF Target 3: to conserve 30% of lands, waters and seas by 2030 (Lessa et al., 2021). PAs are seen as a primary approach to address biodiversity decline (Gurney et al., 2023) and achieve global targets (Bailey, 2023). Although there is no single pathway (Lessa et al., 2021), it is crucial to be strategic about what to protect and where; and have a better understanding of the multiple values PAs can generate (Bernard et al., 2014).

For example, the effectiveness of intrinsic values in conserving biodiversity is captured largely in the traditional protected areas discourse and mirrored in Half Earth framings (E. Wilson, 2016). Closing the high seas to fishing as a first step to enabling a more equitable share of the ocean's bounty (as the majority of those fishing in the high seas are done by high-income nations) could be a recommendation that sits between a Nature for Nature and a Nature for Society framing

(Schiller et al., 2018; Sumaila et al., 2015). Although strict protected areas have traditionally claimed to provide positive impact on biodiversity (G. B. Ferreira et al., 2020; H. M. Ferreira et al., 2022; D. A. Gill et al., 2017), impacts of multiple-use PAs have been mixed with some positive results on environmental outcomes (McNicol et al., 2023; Schleicher et al., 2017), particularly when taking into consideration the counterfactuals of no protection. Insights gained about sustainable use across various extractive (e.g., fishing, gathering) and non-extractive practices can help inform multiple use areas (IPBES, 2022c).

However, the effectiveness of PAs to conserve biodiversity has come under criticism (Büscher & Fletcher, 2019, 2020; Massarella et al., 2022; Obura et al., 2021, 2023). Others, for instance, might view strict PAs to have less biodiversity outcomes (Ferraro et al., 2013), with exclusion of local people, leading to challenges with monitoring (Danielsen et al., 2005). The question of equity is especially compelling against the looming 30x30 as the emphasis of strict PAs on protection of most species possible can produce very different outcomes especially when delivery of benefits to people is concerned. Many Nature for Society framings include the development of PAs for ecotourism, providing local jobs and livelihoods when consciously and carefully planned (Forje & Tchamba, 2022). The viability of ecotourism in generating economic development while conserving the environment, promoting cultural diversity and encouraging community involvement and education has been illustrated in the Galapagos, Costa Rica, Alaska and Mozambique (Lanier, 2014), or the MPAs in Palua and Fiji (Enrici et al., 2023).

An often overlooked, but important pathway is informed by a more Nature as Culture/One with Nature value perspective, which is also enshrined in Target 22 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework that ensures inclusive decision-making with Indigenous Peoples and local communities and other groups. The strong cultural and spiritual link that Indigenous Peoples and local communities have with their territories (Dudley et al., 2009) highlight the relational value of nature as culture, illustrated in Estonia through the sacred forest groves (Gurney et al., 2023). The Adat communities' relations with their territories have helped to protect the forests against industrial conversion and conserve biodiversity. Indigenous led approaches have highlighted innovative ways to design conservation reserves, environmental policy instruments, wildlife monitoring and management programmes (Garnett et al., 2018; Raymond et al., 2010; Tengö et al., 2014; Vigilante et al., 2017).

Action 1.4: Shifting extractive land-use systems to regenerative views, structures and practices

A growing number of studies and initiatives argue that a widespread transition to regenerative views, structures and practices is “a critical task facing humanity” (Buckton et al., 2023). These approaches have their origins in Indigenous worldviews (Sands et al., 2023). A common theme is the need to move beyond sustainability, recognizing ecological damage and designing to produce mutual benefits across socio-ecological systems⁷ (Mang & Reed, 2012). Building regenerative capacities are important, i.e., the ability of complex, interconnected, whole living systems to renew themselves whether in agricultural, forestry, or urban landscapes (Mang & Haggard, 2016). Humans participate as nature, not controlling it (Lyle, 1996; B. Reed, 2007; Wahl, 2016).

⁷ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Spirituality⁷ is infused in relations of interbeing and interdependence (Wahl, 2016). Regenerative systems tend to relational values and responsibilities by nourishing human-nature relations and taking responsibility for past and future (Gordon, 2023).

This requires moving beyond settler colonial ideas of sustainability (Mazzocchi, 2020) and restoration (Grenz & Armstrong, 2023). It involves addressing colonialism, extraction, degradation and the modernist extractive worldviews that currently dominate systems, decisions and policy (Poelina et al., 2022). Going further than technical restoration practices and transforming the social systems that landscapes are interconnected with (Gordon, 2023) is an important facet of regeneration. It includes reviving rural communities (Gordon et al., 2022, 2023) and supporting the emergence of bioregional regenerative cultures (Wahl, 2016). In regenerative cultures people cultivate and support positive reinforcing cycles of wellbeing and cyclical understandings of nature and reality (Fath et al., 2019; L. V. Gibbons, 2020; Gordon, 2023; Gosnell et al., 2019). As such, regeneration entails a transformative shift in how ecosystems are *viewed* by those managing land – becoming more attune to *being regenerative* (Seymour & Connelly, 2023) in their behaviours and relationships.

Disempowering the views, structures and practices associated with extractive land-use can co-occur with strategies that empower regenerative views, structures and practices in these sectors (James et al., 2021). For example, agriculture degrades biodiversity by converting natural habitats to intensively managed systems (Dudley et al., 2017). Even in agricultural systems, more than 70% of global agrobiodiversity has been lost (Holt-Giménez & Altieri, 2013). Conservation policies in the past have focussed on agricultural intensification, which has not prevented biodiversity loss (Dudley et al., 2017). However, biocultural regeneration means maintaining the interrelationships between people and nature to support cultural values, sustainable production and biodiversity in agricultural landscapes (J. B. C. Jackson, 2007; LaCanne & Lundgren, 2018; Norris, 2008; Rey Benayas & Bullock, 2012; Scherr & McNeely, 2008). This includes funding the restoration and reclamation of Indigenous languages, which are pillars of biodiversity conservation (Frainer et al., 2020; Wilder et al., 2016). Such policies could support and establish agroecological and regenerative food systems that decentralise power through food sovereignty initiatives and empower Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Huambachano, 2020; James et al., 2021). Indicators of agricultural regeneration may involve quantitative measures (Newton et al., 2020) but also qualitative measures like relational values (Anderson et al., 2022; Himes et al., 2024; Sands et al., 2023). Such policies might support peer social learning and pathways for young people and new farmers to access land (Day et al., 2022); e.g., co-operatives or agrarian land trusts.

Other examples include permaculture, an ecological design system integrating human habitats and food production based on Indigenous Peoples' knowledge (Mang & Reed, 2020), biophilic design, biomimicry and living buildings (Hes & Plessis, 2014). In agriculture, holistic land management frameworks (Allan Savory) and ongoing organic restoration of complex living systems based upon healthy soils (Robert Rodale) are important (Mang & Reed, 2020). Definitions include processes (e.g., reducing tillage) and/or outcomes (e.g., improved soil health, increased biodiversity) (Newton et al., 2020). In food systems, regenerative agriculture⁸ is a discursive alternative to industrial-productivist systems (Gordon et al., 2022). Agricultural work

⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

sits in nested, living systems, with the overall system having capacities to self-renew via continual learning and departures from industrial approaches to varying extents (Gordon et al., 2022), including wholesale shifts to food commoning (Duncan et al., 2020). In landscape design, regenerative principles and values are integrated into development and design frameworks and technologies (L. Gibbons et al., 2018). Regenerative cities create mutually enhancing relations with any natural systems that sustain them (Girardet, 2015). Regenerative businesses generate value for all stakeholders, while enhancing socio-ecological wellbeing and human potential (Sanford, 2017). Regenerative economy concepts propose a regenerative form of capitalism⁸ (Fullerton, 2015), operating within Earth boundaries (Raworth, 2017) and requiring business, governmental and civic cooperation for natural and social capital regeneration (Lovins, 2019).

Landscape approaches have been considered a useful tool for conservation and restoration of ecosystems along with local communities. It takes an integrated view of the relationship between society, culture and ecosystems and considers factors such as the involvement of diverse stakeholders and local agencies, especially Indigenous and local knowledge (DeFries & Rosenzweig, 2010; Estrada-Carmona et al., 2014; Kremen & Merenlender, 2018; Takeuchi et al., ; Vonthron et al., 2020). For example, the Japanese satoyama and satoumi, or socioecological production landscapes and seascapes in a scientific term, is a good example which have been shaped and traditionally managed through its long history. SEPLS is “a mosaic of various types of ecosystems (e.g., farmlands, secondary forests, wetlands, coastal zones and human settlements)” and “the areas where production activities help maintain biodiversity and ecosystem services in various forms while sustainably supporting the livelihoods and well-being of local communities.” As the areas have been historically formed, it is also considered as cultural landscapes and Indigenous and local knowledge plays a vital role for the maintenance (Cetinkaya, 2009). Other similar conceptual frameworks of landscape approaches related to biodiversity have been raised such as integrated landscape management (Estrada-Carmona et al., 2014), foodscape (Vonthron et al., 2020), whole-landscape approach (De Fries & Rosenzweig, 2010), bioregional planning (De Fries & Rosenzweig, 2010) and biodiversity-related landscape planning (De Fries & Rosenzweig, 2010; Vonthron et al., 2020), whole-landscape approach (De Fries & Rosenzweig, 2010), bioregional planning (Brunckhorst, 2001), multifunctional landscape landscapes (Naveh, 2001) and working landscapes (Kremen & Merenlender, 2018).

4. How intentional transformative change occurs in regeneration

Change in regenerative approaches is intentional, involving active participatory design processes (Manzini, 2015) for co-creation with nature, appropriate human participation as nature and ecological principles e.g., biomimicry, nutrient cycling, soil care (M. S. Reed et al., 2009; Wahl, 2016). Specific pathways for change include design practice, education, community living (Wahl, 2016). Change is achieved through leverage in systems, facilitated by designs with the wider socio-ecological system in mind, creating conditions for self-renewal, adaptiveness and healthy flourishing of all life through regenerative cultures (Wahl, 2016). Regenerative capacities are strengthened across built, cultural and natural environments (Mang & Reed, 2020).

Regenerative design solutions refer specifically to systems of technologies and strategies, generated from place particularities and understandings of whole living systems to manifest their inherent capacity for vitality and evolution (Mang & Reed, 2020). Regenerative development is

broader, providing whole understandings of place and stakeholder capability strengthening for maximum systemic leverage so living beings can co-evolve and planetary self-expression in diversity, complexity and creativity (Mang & Reed, 2012). Regenerative development manifests potentials for health, wellbeing and happiness of all system members, shifts in worldviews, deep inhabitant and practitioner engagement in collaborative processes, attention to supportive infrastructures for mutualistic relations between dynamic system components, value addition across scales and individual and local efforts coordinated within larger scale, regional initiatives to grow wider system regenerative capacity (L. Gibbons et al., 2018).

Partnership with place (moving from a notion of control to one of cultivation and collaboration) and progressive harmonisation (continual improvement of harmony between human and natural systems) can achieve change (Mang & Reed, 2020). Regenerative discourses may support change through bringing together relevant coalitions which share goals and principles, plus translocal organizing and collective learning, but tensions exist between discourses and there are opportunities for greenwashing and co-optation (Gordon et al., 2023).

Box SM.5.2. Transforming forest governance and management through community forestry in Nepal.

To stop deteriorating environmental conditions (e.g., deforestation, forest degradation and soil erosion) in the hills of Nepal and also to supply forest products (e.g., firewood, timber, fodder) to forest dependent local communities, the concept of community forestry started in late 1970s (Pandit & Bevilacqua, 2011b). Since then, community forestry has evolved as a major forestry programme with specific focus in the hills until 1993 before it became a nationwide programme. Through collective efforts of the communities (participation and taking responsibilities for governance) and government (policy formulation and revisions, facilitation of the process and technical support), this programme became a transformative example of decentralized forest governance that empowers local communities to manage national forests as community forests in accordance to the rules and practices decided by the communities. Since its inception in late 1970s by mid-2020, a total of 22,519 community forests with an area of 2,312,545 hectares (i.e., 34.98% of total forest area) are being managed by 3,088,259 households benefiting over 16,606,148 people (i.e., 62.68% of total population) (Pandey & Pokhrel, 2021). Community forestry has contributed to restore forest cover (A. Smith et al., 2023), improve hill environment (Pandit & Bevilacqua, 2011a), empower and transform local communities (Ojha & Hall, 2023) and increase the forest area of Nepal. Evidence suggests that forest and other wooded areas in Nepal increased from 39.6% in 1994 (DFRS, 1999) to 44.74% in 2014 of the total area of the country (147,181 Km²) (DFRS, 2015). It is a pioneering and transformative example of community-led and government-supported forest management and governance programme.

5. Protect All Life, Kisa MacIsaac, Métis artist, educator and facilitator (figure 5.6)

Protect All Life is a contribution of artist Kisa MacIsaac, Métis artist and educator to accompany “Balancing the Narrative: Communications Guidelines for Indigenous-led Conservation” a publication to shed light on the enduring impacts of colonialism, offering anti-oppressive approaches for communicating with and about Indigenous conservation leadership in the

Canadian context, by providing a framework to co-develop communications strategies and content with First Nations, Inuit and Métis partners in respectful, reciprocal and responsible ways. “In my artwork (a mix of acrylic painting and digital illustration), I sought to capture the powerful connection and interconnectedness between nature and humanity, in the context of this land we call Canada—both our history and present-day realities. Woven together are plants, insects, berries, water, sky, people, land—no one more important than the other—no hierarchies: symbolic of the delicate balance that sustains our ecosystems and how all life on earth should be valued as equal and worthy of protection from colonization, land theft, war and direct exploitation of organisms. A reminder that our relationship with the land should be rooted in stewardship and harmony, as has been the case for Indigenous Peoples around the world for thousands of years. We must speak up, we must act, we must fight for justice and liberation of all oppressed peoples, for the protection of children and for all life on the planet. All my relations and kinanaskomitinawaw - I am grateful to you all.”

Action 1.5: Advancing integrated spatial planning

Setting and successfully implementing spatial planning targets requires enabling conditions, personnel and financial capacities and depends on whether actors can equitably use opportunities in the planning process to achieve the planning targets (Kiessling & Pütz, 2021; Simeonova et al., 2017). Consideration of synergies between restoring ecological processes, biodiversity and ecosystem services can yield multiple benefits from spatial planning (Van der Biest et al., 2020). Strategies to promote the integration of biodiversity and ecosystems services into spatial planning include spatially explicit mapping, among others, of key biodiversity areas, landscape heterogeneity and mainstreaming across levels and sectors (C. Albert et al., 2020; Harlio et al., 2019; Harris et al., 2022; Holness et al., 2022; Martinuzzi et al., 2018; Plumptre et al., 2023).

Globally, biosphere reserves in UNESCO’s Man and the Biosphere (MAB) Programme cover about 7.9 million km² of which 82 % (6.7 million km²) are buffer zones and transition areas and have over 276 million people living and working in them (Barraclough & Måren, 2022), combining biodiversity conservation with sustainable social and economic development and can serve as models for implementing the targets and goals of the Global Biodiversity Framework (e.g., Target 3, 2 and 1) and the 2030 Agenda (Barraclough & Måren, 2022; M. G. Reed & Price, 2019). Progress has also been made towards more sustainable inland fisheries by involving under-represented groups into fisheries and water management, enhancing biodiversity and wellbeing outcomes (Lynch et al., 2020).

6. Right relations for regeneration and transformative change

An example of biocultural and regenerative values is the concept of right relations. Colonial dynamics that have historically supported extraction and oppression necessitate a fundamental shift towards 'right relations' to foster equitable and sustainable interactions (Collard et al., 2015; Regan, 2010). Right relations emphasize respect, reciprocity and justice in dealings not only among humans, including Indigenous and non-Indigenous Peoples, but also with the natural world and beyond (Gram-Hanssen, 2021). This concept extends to maintaining a balanced

relationship with the past, present and future, as well as with the physical and spiritual realms, as articulated by (Ross, 2014).

(Yunkaporta, 2023) introduces the concept of 'right story,' which emphasizes the narratives and metaphors shared by interconnected communities that live in harmony with their environment. These stories, derived from group experiences rather than individual narratives, highlight the importance of collective wisdom in shaping interactions with the land and each other. Such perspectives challenge the Western notion of the self as separate from others and the environment, offering broader possibilities for transformative changes in societal values and practices (Foggin et al., 2021; N. Hopkins et al., 2016; Munera-Roldan, 2023; Nightingale et al., 2020; Petrescu-Mag et al., 2022; Pisters et al., 2019).

(Dawson et al., 2021) emphasize that effective conservation and quality of life improvements are contingent on recognizing and empowering local social and cultural practices of Indigenous Peoples and local communities. These communities' deep-seated social-ecological knowledge and governance systems need to be integrated into decision-making processes at higher levels, moving beyond local community engagement to national and international governance frameworks (Díaz-Reviriego et al., 2019; Folke, 2004). Latin America's experience with decentralised conservation governance illustrates the benefits of such integration, enhancing local institutional recognition and supporting community-led conservation efforts on a global scale (Larson & Soto, 2008; Tran et al., 2020).

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Annex 5.3. Strategy 2

Approaches for Strategy 2

This section summarizes different existing approaches to drive systemic change in the sectors most responsible for nature's decline. It highlights the success of the different approaches. Regardless of the approach, actions and instruments within strategy 2 may influence decision-making during the initial phase of the transformation, contributing to unlocking regimes, but they need to be articulated with longer term actions to ensure the phasing out of old regimes and the expansion of sustainable alternatives.

Figure SM.5.6. Instruments within strategy 2 and their links to the transformative change process.

1. Mainstreaming biodiversity

Positioning biodiversity and sustainability as a fundamental criterion for designing governmental taxes, subsidies and support schemes including development funding can (if adequately designed) lead to the internalization of environmental costs and an economic boost for biodiversity supportive business models. “Mainstreaming biodiversity” refers to the process of embedding biodiversity considerations into policies, strategies and practices of key public and private actors that directly impact nature to complement to nature stewardship actions (Whitehorn et al., 2019). Mainstreaming biodiversity is recognized by the Convention on Biological Diversity and its Aichi Targets and, while nonbinding, can be implemented through National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs, see strategy 4). If implemented

effectively, in the long-term mainstreaming biodiversity is expected to produce a shared sense of responsibility among diverse stakeholders, empower a proactive and preventative response to nature decline and help businesses and investors manage risk and opportunity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022b; Å. Persson et al., 2018). Mainstreaming biodiversity is emphasized across sectoral international institutions, agreements and conventions, as it is promoted by FAO in relation to the agricultural sector (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2020b). To date, however, success in mainstreaming biodiversity into economic policy has been patchy at best. Awareness of the importance of mainstreaming biodiversity across economic sectors is reflected in NBSAPs in some developing countries, particularly in Africa, where the NBSAP development process has involved a broad range of stakeholders (S. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen et al., 2018; Whitehorn et al., 2019). Mainstreaming biodiversity can be accelerated by setting enabling conditions, such as functional institutions and adequate funding (Milner-Gulland et al., 2021). For example, setting co-management structures in mangroves in Vietnam involving fishermen and local authorities and trust building in certified palm oil and marine fisheries have aided mainstreaming (Whitehorn et al., 2019). Public, private actors and civil society are important for mainstreaming biodiversity in sectors, each with separate but interrelated roles and responsibilities.

Mainstreaming biodiversity within sectors is more likely to succeed if biodiversity is aligned with the core values and – economic – interests of primary producers, other actors throughout supply chains and consumers. Positive impacts of mainstreaming have been reported in South Africa and Costa Rica, countries that have shown strong political support (Huntley, 2014) and in the fisheries sector, where improved communication has enabled cross-sectoral institutional collaborations on policies and actions (Friedman et al., 2018).

Mainstreaming biodiversity largely relies on a utilitarian framing that considers “nature-as-natural-capital”, focusing on the economic value of nature (W. M. Adams, 2014), thus overseeing the plurality of values that are needed for successfully protecting biodiversity, (IPBES, 2022b; Spash & Aslaksen, 2015). Mainstreaming biodiversity is enacted through processes of commensuration (i.e., enhancing the comparability of nature), aggregation (i.e., a preference of total quantities over qualitative specificity) and capitalization (i.e., producing natural assets). It embodies an ontological understanding of nature as something to be used and managed to meet human needs and preferences, thereby representing instrumental values (S. Sullivan, 2018).

2. No-net-loss or net positive impact (Mitigation Hierarchy approach)

The No-net-loss approach refers to a hierarchy of measures companies can take to reduce their impacts on nature decline and create positive contributions, also referred to as the conservation hierarchy (Arlidge et al., 2018). The approach proposes four steps to mitigate the direct, attributable biodiversity impacts of a project. The first step (avoid the impact) consists in determining the impact of a company, which serves as the baseline situation for monitoring progress. The second step (minimize the impact) refers to measures oriented to avoiding and mitigating the impact. The third step (restore/remediate) refers to measures that can be implemented to restore the biodiversity affected by the impact. The fourth step includes offsetting any residual impact to achieve "no net loss" or "net gain" of biodiversity overall, when compensation measures can be taken to create positive impacts (de Silva et al., 2019).

There has been an increase in policies applying Mitigation Hierarchy principles to address the environmental impacts of companies and governments (de Silva et al., 2019; Zu Ermgassen, Utamiputri, et al., 2019). Despite its extensive use, there is no evidence of its effectiveness. While some governments have taken on “no net loss” pledges for biodiversity, the regulatory apparatus for these promises has fallen short, whether in permit procedures, impact assessments, or market incentives (Maron et al., 2018). A reviewed corporate-level NNL and NPI commitments over the last two decades to establish the extent of their adoption, retraction and scientific foundation suggest that while the numbers of companies making commitments increases, they may not be delivering as intended (de Silva et al., 2019). In general, the application of the Mitigation Hierarchy has resulted in an over-reliance on offsetting rather than avoidance (Phalan et al., 2018), lack of monitoring and compliance (Zu Ermgassen, Baker, et al., 2019), poor design (Maron et al., 2018) and insufficient institutional knowledge and capacity, leading to non-equivalence between biodiversity gains and losses (Brownlie et al., 2017). There is also an increasing recognition of the need to integrate the application of NNL or NPI targets for biodiversity with social considerations, so people affected by development impacts and biodiversity mitigation actions are left no worse off (and preferably better off), particularly with respect to their values for nature (J. Bull et al., 2018; J. P. G. Jones, Bull, et al., 2019).

The Mitigation and Conservation Hierarchy expands the Mitigation Hierarchy in two ways (Milner-Gulland et al., 2021). First, it is designed to be used by sectors and impacts where the Mitigation Hierarchy has not yet been widely applied, including entities, such as city councils, community groups and individuals and sectors, including natural resource exploitation (e.g., agriculture, fisheries and forestry), where the impacts are sometimes geographically dispersed through long, complex value chains. Consequently, it goes beyond mitigating biodiversity impacts that are direct by-products of development (e.g., habitat destruction by an infrastructure project) to also address the impacts of resource exploitation (e.g., the effect of timber extraction on a forest ecosystem). Second, it adds a conservation element that goes beyond mitigating direct negative impacts to encompass *any* activities affecting nature (positive or negative, attributable to specific entities or not, past, or current). This means that conservation actions to address historical, systemic and non-attributable biodiversity loss can be accounted for in the same framework as actions to mitigate specific impacts. In addition, the fourth step of the MCH expands beyond offsetting to encompass proactive actions beyond those directly tied to redressing current attributable impacts, to achieve an overall NPI (such as greening cities; (Milner-Gulland et al., 2021).

3. Nature-based solutions

Nature-based solutions are ‘actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being⁹, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits’ (Palomo et al., 2021; UNEP Environment Assembly, 2022). Nature-based solutions can offer significant opportunities for transformative change (Wamsler et al., 2016). Nature-based solutions have evinced the capacity to deal with the global environmental challenges and crises, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution and are currently supported by policies

⁹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

such as Targets 8 and 11 of the Convention on Biological Diversity's Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, the European Union Climate Adaptation Strategy (2021), and the EU Biodiversity Strategy (2020). Legislative support is more effective when accompanied by practical adaptation across various sectoral (e.g., agriculture, water) and thematic (e.g., climate, circularity) policy agendas (Frantzeskaki et al., 2019; Göpfert et al., 2019, 2020; Palomo et al., 2021). Implementing monitoring and evaluation systems that feed in an evidence base of their multiple benefits alongside the wider adoption of Nature-based solutions has been found to be beneficial .

Yet there are still important challenges to address regarding the implementation of Nature-based Solutions. Recent research on the effectiveness, governance and practice of Nature-based solutions highlights key limitations and pitfalls relate to the focus on natural capital markets to finance their scaling up. Moreover, market-based mechanisms present significant governance challenges and risk further entrenching power asymmetries (Chausson et al., 2023). For example, new landscape-scale approaches to managing multifunctionality in ecosystems can propose to offset the biodiversity and climatic effects of agricultural commodity farming such as palm oil or soya. But research has also shown that protected nature and carbon sinks and stocks in these landscapes (such as High Carbon Stock) can also imply land cover that excludes smallholder (including Indigenous) agriculture, which offers livelihoods and distinctive biodiversity (Dymond et al., 2007; Kull, 2004; Minang et al., 2015), suggesting the need to balance objectives. Large-scale reforestation using a limited number of species can also be claimed to be nature-based but most often do little for biodiversity or local rights (Seddon et al., 2020, 2021). There is consequently a need for knowledge systems that, according to the multilaterally agreed definition of Nature-based solutions, frame and evaluate interventions in terms of diverse objectives, including biodiversity, livelihoods and local rights, rather than representing average carbon and biodiversity as beneficial to all stakeholders.

Co-financing between public and private actors has been identified as a key steppingstone to design and maintain urban Nature-based solutions (Tozer et al., 2020, 2022). Opportunities to invest in Nature-based solutions, such as through credit-based schemes, also provide an avenue to meet corporate commitment for biodiversity and climate, while increasing, in theory, the flows of finance to people and biodiversity (Finance Earth, 2021). For some mechanisms, such as green bonds, the scattered and small-scale nature of most Nature-based solutions also conflicts with the large-scale nature of portfolios needed to attract private finance (Barbier, 2022). There has been a particularly strong push by the private sector and multilateral bodies to attract private capital flows for Nature-based solutions, including through blended finance schemes whereby public grant funding is used to stimulate finance from private and institutional financiers by mitigating investment risks (Lankes, 2021). Similarly, there has been increasing attention to the different roles that the insurance sector can play in relation to Nature-based solutions, to build resilience in the context of probable increased level of damages, and to help decrease risk related to investments in nature (Costa et al., 2020; Lopez-Gunn et al., 2021).

4. Technology-based solutions

Some social actors show high confidence in the potential of technological solutions for transformative change, but using technologies for transformative change is better done by examining how far technologies contribute to deeper changes in production and consumption.

Indeed, the transformative potential of some useful technologies, such as smart electricity meters, might be exaggerated if their application focuses on electricity use, and does not consider how electricity is generated or used (Sovacool et al., 2021). Moreover, focusing on “innovation” might not always be appropriate if older or pre-existing technologies have positive impacts on sustainability. For example, many Indigenous forms of agriculture have been shown to foster diverse forms of biodiversity (Colchester, 1994). Yet, promoting older technologies such as these indicate the need to consider coordinated planning and consideration of local rights and livelihood transitions within economic development rather than technological interventions alone. Agroecology proposes to bridge local traditional and global scientific knowledge through a dialogue of wisdoms, fostering innovation and adaptation of technologies that rely on biodiversity (Gliessman & Titonell, 2015).

There are various widely discussed potential applications of technologies for transformative change (Pentland et al., 2022; Sen, 2014; Švarc & Dabić, 2021). For example, *transforming energy use and electricity generation* is widely discussed to achieve climate targets as well as reduce pressures on landscapes through more decentralised and renewable sources of power (Erlinghagen & Markard, 2012; Ockwell et al., 2010). These objectives can also contribute to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDGs) by promoting electricity for education and healthcare, especially in rural locations in developing countries (Come Zebra et al., 2021; Martinot et al., 2002). But these benefits would have to be considered alongside the reliance of applications such as batteries and solar cells on rare metals and whether these reinforce extractivism that reproduces colonial patterns (Kramarz et al., 2021; Sovacool et al., 2020). Moreover, discussions of energy within transformative change should not be framed only in terms of introducing new forms of energy supply in developing countries, but also on questions of equity (Carley & Konisky, 2020; Muttitt & Kartha, 2020), such as considering ways to reduce energy consumption in larger cities and in more advanced countries or acknowledging that many poorer people in countries such as India rely on coal production for livelihoods (Garg & Maheshwari, 2020).

So-called *smart technologies* in cities also offer opportunities to reduce energy and water use or streamline transportation through electronic monitoring and coordinated development of infrastructure (Maassen, 2012; Meijer & Bolivar, 2016), although rebound effects of technology efficiency should also be considered (Brockway et al., 2021). Yet, as with energy technologies, there is a need to ensure that smart technologies offer pathways to change unsustainable dependencies on resources rather than only making existing pathways more efficient. Moreover, plans for smart cities need to be incorporated into wider urban planning that can also address rapid rates of urbanisation, the rights and vulnerabilities of informal settlements and a range of different urban sizes beyond megacities alone (Burayidi et al., 2020).

Marine technologies also offer possibilities for transformative change in the management of extractive activities in oceans (Sammler, 2018). Parties to the United Nations International Seabed Authority will decide whether to allow deep-seabed mining. Evidence from shallow-water mining suggests that this extractive activity cannot be done sustainably. Consequently, long-term planning for mineral extraction will also need to consider better management of the circular economy (such as by reducing use and increasing recycling) or identify alternatives to these minerals. Some marine applications of biotechnology or biomimetics may offer an option for economic development while decreasing pressure on natural resources and marine biodiversity (Blasiak et al., 2022, 2023).

Digital agriculture solutions hold a promise to build agrifood food systems that are more efficient, environmentally sustainable and inclusive, thereby contributing to the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals¹⁰ (Glatzel et al., 2019; GSMA, 2024; Mabaya & Porciello, 2022). For example, mobile phones have accelerated access to information about markets, or risks such as storms and therefore help to overcome the geographic, social and economic isolation of rural farming communities and connect them better to other segments of the value chain. Digital technologies were instrumental at creating links between producers and consumers during the COVID-19 pandemic, facilitating innovative forms of access to food that persist in Latin America. But the success of such innovations depended on the pre-existence of active local organizations and social movements in the region (Tittonell et al., 2021). Meanwhile, mobile phone apps can be used to conduct citizen science to monitor information about landscape changes or species observations (e.g., iNaturalist, eBird). These initiatives have been called transformative because they also offer opportunities to transform values and awareness among citizens.

Attempts to introduce **new and more sustainable, forms of agricultural production** methods might also incur challenges of equity because of the way in which markets or knowledge systems are organized. For example, in Indonesia, farmers were encouraged to replace monoculture rubber production with “jungle rubber” (the cultivation of rubber trees within tropical rainforests, often incorporating diverse plant species to mimic natural ecosystems and promote environmental sustainability) because this can maintain 70% of pre-existing biodiversity while protecting farmers against rubber prices swings. This initiative, however, has not yet succeeded because of a lack of interest in “jungle rubber” from buyers such as car companies later in the supply chain (Vilamor et al., 2014). Simply providing the technology at the site of rubber production has not (yet) provided a solution; there is a need to consider how to make a value chain approach. Meanwhile, the introduction of climate-smart agriculture technologies in South America, such as the reduction of tilling, has been criticised for empowering multinational companies rather than Indigenous groups who use traditional agriculture (Newell & Taylor, 2018).

Some technologies presented as transformative are highly contested because they can potentially have devastating impacts on biodiversity. Examples of these can be found in the field of agriculture, such as genetically modified crops resistant to glyphosate, widespread in the Americas and Australia, or the emergence and wide dissemination of neo-nicotinoids used as systemic pesticides. The release in the 1990s of glyphosate-resistant genetically modified crops by the same company that created glyphosate, was a lock-in the making, a path-dependency by design. As weeds became resistant to glyphosate through repeated use over the years, farmers gradually increased the herbicide application rate, from 1-2 L/ha as initially recommended to 8 to 10 l/ha nowadays. High application rates resulted in yet wider dissemination of resistant weeds both in the US (Mortensen et al., 2012) and in Argentina (Rubione & Ward, 2016). In the same line, there are many optimistic discussions of genetic modification of food as a transformative technology. For example, technologies such as Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR) might allow editing genes of tropical breeds of cattle to give them the same favourable genetic traits that make Holsteins productive (Gates, 2018). Yet, these discussions often overlook how individual traits of animals or crops need to align with the overall agricultural system they are embedded in (Gerullis et al., 2023; Jørgensen et al., 2019).

¹⁰ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

For example, the high-input need to feed cows at the same level as in the USA or the European Union, which might not be feasible or sustainable in the tropics or for smallholders and lead to further pollution. There's also the risk of disease when all cattle have the same genetic traits (monocultures). Technologies such as CRISPR or automated phenotyping technologies need to be employed such that the capabilities to use them and their outcomes work under context specific conditions. Social system effects and path dependencies need to be considered on the plant and animal breeding level (Clapp, 2021; Gerullis et al., 2023).

It is often claimed that technologies cannot be blamed for the unintended consequences of their “misuse.” However, certain technologies are developed and delivered as universally applicable “packages,” disregarding or neglecting local knowledge systems and creating path dependencies that eventually result in technological and cognitive lock-ins through their widespread (mis-)use (Louah et al., 2017; Weituschat et al., 2022). Lock-ins are usually a problem for farmers, for biodiversity, for the environment, for society, but not necessarily by the companies that tend benefit from such dependency (e.g., pesticide treadmill, pest resurgence (Thorburn, 2015). Indeed, these lock-ins arise from a particular kind of knowledge system that presents technologies as “modern” because they are perceived to be efficient or cost-effective but are actually promoted by companies often backed by governments, development agencies, international donors and NGOs (Bakker et al., 2020). The development and use of technologies to support transformative change is achieved by looking critically at the role of these various stakeholders and their respective responsibilities and integrating local knowledge systems, preferences and aspirations of future technology users. These additional insights should enhance the democratic accountability of technology development from the initial steps of the innovation and development process and lead to responsible uses of technologies that provide equitably shared benefits among stakeholders.

Finally, using technologies for transformative change calls for closing the digital divide and reframing historic debates about access to environmentally sound technologies. The text of international agreements signed in 1992 (the Convention on Biological Diversity, UNFCCC and Agenda 21) committed Parties to “technology transfer¹¹” on concessional terms. For some years, analysts have argued that these words do not acknowledge how technology is increasingly privately owned and developed for commercial purposes. Therefore, technological changes should be seen as part of other legal and planning frameworks, such as intellectual property rights or trade and competitive policies (Mallett, 2016). Moreover, technology “transfer” is widely considered to narrow a framing and there is a need for longer-term technological cooperation and capacity building for technology innovation that are appropriate to local needs and economically viable (Heaton et al., 1994; Mininni, 2017). In food and agriculture, the concept of technology transfer is gradually being replaced by transdisciplinary “co-innovation,” with the consequent need to restructure rural extension systems (Ruggia et al., 2021, 2021).

Table SM.5.4. Sample of technologies for transformative change.

Technology arena	Example	Potential	Challenges	References
Decentralised renewable energy and electricity generation	Minigrids, small renewable energy	Has potential to reduce long-term dependence on fossil fuel use and to enhance rural	Separation of energy and biodiversity planning. Lack of coordination for	(Erlinghagen & Markard, 2012; Mallett, 2016;

¹¹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Technology arena	Example	Potential	Challenges	References
	technologies (RETs), e.g., solar panels	sustainable development	RETs). Challenges form trade and competitiveness policies.	Ockwell et al., 2010)
SMART cities and technologies	Smart meters, coordinated transport, heating and electrification	Energy efficiency and long-term planning	Integrating planning with long-term economic trends, availability of technologies. Need for rare metals for batteries.	(Sovacool et al., 2021)
Marine biotechnologies	Biomimetics	Potential to offset likely impacts on oceanic and seabed biodiversity through replacing mineral extraction and showing benefits of existing biodiversity	Lack of operational replacement technologies, separation of mineral policy from biodiversity policy	(Blasiak et al., 2022, 2023)
Climate smart technologies	High Carbon Stock landscapes, replacement fertilizers, low tilling, fire management	Ability to integrate rural development with biodiversity and climate change policies, provide livelihood-friendly alternatives to carbon-offset forestry	Political economy lacking in analysis, replacing technologies can mean power imbalances on who benefits, High Carbon can also exclude local or traditional livelihoods	(Dymond et al., 2007; Kull, 2004; Minang et al., 2015; Newell & Taylor, 2018)
Digital technologies for agriculture and environmental monitoring	Mobile phone apps and reporting	Can enhance efficiency and inclusion of food production and value chains. Can inform farmers of risks such as storms and floods.	Might reinforce rather than transform existing social hierarchies, such as between landowners and waged labourers. Does not address underlying production and consumption patterns. Need for rare metals for batteries.	(Forsyth, 2018; Mabaya & Porciello, 2022)
Agricultural and landscape management innovations	High-biodiversity agro-forestry systems, selected forms of Indigenous agriculture, climate-smart agriculture, biodiversity offsets	Can integrate land use with biodiversity protection, can implement biodiversity policy simultaneously with climate change and food security interventions	Can pose welfare limitations, or displaced costs between different land users, can have exaggerated benefits for biodiversity	(Dymond et al., 2007; Huntjens, 2021; Kull, 2004; Minang et al., 2015)

Instruments for Strategy 2

1. Instruments for governments

Governments can engage different actors in the transformative change process (Van Oorschot et al., 2020). Governments can choose instruments from four general types of policy roles and strategies: endorsing, partnering, facilitating and mandating. **Endorsing policies** refer to a relatively light form of intervention, where political support, publicity and praise are given to preferred efforts, such as endorsing market standards or public appraisal of ‘best practices.’ Endorsing mostly results in the involvement of mostly intrinsically motivated companies (coalition of the willing). **Partnering policies** include measures in which public and private resources are combined in informal or formal cooperation. This can take shape in the form of multi-stakeholder dialogues, platforms for knowledge dissemination and public-private partnerships. **Facilitating policies** are meant to make it easier for companies to act. It includes setting enabling conditions, removing regulation barriers and helping companies that invest in innovations that do not yet present viable business models. **Mandating policies** cover ‘command and control’ legislation, using regulation, reporting, and enforcement.

Specific instruments four general types of policy include:

- **Biodiversity-relevant taxes:** Taxing externalities means that environmental costs are borne by those who cause them, thus changing power constellations of who benefits and who bears the costs. Biodiversity-relevant taxes include taxes on pesticides, fertilisers, forest products and timber harvests. Based on the polluter pays principle, these instruments place an additional cost on the use of the natural resource or the emission of a pollutant, to reflect the negative environmental externalities they generate. Tax incentives are reductions from paying tax with the goal to motivate taxpayers to spend in a particular area or on certain items. For instance, tax incentives to install solar panels, or financial incentives to compensate for the possible initial losses in transitioning to agroforestry (Tschora & Cherubini, 2020). Governments can also target international tax havens, which have expanded in recent years and have contributed to illegal fishing and destructive cattle ranching (Galaz et al., 2018). The number of biodiversity-relevant taxes has increased since 1980, though there has been a plateau since 2010. A total of 234 biodiversity-relevant taxes are currently reported to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development PINE database, spanning 62 countries. In OECD countries, these biodiversity-relevant taxes generate \$7.7 billion per year in revenue (2017-2019 average). Across all countries reporting, the total revenue generated by biodiversity-relevant taxes is \$8.9 billion per year.
- **Biodiversity-relevant fees and charges:** Biodiversity-relevant fees and charges include entrance fees to national parks, fees on hunting licenses, charges on land-based sewage discharge (such as for the Great Barrier Reef area in Australia), charges for groundwater abstraction and biodiversity-relevant non-compliance fines. The number of biodiversity-relevant fees and charges has also been increasing, though marginally since about 2010, with 194 fees and charges currently in force in 50 countries. Information on the revenue collected from these fees and charges is not consistently reported to the PINE database. Most biodiversity-relevant taxes, fees and charges and environmentally motivated subsidies address only terrestrial biodiversity issues.

- ***Biodiversity-relevant tradable permits:*** Biodiversity-relevant tradable permits include individual transferable quotas (ITQs) for fisheries, tradable development rights, water trade, and tradable hunting rights. These policy instruments (also referred to as cap-and-trade programmes) set a limit on the total amount of a natural resource that can be exploited and then allocate individual permits to users that they can also trade. The allocation of these permits can be allocated to existing users of the resource free of charge, typically in perpetuity or auctioned. If they are auctioned, tradable permits can also mobilize finance. For example, rural landowners in Brazil are obliged by law to conserve native vegetation on their properties (up to 80% in the Amazon), demanding restoration in case of a deficit and allowing deforestation in case of surplus. Tradable permits offer an alternative option: Landowners with a surplus may issue and sell credits rather than deforest, while those with a deficit may acquire them instead of restoring native vegetation (van der Hoff et al., 2019). The Australian water reform, and particularly the water trading scheme in Murray-Darling basin, provides an example of price signals via market-based instruments and incentives. In addition to a basin-wide management plan, the reform includes a federal government Cap (limit) on further water extractions; unbundling land and water entitlements in anticipation of market-based transfers; the creation of a National Water Commission; investment in on- and off-farm water use infrastructure and in buying back water entitlements from willing irrigators to recover water resources for environmental use (Loch et al., 2018). The number of biodiversity-relevant tradable permits schemes has remained relatively constant since 2010, with 39 tradable permits currently active in 26 countries, with at least 4 allowing for the auctioning of the permits. Most tradable permit schemes are ocean relevant.
- ***Biodiversity-relevant subsidies:*** Subsidies coupled with production or consumption encourage overproduction and overconsumption, generating negative consequences for biodiversity (e.g., Kindvall et al., 2022; Pérez & Simonetti, 2022) and market distortion and inequity. Agriculture is one of the most subsidized sectors, receiving between \$520 (Koplow & Steenblik, 2022) and \$851 billion per year (OECD, 2023a). Current agricultural practices affect soil, freshwater and forest preservation and lead to land and marine biodiversity decline and greenhouse gas emissions (Damania et al., 2023; DeBoe, 2020; Forsyth, 2018; B. Henderson & Lankoski, 2019), generating environmental externalities above \$3 trillion per year (FOLU, 2019). The fossil fuel sector is also heavily subsidized, receiving \$440 billion per year on consumption subsidies (International Energy Agency, 2021), and \$1260 billion per year overall (Black et al., 2023). Subsidies to fossil fuels drive direct (DiSilvestro & Irvine-Broque, 2023) and indirect impacts on nature (BIOFIN, 2024; Coady et al., 2017, 2019; Pörtner et al., 2021), generating externalities with an environmental cost above 5.5 trillion per year (Black et al., 2023). Subsidies are highly concentrated in few regions, with just five political entities accounting for 80% of the total of global subsidies in 2016 (China, the United States of America, the European Union, Japan and India). Thus, repurposing would have to consider that -in some countries- subsidy levels have remained historically low (Ash & Cox, 2022). National governments and international organizations (e.g., World Trade Organization) and conventions (e.g., Paris Agreement, 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDGs), G20) have agreed to reform subsidies, but progress has been limited (Dempsey et al., 2020) and only a few, local examples illustrate subsidy reforms to safeguard sustainability. For example, New Zealand, reformed its fisheries subsidies

and offers no subsidy to its fishing industry, but all subsidy funds use strict sustainability criteria as a condition for access (Campling & Havice, 2013). In addition, England's Environmental Land Management Scheme is designed to financially reward sustainable farmland management for the generation of public goods (Hurley et al., 2022). In Chile, the Lafkenche Act, has reallocated resources to Indigenous communities, promoting their active involvement in coastal management to further sustainable coastal management and protect ecosystems and biodiversity (González-Poblete et al., 2020). Limited progress has been attributed to subsidies political costs and trade-offs that manifest at different temporal and spatial scales (Alkon & Urpelainen, 2018; Oosterhuis et al., 2014; Toan, 2016). Assuring the coherence of subsidy schemes with biodiversity support can be a powerful lever for transformation. For instance, changes in the European Union support have been reflected in drastic changes in grassland conservation (Pe'er et al., 2017). Nevertheless, large subsidy schemes such as the EU Common Agricultural Policy are dominated by direct payments to farmers that potentially support biodiversity drivers and are not linked to biodiversity support (Pe'er et al., 2020). Biodiversity-relevant subsidies include those environmentally motivated subsidies that target, for example, forest management and reforestation, organic or environmentally friendly agriculture, pesticide-free cultivation and land conservation. The number of environmentally motivated subsidies relevant for biodiversity currently in force, as reported to the PINE database, is 163, in place in 28 countries.

- **Positive incentives:** Payment for ecosystem services (PES) is an incentive-based mechanism while REDD+ is a performance-based forest management. Both are based on the same principle for incentivizing improved management. Within the overall PES framework, REDD+ features as one PES scheme on carbon. Specifically, PES are voluntary transactions between service users and providers that are conditional on agreed rules of natural resource management for generating offsite services (Wunder, 2015). PES are based on the user- or beneficiary-pays approach and operate through incentives rather than disincentives. Positive incentives can help to enhance public acceptance of biodiversity conservation measures and, if properly structured, provide dynamic and continuing incentives for improvement. Evidence suggests that PES programme effectiveness in achieving environmental objectives and coupled social and economic co-benefits often lags the expectations. For example, China's PES Grain-to-Green programme (GTGP) has reduced forest *exploitation* but has had limited positive benefits for wildlife diversity (Chen, 2020). Similarly weak ecological benefits have been identified for the case of an Indonesian marine protected area (Clifton, 2013). However, where payments directly target the causes of nature decline, as in the case of bird nest protection in Cambodia, increases in population of bird species have been achieved (Clements et al., 2013). (Ravetto Enri et al., 2020) confirmed the effectiveness of an agri-environmental payment scheme in Switzerland (Biodiversity Promotion Areas) in conserving biodiversity in the Southern Swiss Alps. Overall, to date, PES have often proved too small (especially among national level programmes) to compete with biodiversity-harming forms of land use, though not necessarily smaller than the impacts of other conservation policy instruments, such as protected areas, in comparable contexts (Börner et al., 2017). The few evaluation studies that addressed social outcomes of PES have found small positive effects at best, but also no negative impacts (Börner et al., 2017). Contextual factors and design principles (e.g., pre-programme compliance) tend to

matter greatly in practice. Moreover, research suggest that PES literature is decontextualized from political histories of the territory and PES often gets hyped as a proposed solution to ecological challenges often without any credible evidence (Kolinjivadi et al., 2023). In a review of conservation-oriented REDD+ projects, (Wunder et al., 2020) found that both project implementers and households reported conditional incentives as potentially being both the most promising and effective intervention. Still, these conditional incentives remained underutilized in implementation. In a review of the underlying values and moral roots in subnational REDD+ implementation in two Southeast Asian countries with different political histories, (Do & van Noordwijk, 2023) found that maintaining strong national control over forests was a key motivation for initial REDD+ adoption, but further development of the programmes rebalanced efficiency and fairness¹² in decision-making, thus expanding morality beyond financial gains.

- **Reporting obligations:** There are available methods and indicators for measuring large companies progress on managing biodiversity impacts and dependencies. For example, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2464/oj>) requires companies to report in line with the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), established by the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG). Governments could extend reporting obligations to a large group of companies and apply stricter reporting guidelines in sectors with high biodiversity impacts and dependencies. Such reporting will deliver relevant information for an improved accountability biodiversity framework. Systems and guidelines are needed not only for monitoring, transparent reporting and verification of business commitments, but also for disclosure of this information, to enable societal actors to provide the right triggers and incentives for businesses to step up.

2. Instruments for the private sector

The private sector depends either directly, through their supply chains, or through their investments on nature for which a company's position in the supply chain determines the specific measures that companies take (e.g., reducing the environmental pressures of their production process, re-use of resources, sustainable exploitation of ecosystems, restoration measures, use of compensation schemes). Motivation largely determines companies' strategies and speed for integrating biodiversity into their business model, although research suggest that, on their own, relying on companies' motivation (e.g., voluntary, market-oriented mechanisms) result in weak or ineffective outcomes (Clapp & Isakson, 2018; Dauvergne, 2018; Hennig & Wörsdörfer, 2015).

Motivation defines the extent to which companies are susceptible to policies of governments, clustering companies in four types. Inactive or **passive companies** see sustainability mainly as a task for the government. Their focus is on the continuation of the company and safeguarding their own interests. **Reactive companies** are more responsive to societal issues than inactive ones and use a defensive strategy. They do not alter their business models but incorporate sustainability to avoid financial risks – or achieve lower costs – and protect their reputation and brand value. **Active companies** manage risks presented by both impacts and dependencies in a

¹² See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

strategic way and are looking for new market opportunities. **Pro-active companies** are intertwined with sustainability challenges. Their business models explicitly include societal values and aim at transformative change of the whole system.

Specific instruments that companies can use include:

- ***Supply chain regulation:*** Companies increasingly deliver sustainably produced goods (e.g., food) as a response to the demand of conscious consumers (Van Oorschot et al., 2020). Consequently, companies in supply chains also influence each other by demanding and supplying sustainably produced goods and resources. For example, to address concerns about the negative impacts of food supply chains in forest regions, a growing number of companies have adopted policies to influence their suppliers' behaviours, certifications, but also codes of conduct and market exclusion mechanisms (R. D. Garrett et al., 2021). International organizations provide tools to help companies assess and respond to biodiversity-related risks and opportunities across their operations, value chain and investments, as the WWF Biodiversity Risk Filter. A systematic review of the conservation and livelihood outcomes of the mechanisms that companies use to implement their forest-focused supply chain policies suggest that more than half of the cases that rigorously measure the outcomes of such implementation mechanisms find additional conservation and livelihood benefits resulting from the policies (R. D. Garrett et al., 2021) Positive livelihood outcomes are more common than conservation additionality and most often pertain to improvements in farm income through increases in crop yields on coffee and cocoa farms that have adopted certifications or codes of conduct. However, in some cases, certifications lead to a reduction in net household income as farmers increasingly specialize in the certified commodity and spend more on food purchases. This analysis suggests that interactions with public conservation and agricultural policies influence the conservation gains achieved by all mechanisms, while the marketing attributes of cooperatives and buying companies play a large role in determining the livelihood outcomes associated with certification. Establishing mechanisms to hold corporations accountable for biodiversity decline and rights infringements is essential in the post-2020 agenda (Ching & Lin, 2019). While regulations on sustainable supply chains such as the zero-deforestation strategy of the European Union are emerging, studies of sustainable supply chains indicate that cooperation is needed between farmers, suppliers and buyers/traders (often multinational companies) for a successful implementation of sustainable (including zero-deforestation) supply chains.
- ***Standards and certification:*** Eco-labelling are certification schemes for products (e.g., sustainable forestry or fisheries certifications) that adhere to specific biodiversity-friendly practices. Forest certification and financial incentives for local communities support sustainable forest management (Karsenty & Salau, 2023), aiming to prevent forest degradation and over-logging. Voluntary environmental initiatives include zero deforestation commitments (e.g., the New York Declaration on Forests, Soy Moratorium, Amsterdam Declaration, European Union Zero-deforestation strategy, the Soft Commodities Forum). Standards and certification have a certain potential to contribute to biodiversity challenges. For example, certification schemes and zero-deforestation pledges can support sustainable practices that reduce the impacts of telecoupling (socioeconomic interactions across distant places) in agricultural commodities on biodiversity if more companies should adopt zero-gross deforestation targets with

immediate implementation deadlines and clear sanction-based implementation mechanisms in biomes with high risk of forest to commodity conversion (R. D. Garrett et al., 2019).

However, the impact of sustainable production standards on nature is much debated. For example, despite forest certification potential, globally the proportion of certified forests is low. Protected forests cover about 524 million ha (ca. 13%) of global forests (Cubbage & Sills, 2020). Among productive forests, only about 20% are certified (Cubbage & Sills, 2020). The most widespread certification schemes are the forest certification schemes of the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and the national certification schemes of the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC).

Evidence of positive impacts of forest certification is mixed and generally lacks robust empirical basis (Cubbage & Sills, 2020). Certification has led to better forest structure in certified lands in Tanzania (Kalonga et al., 2015), improved biodiversity conservation (Kalonga et al., 2016), higher household forest income (Kalonga & Kulindwa, 2017), reduced deforestation in Kalimantan (Miteva et al., 2015; Rana & Sills, 2018) and general improvement of enforcement practices in Brazil and Russia (L. M. Sundstrom & Henry, 2017). Incentives motivate sustainable forest management practices by community and industrial producers and provides them price premiums for selling certified products (e.g., timber) in specialized markets (Bocci & Fortmann, 2023). (Alveira et al., 2023) show that “certified reduced impact logged forest” in the Argentine Austral Yungas better contributes to biodiversity conservation (similar mammals' richness with unlogged forests) than conventionally logged forests, as 3-4 years after logging, there were no changes (Alveira et al., 2023) in mammals' composition, richness and diversity, between the certified logged area and the unlogged area. Some studies also show that through the process of becoming certified, such as through Corrective Action Requests (CAR), FSC forest certification positively influenced forest management practices “community and social interactions, environmental protection practices and system processes” (Cubbage & Sills, 2020) p. 94 of the target forests in Mexico (Blackman et al., 2017). However, in some cases, no evidence of impact was found (e.g., Mexico, (Blackman et al., 2015) or evidence of reduced deforestation is mixed, as it is the case in Peru and Cameroon (Panlasigui et al., 2015) and in Brazil and Russia (L. M. Sundstrom & Henry, 2017). For example, an evaluation of the effectiveness of Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) plantations compared to non-certified plantations using Indonesian Borneo (Kalimantan) as a case study found no significant difference between certified and non-certified plantations for any of the sustainability metrics investigated (Morgans et al., 2018). Moreover, in some cases, such measures have telecoupled effects. For example, the Soy Moratorium in the Amazon reduced direct forest clearance for soy to about 1% per year (Gibbs et al., 2015) but during the period 2000-2014, 70% of soy expansion was at the expense of areas that were pastures in 2000 (Filho & Costa, 2016; Ermgassen et al., 2020).

A key reason for the mixed success is that these initiatives are embedded in economic and institutional structures maintained by powerful special interest groups that prioritize economic growth over biodiversity concerns (Bartley, 2022) and do not consider local concerns. To improve the effects of forest certification on biodiversity conservation, adapting international standards (e.g., FSC) to local-national contexts is critical for their adoption and success (Elbakidze et al., 2022). Likewise, incentives need to be adapted to

convince producers, especially in tropical forests, to maintain forests and produce certified timber, as producers perceive that benefits of certification are low and costs of certification high (Gullison, 2003). The success of certification also hinges on the willingness of markets/consumers to pay higher prices for the "sustainability of the production system" (Gullison, 2003). The unit costs of certification (per cubic meter) is higher for small scale producers than for large-scale producers (Gullison, 2003). For many biodiversity-rich tropical regions, forest certification has not yet proven beneficial to forest conservation (Gullison, 2003). Further, certification does not reduce the pressure on high conservation value forests. Thus, "conservation strategies that address demand are necessary but not sufficient in themselves to conserve HCVF" (Gullison, 2003). There "is only clear evidence that certification produces biodiversity benefits by improving management of existing timber production forests during the auditing process" and incentives of certification remain insufficient to prevent deforestation, especially in tropical forests (Gullison, 2003), with modest benefits in temperate countries. Thus, any change in incentives or nudges must be accompanied by efforts to address these political and economic interests, ensuring that the economic system reflects broader social values, including the value of protecting the future of the planet (Boiral et al., 2018). To address the barriers to and limitations of certification, (Cubbage & Sills, 2020) suggest governments to recognize certification audits as alternative to government monitoring and enforcement action, thereby reducing the regulatory burden on certified companies and encouraging certification. They also recommend the use of certified or legally verified timber in government infrastructures (Cubbage & Sills, 2020).

- ***Cooperation within the private sector:*** Capacity for cooperation on biodiversity is a critical success factor for companies to move to more biodiversity-positive strategies (van Tulder et al., 2016). Active and pro-active companies that are willing to act on biodiversity issues, mostly do so in cooperation with other actors. Partnering is used, for example, for accessing new knowledge, gaining influence and increasing legitimacy for their activities. Cooperation is also crucial in integrated production landscapes that link consumers served by internationally operating companies to primary producers operating in the vicinity of natural ecosystems that support biodiversity. Data shows that companies prefer to cooperate in multi-stakeholder initiatives, rather than in purely private initiatives. The international cooperative initiatives in which companies participate currently mostly focus on networking and information sharing (Van Oorschot et al., 2020).

The scope for private actors and businesses to transform their systems is determined by and embedded in larger structures. For example, many farmers are locked into large-scale resource-intensive monocultures by contractual obligation with agricultural suppliers and retailers or with investors and lenders, constraining their ability to adopt more sustainable practices (Oliveira & Hecht, 2016; Phélinas & Choumert, 2017). Therefore, government action is indispensable to balance these large-scale forces and structures, reduce barriers for change and catalyse sustainable and pro-biodiversity actions.

3. Instruments for civil society

Triggers and incentives for change often come from civil society and grassroots organizations, who provide triggers to economic sectors (van Tulder, 2018) or directly confront them (Scheidel et al., 2020).

Citizens scrutiny companies' impact on nature and expose their shortcomings (e.g., name and shame) and fuel public debate on responsible and acceptable practices (Boiral et al., 2018; Elmagrhi et al., 2019). Through these practices, citizens have contributed to create voluntary market standards for sustainable production and trade and promote market adoption of these standards. Ignoring these stakeholder concerns can result in a loss of reputation and may lead to the revocation of operating licenses for companies (Adler et al., 2018; Carvajal et al., 2022).

Civil society also provides several social innovations. A systematic review of 100 empirical case studies of rural social innovations occurring across Europe during 1970-2024 illustrates the variety of social innovation initiatives with potential to curve nature decline. The initiatives respond to differing local needs and opportunities and cover diverse sectors, including the agrifood (57%), tourism (40%), forestry (17%) and energy sectors (12%). More than one third (34%) of these initiatives aim to tackle both social and ecological problems, while 6% have mainly an ecological focus. Of the initiatives with an environmental and/or social-ecological focus (40%), the problems most often tackled are environmental degradation like depletion of natural resources, soil contamination or poor quality of land (14%), climate change (10%), landscape or land loss (10%), harmful and unsustainable practices (e.g., intensified land use, (González-Rosado et al., 2021) Organizational interventions range from the creation of new associations to revitalize traditional practices (G. Weiss et al., 2020), second order umbrella organizations for, e.g., natural parks management (e.g., (Ludvig et al., 2020), or the multi-sectoral and multi-stakeholder networks for land conservation and multi-level collaboration networks to tackle environmental degradation situations (e.g., (Chiasson et al., 2019; Dabard & Mann, 2023).

In some cases, civil society also organize for the management and distribution of various forms of collective resources for wellbeing. For example, the 'commons transition movement' supports self-organized working communities that sustain themselves and their environments by collectively managing resources and promoting new models of production into one integrated system (Bollier, 2014). This has been applied, for example, in urban green commons. Green commons are areas of nature in cities that are viewed as a common-pool resource by a local community (Colding et al., 2013). Since such commons are generally subject to the problems of congestion and overuse, especially in urban areas, there is often a need to devise and enforce rules, which are in the hands of an identifiable local community of stakeholders. Hence, members of such commons may collectively craft their own rules-in-use (local institutions) for the management of common-pool resources within given legislative forms of society (Barthel et al., 2022).

Members of civil society also organize in social movements to mobilize against direct impacts on their local environment as shown by the analysis of cases reported in the Environmental Justice Atlas (Scheidel et al., 2020). Much environmental concern about biodiversity conservation has focused on the struggles of local people to resist destructive forms of development (Peet &

Watts, 2004). At times these concerns have also led to transnational advocacy campaigns to support local activists, such as—famously—the resistance of Penan Indigenous Peoples in Sarawak, Malaysia, against the decision of the Malaysian government to allow logging of rainforests in the 1980s, or long-standing concerns to prevent deforestation in the Amazon Basin (Hecht & Cockburn, 1989; Colchester, 2007). But simultaneously, there are also concerns that the interests of local activists might be weakened when their local struggles are absorbed into political campaigns dominated by national or international activists (Covey, 1995). This effect might also occur in the values used to describe or frame biodiversity. For example, the well-known Chipko Andalan resistance to deforestation in the Indian Himalayas was widely represented as local people—and especially women—using techniques such as “tree-hugging” to show an innate respect for nature (Shiva, 1988). Later analysts have instead alleged that these representations have exploited local struggles to build support for other national or international actors’ worldviews about ecology or feminism (C. Jackson, 1995; Leach, 2007), or that they fail to acknowledge the desire of local people to protect resources for their own use and on their own terms (Rangan, 2000). Such initiatives are led by a variety of actors, including grassroots movements (Martinez-Alier et al., 2016), Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Escobar, 2020; Jasanoff, 2005; Pascual, Adams, Díaz, et al., 2021; Konforti 2022), women collectives (Tran, 2021), urban dwellers (Navas et al., 2022), scientists, international NGOs (Scheidel et al., 2020) and youth activists (Bentz & O’Brien, 2019; High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition, 2022).

Most common forms of mobilization by social movements include:

- Non-violent protest and persuasion: Formal petitions (reported in 58% of all cases), public campaigns (57%) and street protests (56%) are the most reported forms of protest and persuasion, followed by the creation of collective action networks, involvement of NGOs and media-based activism. Fridays for Future, the youth-led and -organized movement that began in August 2018, after 15-year-old Greta Thunberg and other young activists sat in front of the Swedish parliament every school day for three weeks, to protest against the lack of action on the climate crisis, is a recent example of non-violent protest.
- Non-cooperation: Strikes, boycotts of official processes, companies and products, of refusal of compensation payments are relevant forms of non-cooperation particularly in urban contexts. However, they appear globally only in up to 10% of all cases.
- Non-violent intervention: *Environmental* defenders use legal strategies such as lawsuits in almost half of all cases and objections to environmental impacts assessments (EIAs) in a quarter of all cases. Local scientists and professionals frequently support the creation of new knowledge and alternative proposals (Conde, 2014). Regarding legal strategies, the filing of lawsuits alone does not significantly associate with higher cancellation rates. However, when combined with formal objections to EIA, cancellation rate is larger. Reports that provide the perspective of affected communities on conflictive projects are produced in 36% of cases, while alternative project proposals are put forward in 23% of cases.

Disruptive interventions such as road blockades (28%), occupation of public buildings (13%), land occupation (12%) and self-sacrifice are employed when previous interventions were not successful (Hanna et al., 2016). The use of such interventions depends also on the political culture; for instance, 40% of cases involving hunger strikes come from India. Potentially violent

protest actions, such as property damage, sabotage, or threats to use arms are rare (7%, 3% and 3% of cases, respectively), testifying to the overwhelmingly non-violent character of defenders' protest actions. Disruptive interventions are often penalised by law, and their success or failure might depend on societal values.

Lobbying, negotiations and litigation have resulted in the establishment of conventions (e.g., a draft Nordic Sámi convention between the Sami and the Governments of Finland, Norway and Sweden), in signing treaties and return of lands to Indigenous Peoples (e.g., the Treaty of Waitangi in which New Zealand “returned ownership of central New Zealand forests to Māori tribes”, modern treaties in Canada transferring government lands to Indigenous nations, or the "negotiations on the Wapichan people's ancestral land claims" in Guyana) (United Nations, 2021b). Negotiations also help to clarify relationships between companies and Indigenous Peoples such as among the Udege people in the Russian Federation. Partnerships of Indigenous Peoples with supportive organizations can help secure Indigenous territories such as in the Amazon region of Colombia, in the Amazonian Kayapo in Brazil, or improve Indigenous rights as in Nepal. Litigations that secure Indigenous ownership to territories, lands and resources have occurred in Indonesia, Belize, Ecuador, India, Colombia, Malaysia, in Yakutia, the Russian Federation, New Zealand, Australia, Canada and Sweden and are valuable legal precedents for other similar cases, although implementation often depends on the political will of decision makers (United Nations, 2021b). Negative outcomes might ensue for Indigenous Peoples such as in India and court rulings might not be enforced (United Nations, 2021b). Being costly, many Indigenous communities may not afford such strategies. Litigation can empower Indigenous communities (e.g., in Kenya, Malaysia and Paraguay) (United Nations, 2021b). The African court on human and people's right have ruled in favour of the Endorois and Ogiek peoples (Kenya) and the Inter-American Court of Human Rights has also dealt with cases in Paraguay, Ecuador, Suriname but implementation remains slow. Non-judicial measures such as national human rights institutions influence the implementation "of Indigenous land rights" (e.g., Malaysia, Indonesia). Through their social and environmental safeguards, international financial and development institutions contribute to compliance with social and environmental standards at low levels (e.g., Cambodia).

The analysis of 2802 social-environmental mobilizations occurring during 1992 and 2022 provides evidence of a total of 46,955 incidents of threats to 13 KM-GBF targets contested by social-environmental mobilizations. Threats to KM-GBF Target 11 is the most frequently contested (9715 threats). Threats to Target 1, Target 3, Target 2 and Target 7 are also highly contested. The same threats also jeopardize the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, leading to landscape loss, livelihood loss and land dispossession (Scheidel et al., 2023).

The most successful way to mobilize seems to not rely on a single strategy but to combine several at once. Effective support for environmental defenders should thus promote measures that enable them to pursue litigation, preventive protest and diverse mobilizations all together (Scheidel et al., 2020). Recognizing the effectiveness of preventive protest has key implications for supporting environmental defenders: it points to the need to address those factors that inhibit or enable preventive mobilization. Empirical analysis suggests that preventive mobilizations (i.e., before projects started) by grassroot organizations result in undesired project cancelation in 17% of cases, twice as much as when mobilizations occurred in reaction to project implementation, or for reparations once impacts were experienced. Additionally, where social movements used more than ten different mobilization forms, projects were again more than twice

as frequent to be cancelled than in cases with less than five types of protest actions. Tactical diversity reflects a range of skills available in the movement and allows more people to participate in a diverse range of protest activities and thus to increase pressure on proponents of conflictive projects and it may turn mobilizations more resilient as claimants can move between protest forms in case of repression of a particular one (Chenoweth & Stephan, 2012).

Initiatives exemplifying actions in strategy 2

- Business platforms: Business initiatives for nature, such as the *Business4Nature network* and the *One Planet Business for Biodiversity coalition*, are emerging that may help to build confidence for governments to adopt a new and ambitious biodiversity framework. The Business4Nature platform, for example, has states that more regulatory and incentivizing government strategies seem necessary.
- BIOFIN: The UNDP and the European Commission, for example, launched the *Biodiversity Finance Initiative (BIOFIN)* in 2012 to seek new methodologies for “optimal” and “evidence-based” biodiversity finance plans and solutions.
- Digital Makerspace: The Digital Makerspace (www.conservationxlabs.com/digital-makerspace) is an open online platform created by the startup ConservationXLab to connect individuals interested in co-creating solutions to conservation problems through tech innovations. The Digital Makerspace has over 1000 members and 150 projects under development, all aiming at the joint application of conservation and business principles to develop innovative solutions (e.g., future products, services, markets and business models) intended to contribute to nature conservation and result in financial gain, or what is known as conservation entrepreneurship (Lobo et al., 2023).
- Action Agenda for Nature and People provide a mechanism to showcase private-sector initiatives and commitments (Kok et al., 2023).
- The United Nations Environment Programme Strategy for Private Sector Engagement focuses on the possible contribution of businesses and financial institutions to the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework, as part of a whole-of-society approach (UNEP, 2019b). The strategy is intended to encourage the business community to make concrete and ambitious commitments for biodiversity that can be tracked and reported on for the successful achievement of the 2050 Vision for biodiversity. Active and willing companies can provide inputs and set positive examples on what is needed from the new framework to support businesses to make commitments and contribute to a net-positive direction. To bring these objectives further, the Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity is active with establishing collaborative partnerships with relevant business organizations and initiatives and promoting a Global Partnership for Business and Biodiversity
- The European Commission also launched its own EU Business @ Biodiversity Platform (B@B) in 2007

- Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS) in 2017, for example, aims to “mobilize mainstream finance to support the transition toward a sustainable economy”, promote the adoption of sustainable and responsible investment principles and address the environmental and societal impacts of the policy portfolios of central banks across the world. At the same time, this approach still faces substantial challenges, such as reshaping entrenched investment norms, risk definitions and investment practices in the financial sector (Crona et al., 2021).
- The Interface Dialogue Finance and Biodiversity (Idfb-dialogue.org) platform brings together stakeholders from governments and the private sector to discuss and share best practices on alignment of all financial flows with the GBF and implementation of the GBF. It was established by the Government of the Netherlands in 2021 in the run up to COP15 to bridge the gap between greening finance and financing green. The IDFB hosted 15 dialogue sessions to bring together perspectives from the public sector and the private financial sector. More than 30 countries and 60 experts engaged in the dialogue sessions, where lessons and best practices on resource mobilization and engaging the private sector were shared.
- We Value Network campaign, an European Union Horizon project (2018-2022) helping to make valuing nature the norm across business in Europe. The website (<https://wevaluenature.eu/>) contains resources including case studies, free training courses, persona action cards (how to engage with colleagues on the topic of natural capital) and other relevant materials.
- The Science Based Targets Network is a science-driven initiative, established in 2019 by a coalition of global NGOs. This civil-society effort aims to collectively determine the actions required for companies and cities to operate within Earth's ecological boundaries while addressing societal needs.

1. Supporting material for action 2.3

Table SM.5.5. Data for “Global economic estimates of actions undermining and strengthening global sustainability” (figure 5.6).

Economic sector	Estimated cost	Extent	US\$ billion	Year	Adjusted 2023 US\$ billions	Source
Agriculture	Subsidy (Min)	Global	610	2023	610	(Koplow & Steenblik, 2024)
	Subsidy (Max)	OECD countries	851	2021	939	(OECD, 2023a)

	Externality (Min)	Global	3100	2018	3693	(FOLU, 2019)
	Externality (Max)	Global	12 700	2020	14 718	(Food and Agriculture Organization, 2023)
Fossil fuels	Subsidy (Min)	Global consumption	577	2021	637	(Damania et al., 2023)
	Subsidy (Max)	Global	1260	2021	1390	(Black et al., 2023)
	Externality	Global	5250	2021	5792	(Black et al., 2023)
Infrastructure (Road / irrigation)	Subsidy (Min)	Global	224 / 30	2019 / 2004	263 / 48	(Kjellingbro & Skotte, 2005; OECD, 2021)
	Subsidy (Max)	Global	586 / 158	2015 / 2015	739 / 199	(Oxford Economics, 2017)
Forestry	Subsidy (Min)	Global	55	2019	64	(Deutz et al., 2020)
	Subsidy (Max)	Global	175	2023	175	(Koplow & Steenblik, 2024)
	Externality (Min)	Global	935	2023	935	(Koplow & Steenblik, 2024)
	Externality (Max)	Global	1939	2023	1939	(Koplow & Steenblik, 2024)
Fisheries	Subsidy (Min)	Global	35.4 / 5.2	2018	42 / 6	(Mejaes, 2021; Skerritt et al., 2023)
(Marine / aquaculture)	Subsidy (Max)	Global	55 / 5.2	2023 / 2018	55 / 6	(Mejaes, 2021; Skerritt et al., 2023)

	Externality	Global (marine)	83	2016	103	(World Bank, 2017)
Metal mining	Subsidy	Global	40	2023	40	(Koplow & Steenblik, 2024)

2. Sentiment analysis on Subsidies to economic sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature decline

Drawing on a subset of the assessment corpus including documents that refer to government support to different economic sectors that directly drive nature decline (n=124,517 hits), a sentiment analysis was conducted to assess whether subsidies are presented as “positive”, “neutral”, or “negative” in the literature. The number of new publications per year documents referring to subsidies shows a constant increase until the beginning of the 2010’s decade, after which tends to stabilize. Most documents come from authors in the United States of America, China and the European Union, some of the political entities that provide most subsidies. The sentiment analysis of words appearing in the document’s abstracts show an increasing stabilization of positive sentiments towards EHS. Before the 1980’s, both positive and negative sentiments towards EHS were highly variable, but variation was reduced thereafter. After the 1980’s and particularly after the 1990’s, positive sentiments towards EHS increase whereas negative sentiments towards EHS stabilize or even show a slow decrease.

Figure SM.5.8. Sentiment analysis of documents referring to subsidies in the transformative change corpus.

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Annex 5.4. Strategy 3

Approaches for strategy 3

Modifying production and consumption for sustainability has been proposed by different alternative economic models that provide alternatives to today's conventional economics, although these approaches have failed to replace neoliberalism¹³ in the economic mainstream (Riedy, 2020). There have been calls for a 'strategic dialogue' among new economic discourses to make them fit for a global stage (Beling et al., 2018), which must include understanding common ground and disagreement in attitudes towards the economic status quo (Linnér & Wibeck, 2020). Alternative economic visions to mainstream economics are reviewed in chapter 2. Common features of these approaches are the focus on conservation and sustainable use of nature and good quality of life and sustainable development, although they differ in the depth of change sought, the relative emphasis on environmental and social aspects, and the timescale that might be needed to reach results. Three main approaches (e.g., 'Green economy', 'Limits to growth' and 'Shared Socioeconomics with Planetary Boundaries') are discussed presenting examples of economic instruments they propose.

1. Green Economy

The Green Economy approach includes proposals for 'green growth', 'bioeconomy', 'circular economy' and 'green growth'. It mostly corresponds to the alternative economic vision labelled Circular Economy, Although oriented towards shifting how economies function with respect to production, this approach is critiqued as it is business- and foundation-led, it retains an economic growth orientation, and it rests on a technological 'fix' that goods can be re-used for long periods of time. Moreover, this approach does not significantly shift the purpose of the economic system (D'Amato et al., 2017; T. Jackson & Victor, 2019).

a. Bioeconomy

Though there is no universally agreed definition, and several definitions are available, bioeconomy generally refers to economic approaches that harness the potential of biological resources, processes and principles to generate sustainable economic growth, enhance resource efficiency and promote environmental and social well-being (Tan & Lamers, 2021) to reconcile nature's and humans' needs (IACGB, 2023). Despite differences in definitions (Gardossi et al., 2023), the core idea of the bioeconomy is using biological resources derived from living organisms, including plants, animals and microorganisms across various sectors including agriculture, forestry, fisheries and biotechnology. Biological resources as ecosystem services serve as inputs to innovate a wide range of goods, materials and energy, including biofuels, bioplastics, biochemicals, pharmaceuticals and food products for economic sectors. Also, bioeconomy seeks for maintaining ecosystems and moving away from extractive practices,

¹³ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

rethinking consumption, while still supporting employment and other societal needs (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2018; Robert et al., 2020).

Overall, the bioeconomy is presented as a transition towards a more sustainable and resilient economic model that capitalizes on the renewable biological resources while minimizing dependence on finite fossil-based resources and reducing environmental footprints. Such nature-based products could help improve the circularity of different production and consumption systems and would be beneficial to the implementation of circular economy approaches (Daurimar et al., 2021). The bioeconomy approach is particularly popular in developing countries that seek to assess the potential of nature-based products to leverage conservation and restoration efforts, including through support to the livelihoods of biodiversity-dependent communities and the adequate valuation of the traditional knowledge from Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Lindberg et al., 2023). For example, research in Nordic countries suggests that the transformation of land use and societal practices associated with bioeconomy might not be as costly as expected (Immerzeel et al., 2023). Other nations are also experimenting with bioeconomy; for example, Brazil is experimenting with bioeconomy as a means of preserving the Amazon (Da Silva et al., 2023; Daurimar et al., 2021; R. Garrett et al., 2024).

b. Circular Economy

The general idea of a circular economy is reducing demand for raw materials by maximizing the productivity of existing circulating materials. It mainly focuses on understanding the life cycle of products and materials to improve resource management and efficiency (Tan & Lamers, 2021). The circular economy vision for nature is meant to eliminate waste by generating economic value out of all residuals. It thereby proposes reducing nature's threats by 1) eliminating (reducing) pollution, greenhouse gases, and single-use materials through changes in design; 2) circulating products and materials to leave room for nature because fewer virgin resources are being used; and 3) regenerating nature to enable nature to thrive by employing nature actively to regenerate natural systems (regenerative approach) in multiple biomes (land, ocean, freshwater). The circular economy proposes to produce more with less waste, resources and energy through a make-use-recycle-reuse circular pattern. New business and distribution models are needed to achieve deployment at scale.

The circular economy, however, may not deliver the transformation to sustainability if circularity measures fuel a growth strategy that leads to increased material consumption. The key goal of a circular economy is to slow, narrow and close material resource loops, built on the foundation of renewable energy and non-toxic materials (Tan & Lamers, 2021). An economy downsized to match the material input that it can recycle would be a very slow economy (Kovacic et al., 2019). The concept of 'circular economy' suggests that material resources could be increasingly sourced from within the economy, reducing environmental impact by increasing the reuse and recycling of materials. However, in the current economic system, recyclable material remains a meagre portion of material throughput (Giampietro, 2019).

c. Circular bioeconomy

The circular bioeconomy is an economic model at the intersection between the circular economy and the bioeconomy. The approach is different from current systems by design, with materials used for as long as possible and emissions-reducing practices put into place. It emphasizes the sustainable use of biological resources in a closed-loop system, aiming to minimize waste, maximize resource efficiency and promote environmental conservation, while recognizing that such resources are limited. In the circular bioeconomy, biological materials, such as agricultural residues, forestry by-products and organic waste, are utilised as inputs for various production processes. These materials are managed to prioritize regeneration, reuse and recycling, rather than disposal or incineration (Tan & Lamers, 2021). Principles of the circular bioeconomy include biomass valorisation (i.e., efficient and sustainable use of biological resources to produce goods, energy and services); closed-loop systems (i.e., designing production and consumption processes that minimize waste generation and maximize resource recovery through recycling and reuse); renewable energy integration (i.e., harnessing environmentally sustainable bioenergy sources, such as biomass or biogas, the production of which has not caused land use change or environmental degradation, to replace fossil fuels); sustainable ecosystem management and innovation and technology development. Overall, the circular bioeconomy aims to transform traditional linear production and consumption patterns into circular, regenerative systems that are economically viable, environmentally sustainable and socially inclusive (Tan & Lamers, 2021).

The circular bioeconomy approach is particularly popular in developing countries that seek to assess the potential of biodiversity-based products to leverage conservation and restoration efforts, including through support to the livelihoods of biodiversity-dependent communities and the adequate valuation of the traditional knowledge from Indigenous Peoples and local communities (e.g., (Lindberg et al., 2023);). Those biodiversity-based products could unlock new investments in sustainable activities, but they would necessarily do so through a circular economy lens.

d. Green growth

Green growth is a form of economic growth that prioritizes environmental sustainability, resource efficiency and low-carbon pathways while fostering economic prosperity and social inclusion. Green growth theory asserts that continued economic expansion is compatible with our planet's ecology, as technological change and substitution will allow us to absolutely decouple GDP growth from resource use and carbon emissions. Green growth seeks to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation by promoting sustainable production and consumption patterns, investing in clean and renewable energy sources and adopting innovative technologies and practices that minimize environmental impacts (Hickel & Kallis, 2020; Smulders et al., 2014). It emphasizes the integration of environmental considerations into policymaking, business strategies and investment decisions to achieve long-term economic resilience and ecological balance (Smulders et al., 2014). It is based on ecomodernist thought that invests its hopes in scientific and technological progress (e.g., eco-design, green innovation) directed towards sustainability. Critics argue that empirical evidence on resource use and carbon emissions does not support green growth theory as: (1) there is no empirical evidence that absolute decoupling from resource use can be achieved on a global scale against a background of

continued economic growth and (2) absolute decoupling from carbon emissions is highly unlikely to be achieved at a rate rapid enough to prevent global warming over 1.5°C or 2°C, even under optimistic policy conditions (Hickel & Kallis, 2020). Several countries and international organizations, such as the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, World Bank, and United Nations, have developed strategies for green growth (OECD, 2011; World Bank, 2012).

(Hamari et al., 2016). The sharing economy advocates for community-based solutions that disrupts ownership norms for a more sustainable future (Mi & Coffman, 2019)

2. Limits to growth

The limits to growth approach includes proposals for a ‘steady-state economy’, ‘degrowth,’ and ‘post-growth’, all built on the idea of staying within the biophysical limits of the planet. It mostly corresponds to the alternative economic vision labelled Degrowth and Steady State. The approach is based on the scientific consensus that absolute decoupling of GDP-based growth from environmental damage is unfeasible and that there are fundamental thermodynamic limits to material-based (Giampietro, 2019; Greenford et al., 2020; Tilsted et al., 2021). Core principles are that ecosystems have value in themselves, not just for services provided and that humans are part of nature, which includes ‘rights of nature’ to preserve and regenerate ecosystems. Since effective decoupling of economic growth from resource use is not feasible, this approach proposes reductions in the scale and scope of the economy towards zero growth or degrowth, including physical limits on some forms of production and consumption (IPBES, 2019b; O’Neill et al., 2018). Respecting ecological limits without compromising human or planetary wellbeing can be done if measures taken are just and equitable and if they effectively address excess wealth and consumption (Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020; Otto et al., 2019).

a. Steady-state economy

A steady state economy would be one that undergoes neither growth nor recession, resulting in a constant rate of throughput (the economy’s use of energy and materials) aligned with human population. This approach proposes legal limits to throughput, allowing the economy to develop qualitatively within such limits (Daly & Farley, 2011; Dietz & O’Neill, 2013). Since the 1970s, the concept has been associated with the work of Herman Daly, which includes the ecological analysis of natural resource flows through the economy and that recommends immediate political action to establish the steady-state economy by imposing permanent government restrictions on all resource use (Daly & Farley, 2011). Four key features of steady state economy include: 1) sustainable scale, 2) fair distribution, 3) efficient allocation and 4) high quality of life. Critics of the steady-state economy argue that resource decoupling, technological development and the operation of market mechanisms are capable of overcoming resource scarcity, pollution, or population overshoot. Proponents maintain that these objections remain insubstantial and mistaken (Dietz & O’Neill, 2013).

b. Degrowth

Degrowth is both an academic concept and a social movement studying and advocating for a downscaling of production and consumption to reduce ecological footprints planned democratically in a way that is equitable while securing wellbeing (Kallis et al., 2018). This strand of literature suggests that, because of the current coupling between Gross Domestic Product and environmental pressures, the only viable option left for high-income economies to bring back their footprints to sustainable levels is to produce and consume less (Parrique et al., 2019). The focal point of degrowth is mainly – although not exclusively – to phase down or phase out socially unessential and ecologically unsustainable goods and services. Degrowth advocates assume that the magnitude of this drawdown will be so significant that it will lead to a decrease in overall levels of GDP. Growth-critical scholars argue that prosperity can be achieved without further economic growth or even at lower levels of output granted a more equitable sharing of available wealth (Hickel & Sullivan, 2024). As a transition strategy, degrowth only applies to affluent parts of the world where resource use could be most easily reduced to free up biophysical budgets for poorer communities whose needs remain unmet (De Schutter, 2024). Degrowth remain a controversial term with critiques arguing that such macroeconomic slowdown might be either unnecessary if economic growth can be greened or even undesirable if it generates unemployment, financial instability, or puts strain on the ability of a state to finance itself (for a review of critiques of degrowth, see Parrique (2020), chapter 7). Other critiques also argue that most studies on degrowth are opinions rather than analysis, few use empirical data or adopt a system-wide perspective and instead most focus on small, local cases without a clear implication for the economy as a whole, for which their results are not scalable (van den Bergh & Kallis, 2012).

c. Post-growth

This school of thought focuses on the need to decouple well-being from economic growth (Wiedmann et al., 2020). This proposal, developed by the German economist Niko Paech (2012), centres around the idea of reducing consumerism¹⁴, supporting repairing skills and promoting regional economic production. It is based on principles of deceleration, decluttering/moderation, communal use/sharing production-consumption, repairing skills and a fruitful local economy. All these lead to an increase in social justice on a global scale while remaining within the ecological boundaries. According to Paech, if these principles are to be followed, this would lead to a reduction of the current industrial production. It argues for environmental and well-being policies, regardless of their effects on GDP (Raworth, 2017; van den Bergh & Kallis, 2012).

Table SM.5.6. Instruments for limiting growth.

Instruments	Description	Examples	Key actors	References
Downscaling levels of production	organize an equitable rationing of a declining volume of natural	Personal carbon allowances and other ‘cap and	- Intergovern. org.	(Fleming & Chamberlin, 2011; Fuso

¹⁴ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Instruments	Description	Examples	Key actors	References
	resources to reduce resource use and environmental impacts	share' schemes such as Tradable Energy Quotas (TEQs); needs-based water rationing schemes during droughts.	- National government - Private sector	Nerini et al., 2021)
Frugal consumption	Encourage minimalist lifestyles and cultures of sufficiency by removing incentives to consume and facilitate low impact means of need satisfaction	Limit advertising, ban planned obsolescence ¹⁴ , regulate online shopping, invest in public facilities for collective, shared consumption	- Individuals - Municipality - Civil society - National governments	(Berger et al., 2024; Jackson, 2021; Soper, 2020)
Share of welfare infrastructures	organize needs-satisfaction based on common access rather than private possession to increase the wellbeing of all.	Shared ownership (e.g., tool libraries, repair cafés). Promote borrowing, renting, gifting, swapping and buying used, common, or idle resources.	- Municipality - National government - Civil society	(Bollier & Helfrich, 2019; Hüttel et al., 2020)
Relocalize the economy		<i>Satoyama</i> in Japan; community energy cooperatives; energy sharing platforms; microgrid; local currencies	- Civil society - Individuals - Municipality	(Albert & Tercero-Lucas, 2020; Leach et al., 2021; Pulighe & Lupia, 2020)

3. Wellbeing within Planetary Boundaries

The 'wellbeing with planetary boundaries' approach includes proposals for a 'economy of the common good', 'doughnut economy,' and "*buen vivir*". It mostly corresponds to the alternative economic vision labelled Wellbeing for All Within Planetary Boundaries (**chapter 2, table 2.1**).

These approaches built on the idea of a ‘safe operating space’ or a ‘safe and just space’ for humans living in harmony with the natural environment by keeping the impacts of their activities within planetary boundaries. It also entails living with values oriented towards ‘sufficiency’ in resource consumption so that both physical and social provisioning systems are balanced with nature’s capacities. Goals of this approach include reducing inequality, enhancing social supports, meeting the sustainability goals associated with the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals, while shifting the economic agenda away from (financial, monetary and material) growth towards sustainable and equitable human wellbeing within planetary boundaries. Core values that focus on life-centred economics supporting this approach include stewardship of the whole system (at multiple levels), co-creation of collective value, cosmopolitan localist governance shifting decision democratically and locally, ecological regeneratively, reciprocity and circularity, emphasis on relationality and connectedness and equitable markets and trade.

a. Economy of the Common Good

This approach is based on the constitutional merit of common welfare/common good, which can be found in most constitutions around the world. At its core, it advocates that the economy is to be at the service of the common good (not at the service of private benefits). The Austrian economist Christian Felber developed a matrix, which includes five main categories: human dignity, solidarity and justice, ecological sustainability and transparency and participation (Felber, 2015). The matrix is based on a point-receiving system and can be applied to communities, companies, schools and even private households.

An alternative proposal for the commons views roots itself in communal governance of goods. Ostrom conceptualized this approach identifying nine principles of Common Pool Resources (CPR), which include the clear definition of resources, their provision and appropriation and the conception of collective decision-making processes (Ostrom, 1990). A Commons Transition movement moves away from the legislative economic framework of property law and focuses on expanding the practical side of what it means to share and manage resources within a community. It, therefore, supports self-organized working communities that sustain themselves and their environments by collectively managing resources and promoting new models of production.

b. Doughnut Economy

The principal idea of the Doughnut economy is to meet the needs of all within the means of the planet. This framework uses the planetary boundaries as an outer set of constraints and offers an inner set of social foundations of what people need as a minimal social foundation, with the ‘doughnut’ in between considered a safe operating space for humanity. The doughnut of social and planetary boundaries is a chart that visualizes the impact of our current global economic system. It depicts nine planetary boundaries (e.g., climate change, nature decline and air pollution) and twelve dimensions of a social foundation (e.g., food, water and housing). The goal of the Doughnut chart is to illustrate a potential balance between our needs and those of the planet. Combines attention to the legitimate needs of the present human population with the need for a transformation to a sustainable future (Raworth, 2017). Raworth describes the ‘Doughnut

Economics’ as: ‘A new model of human wellbeing that depends on enabling every person to lead a life of dignity and opportunity, while safeguarding the integrity of Earth’s life-supporting systems within planetary boundaries’.

c. Buen Vivir

This proposal originates from Indigenous communities in the Andes. ‘*Sumak Kawsay*’ (Quechua) or ‘*Suma Qamaña*’ (Aymara) are two of the names given to the concept, which is loosely translated into Spanish as ‘*Buen Vivir*’ (Escobar, 2011). Similar notions of this concept can be found in Guatemala, Mexico, Panama and Chile. At its centre, *Buen Vivir* is about harmonious life between human beings themselves and their environment. This diverse movement sees human beings, especially Indigenous Peoples as the stewards, even guardians, of the earth and nature. It is a vital economic practice within the individual communities and stands in stark contrast to our Western notion of property. The *Buen Vivir* movement acknowledges that “the good life” or “good living” is to be considered as something that is undergoing a constant construction and reproduction process and as such can never fully be attained but always worked towards. Based on the idea of "*sumak kawsay*", the government of Ecuador introduced the "Plan Nacional de Desarrollo”, which establishes a set of bold public policies aimed at strengthening Indigenous self-organization as opposed to capitalist development.

Instruments for strategy 3

This section presents instruments and actions to influence indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, focusing on transformation of economic systems. Trade and investment are major factors affecting nature and current global supply chain arrangements often encourage unsustainable sourcing or overproduction (Clapp & Isakson, 2018). Reforming these agreements and establishing green procurement policies, which include sustainability and biodiversity standards and certification schemes, can be powerful ways to promote pro-biodiversity production and trade (Lindström et al., 2020), although at present such measures remain weak (Dauvergne, 2018). However, environmental sustainability reporting standards are evolving globally, such as European Union’s Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) and its Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (European Commission, 2023; K. Hummel & Jobst, 2024).

Financial institutions (e.g., banks, investors and insurance companies) have a large potential to bring about change among the companies in their portfolios mostly by anchoring nature in companies’ non-financial reporting to influence the decisions made and shift sectoral investment flows in a more nature-friendly direction. Currently, the motivation of financial institutions is mostly driven by risk and reputation management. For instance, investment decisions and engagement with investee companies are based on the exposure of companies to climate change risks and on their capacity to manage these risks. Innovative financial instruments communicate the value of nature to financiers in monetary terms (Dasgupta, 2021). Currently, green financial products like green bonds, green loans, equity funds and others account for \$3.8 billion to \$6.3 billion (Deutz et al., 2020; Tobin-de la Puente & Mitchell, 2021). A considerable number of loans and investments could be linked to nature decline. Engagement by financial organizations must be made legitimate and supported by national and international policies with a clear vision

and targets. Finance also needs to move away from nature-harming industries such as fossil fuels towards environmentally beneficial activities. The increasingly common requirement for loan recipients to comply with Equator Principles on minimizing environmental and social impact as a condition of receiving capital investment is an example of such a transition already underway

1. Innovative financial instruments

All innovative finance instruments have a material basis for making transactions possible. Many instruments tie financial resources to objects like credits, rights, quotas, offsets and permits that in many ways give access to natural capital (van der Hoff R & Zwieten NA, 2022). Access to nature should be understood either as a source of natural resources (e.g., permits to extract fish) or as a sink for the wasteful byproducts of economic activity (e.g., credits for greenhouse gas emissions). In the financial sector, proposed instruments include bonds, derivatives, securities, swaps, futures and insurances, that facilitate investments in conservation (e.g., green bonds) or hedge against the risk of nature decline (e.g., weather derivatives) (Anyango-van Zwieten, 2021; S. Sullivan, 2018). Some of these instruments include:

Green (or blue) bond markets, of which biodiversity is a small share, offer the possibility of raising financial resources for green development projects and natural assets (e.g., marine protected areas and sustainable fisheries management) in exchange for a return to the investor after the contract period ends (Tobin-de la Puente & Mitchell, 2021).

Biodiversity credit schemes are tradeable credits based on nature to incentivize conservation and restoration. However, incorporating the multifaceted aspects of nature meaningfully in credit schemes remains challenging (Ducros & Steele, 2022). Moreover, current schemes fail to balance scientific understandings of nature with socio-cultural values, which challenges aligning credit schemes with the knowledges, needs, values and aspirations of Indigenous Peoples and local communities

Risk-related financial disclosures: Methods and indicators are available for measuring progress on managing nature impacts and dependencies on natural capital and large companies are obliged to report on sustainability to track progress on commitments. Enforcing and extending such obligation could be an important enabling factor for financial institutions to be a driver of change (Van Oorschot et al., 2020). The disclosure of this information could enable societal actors and financial institutions to provide the right incentives and triggers for businesses to step up. An analysis of a balanced data panel of 8,320 firm-year observations from 832 global companies operating in different sectors of activity over the period 2011–2020, indicates that institutional investors, especially those with investment a long-term investment horizon, are interested in biodiversity commitments and exercise their demand for information (i.e., disclosure) on these initiatives through their representatives on the board of directors. Companies are rewarded for disclosing relevant information on business policies, nature management and the valuation of ecosystem services in the value chain (Ali et al., 2024).

Biodiversity offsets¹⁵ are compensatory measures for unavoidable nature decline, after prevention and mitigation measures have taken place, where developers or companies invest in nature conservation elsewhere. In most biodiversity offsets schemes the biodiversity in areas with natural vegetation is assessed based on indicators of habitat type, species, threat level, richness, rarity, diversity and connectivity. These indicators are then used to classify these areas and establish biodiversity offset credits, which are the financeable objects of biodiversity offsetting that can be acquired by developers to compensate for their impact on nature (Koh et al., 2019). At least 37 countries have laws requiring biodiversity offsets as a prerequisite for certain developments. Close to 13 000 offset projects have been identified across these countries (J. W. Bull & Strange, 2018). Finance mobilized by biodiversity offsets has been estimated at \$6-\$9 billion per year (Deutz et al., 2020).

Innovative financing instruments for nature conservation commonly involve multi-actor networks. Firstly, they establish connections between the “users” and “providers” of nature. For example, biodiversity offsetting ties potentially harmful development projects to conservation efforts and responsible investors can buy green bonds from organizations or governments that develop sustainable economic activities or strengthen conservation. Secondly, the actor networks of innovative finance instruments often extend beyond “users” and “providers.” In Germany, for example, municipal governments are responsible for matching the supply side (i.e., buying or leasing land for conservation) and the demand side (i.e., reviewing assessments of nature decline at impact sites) of development impact compensation (Koh et al., 2019). Some finance instruments also link conservation actions across governance levels. In the case of the Amazon Fund, the financial resources are passed on by the recipient (i.e., Amazon Fund) to projects that correspond with core categories of Brazilian environmental policies, most notably monitoring and control, land tenure and regularization and sustainable economic activities. These examples suggest a potential of some nature finance instruments to foster coordination among different actors toward nature conservation objectives.

2. Redistribution of wealth

About 10% of the world population owns 76% of global wealth, 52% of global income and accounts for almost half (48%) of global carbon emissions (Chancel et al., 2022). Increased wealth inequalities limit the state and civil society’s ability to manage and fund conservation or other transformative options (Chancel et al., 2022). Economically powerful actors pursue agendas based on private interests that are often at odds with sustainability (Ceddia, 2020; Downey & Strife, 2010; Kenner, 2019). For instance, in the European Union, lobby groups push for increased agricultural intensification over multifunctional agriculture (Anania et al., 2015; Erjavec & Erjavec, 2020). Unregulated and highly unequal global financial trade is often associated with speculative investments - often coined as land grabs - that often harm local communities and the environment (Galaz et al., 2015; Zoomers, 2010). Power inequality increases deforestation in the tropics through increased investments in land-based commodities by the wealthiest (Ceddia, 2020; Galaz et al., 2015, 2018; Rijk et al., 2023) and correlates with nature decline and reduced willingness to collaborate with environmental policy (Holland et al., 2009; Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Such correlation also exists when income inequality and other

¹⁵ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

measures of environmental degradation (e.g., air pollution) are considered, although the evidence is mixed for other indicators such as increased level of species imperilments highlighting the complexity of the inequality-environment (or inequality-biodiversity) relationship (Hamann et al., 2018; Kubiszewski et al., 2024). Land has been found to be highly unequally distributed globally, affecting women, the landless and Indigenous communities more specifically, with significant indirect impacts on nature and equity (Anseeuw & Baldinelli, 2020; Benra & Nahuelhual, 2019; Laterra et al., 2019). Redistribution of wealth (i.e., land, investments, capital, infrastructure) is a key policy option¹⁶ to alleviate root drivers of unsustainable production and consumption.

Several policy instruments have been proposed to redistribute wealth. These include changes in taxation systems and inheritance, policies to further integrate externalities emerging from global trade and finance and other social and economic policies. In terms of addressing wealth inequalities, options also include making the system more transparent or reforming tax systems to capture more revenues from the very wealthy. Wealth tax targeting the very rich which could bring revenues to states to tackle inequality and ecological transition e.g., reform tax law to implement progressive taxation on wealth (Chancel et al., 2022). although such reforms need to be carefully considered and contextualized. The tax on foreign exchange transactions, known as Tobin tax, is also another option proposed to limit speculation and reduce financial volatility. Such tax would raise revenue from the global financial market, but it has never been applied (McCulloch & Pacillo, 2011). Actions to tackle land inequality include land redistribution and agrarian reforms – that need to be carefully implemented and contextualized to avoid unintended consequences (Cousins & Scoones, 2010; Scoones et al., 2011); reform in land taxes; regulation of land markets and greater corporate and investor accountability (Anseeuw & Baldinelli, 2020). More radical approaches propose to address root causes of inequalities namely the presence of inequality regimes that sustain continued inequality through time (Piketty, 2020).

3. Universal basic income

Core to most definitions of Universal Basic Income is the payment of an unconditional, regular income by the state to every resident in a country. Unconditionality means that payments do not depend on levels of other income sources or wealth, willingness to work, or domestic living arrangements. While Universal Basic Income was not primarily developed to deal with the triple planetary crisis, some authors have highlighted its potential benefits for addressing it by supporting post-growth economic systems (Büchs, 2021; Van Parijs & Vanderborght, 2017). Specifically, scholars argue that Universal Basic Income could facilitate a transition to a sustainable economy by supporting livelihoods during economic stagnation or decline. Supporters argue that Universal Basic Income might reduce consumption-driven spending and conspicuous consumption, promoting more purposeful activities, consequently decreasing resource use and related environmental impacts (Lawhon & McCreary, 2020; Van Parijs & Vanderborght, 2017). Detractors, however, argue that UBI could boost material consumption by enhancing economic efficiency and incentivizing labour market participation. An analysis of a Universal Basic Income experiment that covered a whole town in Canada in the 1970s found an aggregate decrease of labour market participation and an increase in wages (Calnitsky, 2020).

¹⁶ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

But things are complicated by the fact that higher income groups would experience a net loss of income from a Universal Basic Income that is financed through progressive taxation. If higher income groups want to maintain their lifestyles, they may still increase supply of labour (Büchs, 2021).

The potential impact of Universal Basic Income on consumption remains uncertain, with models suggesting that redistributing income to poorer groups might increase consumption and emissions due to their higher carbon-intensive spending habits (Oswald et al., 2021). Furthermore, a Universal Basic Income on its own would not change the way in which goods are produced or services provided and it would not dis/incentivize what people could spend the additional income on. If there are few options for environmentally friendly consumption, or if people choose to spend their income on high-impact products or services, a Universal Basic Income would have little capacity to reduce environmental impacts (Andersson, 2009; Boulanger, 2009; MacNeill & Vibert, 2019). Some scholars have proposed Universal Basic Income could be coupled with environmental policies, for instance by financing it through progressive taxes on natural resources or pollution. The analysis of case studies suggests that, despite best intentions, without critical engagement and nuance around questions of power, the radical potential of basic income may be jeopardized, with basic income becoming another technological quick fix of development and policy interventions (Fouksman & Klein, 2019).

4. Localization/deglobalization

At a lower spatial scale, instruments exist to localize or deglobalize how finance works, largely by giving a much greater role for short, local supply chains (including urban farming) (J. F. Albert & Tercero-Lucas, 2020; Leach et al., 2021; Pulighe & Lupia, 2020). Instruments in this line range from localizing production and consumption to tourism systems that promote local travel, linking to *Buen Vivir* and convivialism (Everingham & Chassagne, 2020; Lehto et al., 2020) and postdevelopment ‘delinking’ from the dominance of high-income countries in globalized trade, whereby governments of low-income countries collectively demand fairer trade conditions (Hickel, 2022). Deglobalization was seen to align closely with degrowth (Ashford et al., 2020; Çakar & Uzut, 2020). Deglobalization processes encourage, rather than homogenise, local nuances in approaches to change (L. V. Gibbons, 2020).

5. Not-for-profit

The not-for-profit economy (e.g., foundation-owned limited liability companies, consumer cooperatives, credit unions, mutual companies) is a promising model to deliver broader societal (and environmental) benefits. This is because, in contrast to the for-profit economy, there is a wider circulation of resources and there is no inherent incentive for overconsumption, wage suppression, private wealth accumulation, political capture, or market concentration; all of which contribute to growing inequality and contribute to extractive economies (Hinton, 2020, 2021; Hinton & Maclurcan, 2017). For-profit legal frameworks are designed to enrich investors through the distribution of surplus (profit) rather than to achieve social and environmental goals (Foster, 2014; Hinton, 2020, 2021; Magdoff & Foster, 2011; Schnaiberg et al., 2002). These for-profit economic models have money as the goal and measure of success (e.g., GDP, profit) and

are a major driver of overproduction and overconsumption that contribute to the climate crisis and biodiversity loss (Foster, 2014; J. W. Moore, 2014; Schnaiberg et al., 2002).

There is considerable diversity in not-for-profit businesses, which is one of the strengths of this model (Hinton, 2023). That said, most not-for-profit businesses are either: not-for-profit organizations that generate most or all their income through selling goods and services (e.g., Goodwill); or standard for-profit businesses that are 100% owned by a not-for-profit association or foundation (e.g., Patagonia). Instruments of the not-for-profit economy include foundation-owned limited liability companies, consumer cooperatives, credit unions, or mutual companies (Hinton, 2021; Hinton, 2020; Hinton & Maclurcan, 2017). Consumer cooperatives (including credit unions and mutual insurance companies) are also not-for-profit businesses. Examples include cinemas and recreation centres owned by associations; hotels and restaurants owned by foundations, farms and energy systems owned by a community trust; non-profits that operate recycling centres and second-hand shops; consumer cooperative grocery stores; or credit unions and savings and loans banks (Hinton, 2023). Some of these not-for-profit enterprises have existed for a long time, for instance, BRAC (which started in Bangladesh in the 1970s but has now expanded to several other countries) is a not-for-profit foundation that owns and operates several businesses and uses the profit to make healthcare and education more accessible to people in the countryside. BRAC's businesses include a dairy, retail of handmade artisan goods and microloan services ((BRAC, 2024).

For-profit models that seek to balance people, planet and profit as goals (e.g., benefit corporations in the US) reinvest their surplus into social benefit, but these models can still drive inequality and overconsumption because they do not address the trade-offs between using limited resources to enrich private investors and using those resources to achieve social and environmental benefit (Hinton, 2021; Hinton, 2020; Lodsgård & Aagaard, 2017; Schneider, 2020).

6. Harnessing new adaptive capacities to react to crises

Crises deserve attention in discussions of transformative change because they often prove to be “game changers” (Loorbach et al., 2016), changing the existing status quo. Crises may reinforce processes driving inequalities and vulnerabilities. Powerful actors often take advantage of crises, including natural disasters and wars, to further accumulate resources and establish policies that are favourable to their interests during times when people are emotionally, financially and socially less able to resist such actions (V. Adams et al., 2009; Klein, 2007). For instance, in the United States of America, the Trump administration revoked several key environmental provisions while public interest focused on the COVID-19 pandemic (Powers et al., 2021). But crises might also open opportunities to change ways of doing, thinking and organizing, which may lead to shifts towards sustainable and/or just pathways. In terms of unleashing or changing values towards pro-environmental behaviours and practices, crises often enable diverse ways of framing and knowing to permeate the broader social discourse (Wittmayer et al., 2019). For example, the 2010 economic crisis favoured a back-to-the-land movement in Greece where people experimented with sustainable farming practices, catalysing agency for collective action in response to a failing political and economic system (Benessaiah & Eakin, 2021). This was possible in part because previous models of social success were discredited, opening spaces for experimentation. Other studies similarly show how crises often enable experimentations that may

prove valuable for learning how to transform. This focus on ‘doing’ to bring about the future one desires has been called ‘prefiguration’ (Trott, 2016). The ‘Occupy’ movement, as well as the ‘indignados’ movement in Europe, are good case studies to illustrate how times of crises could lead to inner transformations as well as collective action that build a basis for future transformations, often by putting emphasis on experimentation. The 2010 financial crisis which intersected with more long-term crises such as rising inequalities and poverty, led to people experimenting with new political structures and decision-making processes in their daily lives (Asara, 2020; Benessaiah & Eakin, 2021; Maeckelbergh, 2011). These led – in some cases – to a strengthening of values, political projects and practices around ideas such as self-organization, environmental sustainability and social justice, that have percolated in some instances to more formal political organization, for instance by electing progressive municipal governments in Spain (Bua & Bussu, 2021), reclaiming autonomy as seen in the Zapatistas movement in Mexico (Stahler-Sholk, 2007) or new sustainability food initiatives in Greece post-2010 economic crisis (Benessaiah, 2021; Benessaiah & Chan, 2023). In other cases, these crises reinforced other values and ideas centred around populism and authoritarianism as can be seen by the rise of right-wing movements around the world (Gelcich et al., 2010; Scoones et al., 2022). Ultimately, whether these new ideas and their underlying values, lead to broader transformations depends on context and the ability of people to build capacities, a process that often takes a long time. An example of how long it may take for ideas at the margin to scale up to policy change include the linkages between the 2011 Occupy Wall Street movement and its organizing and Biden’s recent announcement in 2022 that student loan relief would be implemented (Solnit, Rebecca, 2022).

7. Alternatives to GDP

Gross Domestic Product is a widely used measure of economic growth, but it is also criticized due to its reliance on marketed goods and services only (Costanza et al., 2009; Stiglitz et al., 2018). An important distinction needs to be drawn here between GDP growth and the growth of material throughput to the economy. The post-growth literature mainly focuses on material throughput as this is the main criterion for planetary boundaries. However, some of the post-growth literature also remains critical of GDP growth because currently available evidence suggests it is unlikely to be technologically feasible to stay within planetary boundaries while global GDP continues to grow. Even though there are examples of absolute decoupling between GDP growth and environmental impacts in some rich countries, decoupling only occurred at very low rates of growth and the rate of reduction of environmental impacts remains too slow to be compatible with planetary boundaries (Haberl et al., 2020). Beyond GDP, various measures of economic growth have been proposed that are more inclusive and representative of human wellbeing (Kubiszewski et al., 2013; Pinyol Alberich et al., 2022; Stiglitz et al., 2018). Proposed instruments either adjust the traditional form of GDP by including environmental considerations account for economic activity’s impacts on resource depletion, environmental degradation and pollution (i.e., Green GDP, Genuine Progress Indicator, Product Biodiversity Footprint, Genuine Savings), replace it with more inclusive indices that account for human wellbeing (e.g., Happy Planet Index, Human Development Index) or supplement it (e.g., System of Environmental Economic Accounting). For example, the Green Growth Index produced by Global Green Growth Institute measures the performance of countries or regions in achieving sustainability targets including Sustainable Development Goals, Paris Climate Agreement and Aichi Biodiversity Targets from four green growth dimensions: efficient and sustainable resource use,

natural capital protection, green economic opportunities and social inclusion (Acosta et al., 2020).

Some of these measures have been applied to calculate progress in different countries and contexts. For example, green GDP has been assessed for China (Liang & Luo, 2023), Ecuador (Sánchez et al., 2020), Jordan (Hajar & Hajer, 2023) and Pakistan (Jabeen & Khan, 2022). Green GDP has also been calculated for OECD countries (Ates and Derinkuyu (2021), the European Union (Cheba & Bâk, 2019) and globally (Acosta et al.(2020) for global; Adamowicz (2022) for global; and Stjepanović et al. (2019)for developing and developed countries. The Inclusive Wealth Index (Managi & Kumar, 2018) has been applied to assess progress in Pakistan (Islam et al., 2022),African regions (Coulibaly & Managi, 2023) and China (Fan et al., 2022). The Index of Sustainable Economic Welfare or Genuine Progress Indicator has been applied in the United States (Fox & Erickson, 2018; Howarth & Kennedy, 2016), Germany (Held et al., 2018), Belgium (Van der Slycken and Bleys (2023), as well as globally (Pais et al., 2019).

Table SM.5.7. Selective set of beyond GDP measures

Alternative to GDP	Pros	Cons	Proponent and source
Human Development Index (HDI)	It emphasizes that people and their capabilities should be the ultimate criteria for assessing the development of a country. It considers three dimensions of social development: health, education and standard of living. It is widely used in developing economies.	Could hide inequality. Does not consider environmental degradation.	Created by UN (Barnes & Boait, 2020)
Genuine Progress Indicator (GPI)	It considers both positive and negative results of economic activity and provides net benefit; consider non-financial transactions; It shifts the value basis of a product by adding its social and environmental impacts	The measurement of non-economic variables is subjective	Proposed by scientists, see (Berik, 2018; Kubiszewski et al., 2013)
Thriving Places Index (TPI)	It provides a breakdown of holistic elements that help support thriving communities and economies, including mental and physical health, education and learning,	It seems a too radical departure from the current GDP paradigm	(TPI, 2023)

Alternative to GDP	Pros	Cons	Proponent and source
	work and local economy and green infrastructure.		
Green GDP	It measures the cost of environmental damage as the result of economic growth by subtracting factors such as resource depletion and environmental degradation from the GDP.	It modifies economic growth statistics.	(Georgeson et al., 2017)
Better Life Index (BLI)	It includes 80 indicators of wellbeing that provide a comprehensive picture of natural, human, economic and social capital.	From a finance perspective, the information in the index may not contain enough economic indicators to provide a satisfactory GDP alternative	(OECD, 2023b)
Inclusive Wealth Index (IWI)	It measures the wealth of nations considering the assets from which human wellbeing is derived – manufactured, human and natural capital. It includes “green” accounting into the assessment of capital assets and assesses changes in natural capital.	The IWI needs to be part of broader macroeconomic planning, alongside other indicators.	Developed by the UN (Polasky et al., 2015)
Genuine Savings Indicator (GSI)	The GSI considers factors such as public investments of resource revenues and the social costs of pollution emissions as equally relevant aspects in determining the overall level of saving.	Until tools have been developed to measure this reliably, it is a fundamentally flawed way of measuring economic health	Developed by the World Bank (Hamilton, 2000)

Alternative to GDP	Pros	Cons	Proponent and source
Happy Planet Index (HPI)	It is a composite measure combining three elements – life expectancy, wellbeing and ecological footprint	Ecological footprint is a contentious measure of economic development; it also fails to account for some key happiness killers, such as human rights violations and modern slavery	Developed by the UK’s New Economic Foundation (HPI, 2023)
Gross National Happiness Index (GNH index)	It combines traditional, interdependent social and economic factors with non-economic aspects. It integrates aspect for the social and economic dimensions of sustainable development, cultural preservation, environmental conservation and good governance.	The subjective nature of measuring wellbeing and happiness makes it difficult to apply the GNH index.	Applied in Bhutan (Riedy, 2020)
System of Environmental Economics Accounting (SEEA)	It focuses on environment and economy; specific focus is on ecosystem. Capturing the value of natural capital	Valuing some of the non-marketed goods and services from using some methods may not be applicable	(United Nations, 2012)
Gross Ecosystem Product (GEP)	It focuses on the value of ecosystem services to the economy in monetary terms; fully captures the contributions of nature to economic activity and human well-being; can be constructed concurrently to GDP.	Only limited to the contributions of ecosystem services; many services that are part of GDP are excluded, e.g., manufacturing, construction, transportation etc.	(Ouyang et al., 2020; Polasky, 2023; Zhiyun et al., 2013)
True Cost Accounting	It calculates the real cost of a specific product or service, including its effects on the natural and social environment in which a company operates	Calculations are excessively complex	The State of Food and Agriculture 2023 and upcoming State of Food and Agriculture 2024. Revealing the true cost of food to transform agrifood

Alternative to GDP	Pros	Cons	Proponent and source
			systems (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2023)

8. Regulating global exchange prices

Regulation of the financial sector might also have economic co-benefits: Reducing systemic risks in the supply and trade of essential products (such as food and energy) enhances the resilience of social and economic systems. Regulation can also ensure that financial institutions take nature into account when they assess the value of their assets and the risks of planned investments.

International trade and investment are major factors affecting nature and current global supply chain arrangements often encourage unsustainable sourcing or overproduction (Clapp & Isakson, 2018). Supply chains are increasingly organized on a global level, at which government regulation is largely absent (Hajer, 2003), with the governance of international trade mostly handled by the financial and economic sectors. Unregulated global financial trade is often associated with speculative investments - often coined as land grabs - that often harm local communities and the environment (Galaz et al., 2015; Zoomers, 2010). Substantive reforms to agreements that regulate the global supply chain can be powerful ways to promote pro-nature production and trade (Lindström et al., 2020), although at present such measures remain weak (Dauvergne, 2018). Asymmetric net flows of biophysical resources from poorer to richer countries enable a “hidden transfer of value” from low- to high-income countries, which takes place subtly with prices naturalized on the grounds that they represent the outcome of market mechanisms, expressed in value prices. Therefore, price differentials in international trade maintain unsustainable patterns of nature appropriation (Amin, 1978). Environmental input-output data and footprint analysis quantifying the physical scale of net appropriation from low-income countries in terms of embodied resources and labor over the period 1990 to 2015 provides empirical evidence for ecologically unequal exchange as a persistent feature of the global economy from 1990 to 2015 (Dorninger et al., 2021; Hickel et al., 2022). Over the period 1990-2015, high-income countries obtained without compensation in equivalent terms through trade enough resources to end extreme poverty 70 times over. These resources were the equivalent to 12 billion tons of embodied raw material equivalents, 822 million hectares of embodied land, 21 exajoules of embodied energy and 188 million person-years of embodied labour, worth \$10.8 trillion in high-income countries prices. Over the period, drain from low-income countries totalled \$242 trillion (constant 2010 USD). This drain represents a significant windfall for the high-income countries, equivalent to a quarter of high-income countries GDP. Low-income countries’ losses due to unequal exchange outstrip their total aid receipts over the period by a factor of 30 (Hickel et al., 2022).

Regulating global exchange prices to reduce price disparities would help diminish the high-income countries net resource appropriation. This, in turn, would alleviate ecologically unequal exchange, lower excessive consumption in high income countries, and reduce the ecological harm inflicted on low-income countries (Hickel et al., 2022). Additionally, it would enable low-income countries to earn a fairer income from international trade, allowing them to better

mobilize domestic resources and labor to meet local needs. Following the polluter pays principle, which is applied in the European Union, the United Kingdom, the United States of America, and other OECD countries, the social, economic, and ecological damages linked to resource appropriation from the South – including those from emissions – should be compensated by the appropriators.

9. Reconsidering global debts

There have been calls to reduce or eliminate debt from low income countries that severely prevents countries from investing into biodiversity and/or other social and ecological goals (Srinivasan et al., 2008). One research group found that the share of low income countries government resources dedicated to foreign debt repayment tripled from 2011 to 2020, to an average of 17.4%, with some as high as 40% (Dempsey et al., 2022; Ghosh & Kvangraven, 2021). Calls have also been made to democratise the institutions of global economic governance, such as the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund and the World Trade Organization, so that low income countries have more control over trade and finance policy. More radical approaches towards debt included debt cancellation and debt-free financial aid. Some proponents of debt cancellation emphasize that the external debt from low to high income countries has already been paid on account of the ecological debt high income countries owes to low income countries, including the Jubilee 2000 campaign of Christian churches for cancellation of external debt (see Paredis (2009) for a review; Warlenius et al., 2015),

Ecological debt has been defined as 1) the ecological damage caused over time by a country in other countries or to ecosystems beyond national jurisdiction through its production and consumption patterns; 2) the exploitation or use of ecosystems (and its goods and services) over time by a country at the expense of the equitable rights to these ecosystems by other countries (Hornborg & Martinez-Alier, 2016). The debt arises from: 1) exports of raw materials and other products from relatively poor countries or regions being sold at prices which do not include compensation for local or global externalities; 2) rich countries or regions making disproportionate use of environmental space or services without payment (for instance, to dump carbon dioxide). Ecological debt usually designates a public debt a country has towards other countries (foreign debt) but can also be used to calculate a debt (or liability) from a company (private debt) or a debt a nation has towards future generations (generational debt) (Goeminne & Paredis, 2010). Ecological debt has been defined as 1) the ecological damage caused over time by a country in other countries or to ecosystems beyond national jurisdiction through its production and consumption patterns; 2) the exploitation or use of ecosystems (and its goods and services) over time by a country at the expense of the equitable rights to these ecosystems by other countries (Goeminne & Paredis, 2010; Hornborg & Martinez-Alier, 2016).

10. Official development assistance

Official development assistance can be an important lever for biodiversity conservation – or if badly designed – for drivers of nature decline in the global south. Development aid for agriculture could benefit from clearer defining biodiversity standards for all projects and implement them already before degradation is visible (Dávalos et al., 2016; Hugé et al., 2020).

Overall, development projects funded by international bodies and bilateral cooperation have shown to strongly overlap with biodiversity hotspots and Indigenous territories and thereby pose strong threats to the integrity of ecosystems and local communities (Yang et al., 2021). Global and private land-grabbing activities further add to this trend (Hausermann et al., 2018). A general use of Environmental Impact Assessments for ODA could be an option, but only if linked to general, legitimized biodiversity targets that are not dominated by utilitarian biodiversity framings (Hugé et al., 2017, 2020). As a direct option, the effects of official development assistance on biodiversity and good governance can be assessed (Miller et al., 2013) and efforts in international cooperation can be revised accordingly. Transparency and clear accountability frameworks for these trans-actions are important options for transformative action (Hausermann et al., 2018).

The example of the war on drugs in Latin America has shown that large part of deforestation resulted from anti-drug campaigns and alternative development projects (Maggiocca et al. 2024 Dávalos et al., 2016), as well as the privatised war on drugs with arising vested interests that have further weakened democratic institutions and destabilized social order (Bartilow, 2019; Hobson, 2014; Magliocca et al., 2024; McSweeney et al., 2014; Sesnie et al., 2017; Wrathall et al., 2020). About half of the global deforestation is linked to illegal forest conversion and is - particularly in Latin-America - strongly linked to drug production (Lawson, 2014). The appearance of drug production and trafficking routes are often located in deforestation hotspots, highlighting that conservation needs to be a central aspect of drug policy (McSweeney et al., 2014; Sesnie et al., 2017; Wrathall et al., 2020).

At the same time, there is growing evidence that it is not coca cultivation directly, but the related social problems such as poverty and migration coming with it, as well as coca eradication policies that drive deforestation (Dávalos et al., 2016). This corporate regime is investing money laundering activities that drive deforestation, controls land rights and corrupts elites and decision makers (Tellman et al., 2020). A fundamental challenge for addressing narcotrafficking is the fragmentation of policies across the trading and especially in the consuming countries, responding to narcotrafficking with diverging and incoherent framings ranging from security, to health or social policies (Bartilow, 2019; Bergman, 2018; Fukumi, 2016; Tellman et al., 2020). These complex interdependencies highlight the need for more integrated policy approaches and international collaboration in efforts to transform and govern the threats linked to illegal economies (see strategy 4).

Initiatives exemplifying actions in strategy 3

Several initiatives exist that have operationalized one or several of these approaches.

1. Corporate initiatives

Task Force on Nature-Related Financial Disclosures: This task force is a corporate-led effort that aims to identify how changes to nature may create financial risks for companies and investors. It aims at managing the impact of business on nature, with the assumption that risk disclosure will more effectively price nature-harming activities. Research shows that the relationship between disclosing nature risk and redirecting finance away from environmental degradation is tenuous and unproven, making this mechanism insufficient for addressing the impact of the financial

sector on nature (Irvine-Broque & Dempsey, 2023). Further, there are risks that this financial sector approach to nature will reinforce the highly unequal concentration of power and wealth, which is itself inimical to transformative change (Irvine-Broque & Dempsey, 2023).

The Equator Principles, a voluntary and self-regulatory Corporate Social Responsibility initiative in the field of project finance. They provide several principles to businesses to reduce the negative impacts of lending practices linked to environment-damaging projects. Research suggest that the actual impact of the EPs is very still limited due to their voluntary nature, their narrow focus on project finance and their lack of adequate governance mechanisms, that is, enforcement, monitoring and sanctioning (Hennig & Wörsdörfer, 2015). It is argued that (more) mandatory and legally binding rules and standards at the transnational level to overcome the EPs' 'voluntariness bias' (Hennig & Wörsdörfer, 2015). One examples of a company adopting voluntary and self-regulatory Corporate Social Responsibility programmes is the programme 'We Sea', Jealsa's Corporate Social Responsibility programme.

The Global Reporting Initiative has developed and delivered the global practice for how organizations communicate and demonstrate accountability for their impacts on the environment, economy and people. They provide the world's most widely used sustainability reporting standards, which cover topics that range from biodiversity to tax, waste to emissions, diversity and equality¹⁷ to health and safety (Ali et al., 2024). In January 2024, GRI released updated version of its standard (i.e., GRI 101: Biodiversity 2024 to be effective from January 2026 by replacing and expanding its earlier version GRI 304: Biodiversity 2016), which aligns the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and helps organizations to better understand which of their decisions and business activities lead to nature decline. It also helps them to locate where in their value chains biodiversity is being impacted and how they can manage such impacts. GRI disclosure standard is informed by initiatives and instruments such as TNFD, Science Based Targets Network and can be used to report biodiversity impacts in a transparent and accountable way (GRI, 2016; GRI & TNFD, 2024).

Finance for Biodiversity movement is growing through different initiatives that links to financial institutions for different topics and activities (Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, 2022). Financial institutions by these targeted initiatives are investors, banks, insurers and corporations. The type of activities includes sharing, co-development and collective action. The topics covered by these initiatives include Environmental Social Governance and engagement, measurement and data, target setting, reporting and disclosure, positive impact and public policy advocacy. Similarly, a sustainable blue economy finance initiative was launched in 2018 with 14 blue economy finance principles - protective, compliant, risk-aware, systemic, inclusive, cooperative, transparent, purposeful, impactful, precautionary, diversified, solution-driven, partnering, and science-led - to provide a framework for banks, insurers, and investors to finance blue economy (Benzaken et al., 2024; Stefanova et al., 2024; UNEP Finance Initiative, n.d.).

¹⁷ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Table SM.5.8. Overview of Finance for Biodiversity initiatives targeting different financial institutions and activities.

Initiative	Financial institutions targeted				Activities not covered
	Investors	Banks	Insurers	Corporations	
<i>F@B</i> Finance@BiodiversityCommunity	X	X	X		PPA
<i>FfB</i> Finance for Biodiversity Pledge and Foundation	X	X	X		
PRI Principles for Responsible Investment	X				RD, PI, PPA
<i>PRB, PSI & ILP</i> Principles for Responsible Banking, Principles for Sustainable Insurance & Investment Leadership Platform	X	X	X	X	
<i>TNFD</i> Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures	X	X	X	X	ESGE, TS, PI, PPA
<i>NatureFinance</i> formerly F4B Initiative	X	X	X	X	TS
<i>SBTN</i> Science Based Targets Network	X	X	X	X	PPA
<i>Align</i> Aligning accounting approaches for nature	X	X	X	X	ESGE
<i>PBAF</i> Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials	X	X	X		PPA
<i>ENCORE</i> Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities, Risks and Exposure	X	X	X		ESGE, RD, PI, PPA
CBF Consortium for Biodiversity Footprint	X	X	X		ESGE, TS, PI, PPA
<i>CPIC</i> Coalition for Private Investment in Conservation	X	X	X		ESGE, TS, RD, PPA
<i>BIOFIN</i> The Biodiversity Finance Initiative	X	X	X	X	
<i>CISL</i> University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	X	X	X		TS, PPA
<i>CFA</i> Conservation Finance Alliance	X	X	X	X	ESGE, RD

Initiative	Financial institutions targeted				Activities not covered
<i>WEF Learning Coalition</i> Biodiversity Finance Learning Coalition: Internalize the Externality	X	X	X		TS
<i>B4B + Club</i> Business for Positive Biodiversity Club	X	X	X	X	
<i>CERES</i> Land Use and Climate Working Group, Biodiversity	X	X			
<i>C4C</i> Capital for Climate	X	X	X	X	ESGE, TS, RD, PPA

(source Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, 2022, pp.3-4)

Wellbeing Economy Alliance, a global coalition of ‘new economy’ efforts aimed at fostering what can broadly be characterized as wellbeing economies. In a wellbeing economy, business and financial activities help achieve human and ecological prosperity, where the measure of social progress considers alternative measure to Gross Domestic Product as measures of social progress (WWF et al., 2022). Such measures accommodate three domains or dimensions of social progress: current wellbeing, distribution of the wellbeing (inclusion) and sustainability of the wellbeing in the future. There are different indices and indicators for each domain or dimension. For example, for sustainability domain, inclusive wealth could be an index and planetary boundaries could be the indicators (WWF et al., 2022).

2. Public initiatives

The IRP’s Global Material Flows Database, an initiative from the International Resource Panel offers comprehensive insight into the connections between the world economy, population and material use. The data set comprises four decades of global materials extraction and materials trade and provides direct and consumption-based material flow indicators for more than 185 countries, covering total usage, per capita use, material use per US dollar and details for different groups of materials. The information is central to monitoring the changing patterns of resource use at the global level as it provides data to help governments, policy researchers and interested stakeholders to understand and trace the linkages between economic growth and raw material usage.

The European Green Deal is the latest European Union growth and development agenda. It extends the idea of the US “New Deal” approach of massively investing in infrastructure projects to create jobs, but it targets jobs in the green and new economy sectors such as resilient construction, decarbonized energy, clean transport, sustainable agriculture and clean cities. The Global Green New Deal proposed by UNCTAD5 crucially includes an equality and equity dimension. The European Union identifies climate and environmental-related challenges to be of highest strategic importance and ‘this generation’s defining task’, justifying a set of ‘deeply transformative policies’ (Miola et al., 2019). It has been argued that the initiative is largely conceived as a transition to decarbonization through technological investments that pay little attention to the concurrent need to preserve nature and functioning ecosystems. At the level of the European Union, the extent of investments and the level of political willingness towards

climate neutrality and nature is too low (Penca, 2023). The nature restoration law, a pillar of the European Green deal, will set an obligation for EU countries to restore at least 20% of their land and seas by the end of the decade. It contains binding targets to restore at least 30% of degraded habitats by then, rising to 60% by 2040 and 90% by 2050. In European Union decision-making processes around creating an effective green architecture of the Common Agricultural Policy, for instance, well-organized farmer advocacy groups lobby for their interests (Anania et al., 2015). At the same time, these influential groups manage to position a productivist narrative in the societal discourse on land-use, prioritizing efficiency and intensification over multifunctionality and biodiversity conservation (Erjavec & Erjavec, 2020). To balance the different interests on a societal level, a stronger participation of other sectors (including the environment) in decision-making processes, such as in the decision bodies for designing the Common Agricultural Policy (Brown et al., 2019) and acknowledging and incorporating new discourses (Lakner et al., 2019) can strengthen the role of biodiversity. Different inter-institutional formats for decision-making have been proposed (Greer & Hind, 2012)

Green public procurement in Sweden: Green Public Procurement (GPP) policies have been established by several governments. In 2006, the Swedish government established a GPP stating objectives related to organic farming. The policy aims to increase the public sector's organic food purchases, to incentivize Swedish farmers to convert to organic practices, thereby contributing to national environmental quality objectives. Analysis of this policy from 2003 to 2016 including information on municipalities' organic food purchases, land use and direct subsidies aimed at organic production suggest that the 2006 organic food policy is associated with a significant positive impact on organic agricultural land (Lindström et al., 2020).

3. Civil society initiatives

Several initiatives exist around the world. Some of these initiatives have been compiled:

- **Environmental Justice Atlas:** Around the world, environmental conflicts are mounting. The situation underscores the urgent need for justice in the face of ecological harm (Martinez-Alier et al., 2016; Scheidel et al., 2018). In this context, scholars and activists have developed the Environmental Justice Atlas (EJAtlas.org) that has reached 4000 entries by early 2024 and should grow further, enlarging its geographical and thematic coverage. This global database draws on both activist and academic knowledge to document conflicts across more than 100 fields. It captures the commodities at stake, the involved actors, impacts, forms of mobilization and outcomes. This comprehensive approach allows for analyses of comparative political ecology aimed at developing a general theory of ecological distribution conflicts. The project also explores the efficacy of grassroots protests versus institutional public policies.
- **Agroecology movements:** Agroecology has high potential to enable more sustainable food production and enhanced farmers' incomes compared to conventional and industrial approaches (D'Annolfo et al., 2017; van der Ploeg et al., 2019). Initiatives range from organic farming, ecological intensification, community supported agriculture, agricultural ecotourism.
- **Clean energy movements:** Civil society has organized around production and consumption of clean energy, in initiatives such as community energy cooperatives (i.e., local communities unite to establish cooperatives, collectively investing in, owning and operating renewable energy projects such as solar photovoltaic or wind power

generation), energy sharing platforms (i.e., through online platforms, individuals and businesses can share their capacity for renewable energy generation for others to purchase and use), or microgrids (or small-scale energy systems that include renewable energy generation, energy storage and local power networks. Microgrids can operate independently or connect to the main grid, providing reliable energy supply and energy autonomy for communities, industrial parks, islands and other areas (Palensky & Dietrich, 2011).

- **Clean transportation movements:** Civil society has organized around production and consumption of clean energy, in initiatives such as
 - Carpooling and Ride-Sharing Platforms: Through online platforms, individuals can share car rides, carpool, or provide ride-sharing services, reducing the number of vehicles and traffic congestion, while saving transportation costs.
 - Public Transit Optimization and Electrification: Optimizing public transportation networks to improve accessibility and coverage, gradually introducing electric buses to reduce tailpipe emissions and environmental pollution.
 - Sustainable Urban Logistics: Adopting eco-friendly delivery methods to reduce traffic congestion, pollution and energy consumption in urban goods movement.

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Annex 5.5. Strategy 4

Action 4.1: Strengthening biodiversity-related values in integrated governance across sectors

To bend the curve of biodiversity loss, the assignment and management of protected areas and the implementation of programmes for the protection of endangered species are not enough. Governing the direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, including land- and sea-use changes, pollution and direct exploitation of organisms (direct drivers, see strategy 2) as well as trends in production in technological development and innovation, consumption and trade, (see strategy 3) and global governance (indirect drivers; IPBES, 2019). A stronger importance of biodiversity in governance depends on positioning diverse values related to biodiversity in decision-making, in policy mixes that take into account the complex interdependencies of problems and to overcome gaps of capacities, resources and information (Kelemen et al., 2022). This is however impeded by inadequate policies and unfit institutions and existing power imbalances and inequalities.

“Integrative governance” refers to the “the relationship between sectors and policies and [approaches that] help to ensure policy coherence and effectiveness”(IPBES, 2019, chapter 6). The Convention on Biological Diversity and its Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework refers to “mainstreaming” (i.e., Target 14) to consider biodiversity values in all relevant policies, plans and monitoring processes (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022a). Aspects identified in the global assessment (Kelemen et al., 2022) were complemented with a systematic literature review on biodiversity mainstreaming and policy integration and conducted additional targeted searches and identified the following enabling options to strengthen integrative governance: joint planning and inclusive discourses, changing institutional constellations redirect political power, revising existing policies that negatively affect biodiversity, providing capacities for integrative governance and utilizing external shocks.

4. Joint planning and inclusive discourses

Joint planning among stakeholders representing sectoral and biodiversity interests enables a co-design of a future vision that bridges different interests, assigns clear roles and responsibilities and thereby enables policy integration (Zinngrebe et al., 2022). Key elements include the alignment of goals, the pooling of resources, the alignment of monitoring schemes and bringing together of data and knowledge and the designation of clear responsibilities. In addition, coalitions among stakeholders can induce leadership to push formal sectoral mandate and facilitate processes by including intermediaries or brokers (S. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen et al., 2018; Reber et al., 2023). Joint planning can be incentivized by a formal requirement to incorporate biodiversity in sectoral plans. The NBSAPs for instance were observed to be important for holding policy sectors accountable for biodiversity action (Cardona Santos et al., 2023).

It is also important to provide clear targets and a clear theory of change for the stakeholders or to develop these with them. In most cases, biodiversity targets are set in soft formulations in the sectors (Runhaar et al., 2024; Zolyomi et al., 2023) and even national biodiversity strategies are

often no exception (Pröbstl et al., 2023). In contrast, (Dik et al., 2023) report on targeted nature conservation measures for selected species in connection with the Dutch Agri-Environmental Schemes, which can lead to better evaluability of the measures and guidance for land users.

Secondly, discourse is an important variable. This can both support and prevent the integration of biodiversity. For example, (Xie et al., 2022) find that in Europe, biodiversity in the city has so far primarily played a subordinate role, especially since in the discourse on urban habitats, housing and urban infrastructure, these are presented as separate from nature. As a result, the linking of values and perceptions to the respective overall social considerations is central, which can be positively influenced in the direction of biodiversity by addressing alternative discourses (e.g., ecosystem services, nature-based solutions; Fajardo et al., 2021; Pröbstl et al., 2023; Shih & Mabon, 2018). The same applies to the increased inclusion of Indigenous and local knowledge, as well as plural perspectives as a whole in order to prevent a narrow view by primarily structurally powerful actors or sectors (Whitehorn et al., 2019).

5. Changing institutional constellations redirect political power

Institutional configuration can lead to policy misfits and political path-dependencies which can undermine the ability of actors to contribute to transformative change. At the same time, changing these configurations can mobilize agency, as political power can be regarded as the ability of actors to shape discourses and norms, influence decision-making and harness resources (Avelino, 2017, 2021). Institutional adjustments that define binding responsibilities can therefore play an important role as this can shift responsibility, resources and power between the individual sectors and actors (Sarkki et al., 2016). In the absence of binding responsibilities, collaborative policy-design and implementation procedures can lead to political buy-in and shared responsibilities in overcoming path-dependencies (Cardona Santos et al., 2023). In order to achieve this, processes will however have to address trade-off decisions and solutions that go beyond compensation or parallel, fragmented policy processes (Pröbstl et al., 2023; Simoncini et al., 2019).

For this transformative change, the perceived responsibility of individual involved sectors and their willingness to act on nature and adopted biodiversity targets is fundamental (Siddiqui, 2013). Central to achieve this are collaborative arrangements between sectors, that acknowledge a shared responsibility and that lead to long-term commitments to biodiversity extending beyond the relevant election periods and that thus solidify political ownership in the long term (Cardona Santos et al., 2023). Adjusting political mandates and the way budgets are distributed further adds to this process. (de Queiroz-Stein & Siegel, 2023) showcase for the bioeconomy concept that in addition to institutional adjustments, organizational capacities and political pressure through social movements, bottom-up processes and purchasing decisions are central factors for change. Involving these movements, Non-Governmental Organizations, think tanks or other diverse actors in shaping the implementation of cross-cutting for biodiversity and global sustainability can bring about innovative ideas and challenge established path-dependency dominated by technocratic administration and powerful private interests (de Queiroz-Stein & Siegel, 2023; Gauthier & Bogdan, 2021). This engagement can further improve the transparency of processes, adding to legitimacy and acceptance (Brown et al., 2019; Gauthier & Bogdan, 2021).

Well-organized groups lobby for the maintenance and expansion of private interests that are often at odds with sustainability. For instance, in the European Union efforts to build an effective green architecture for the common agriculture policy are largely shaped by institutional structures and power of interest groups (**box SM.5.3**).

Box SM.5.3. Greening the European Union agricultural policy – a gradual but incomplete reform.

The Common Agricultural Policy has been introduced by the European Union with the adoption of the treaty of Rome in 1957 aiming at productivity, fair living standards and market stability, before, starting gradually in 1992 adopting measures and targets to address biodiversity loss and other sustainability concerns (Lakner et al., 2021). New discourses around multi-functional land-use have emerged after 2005 and integrating biodiversity as an important factor of agricultural landscapes, are however repetitively overpowered by the traditional productivist narrative (Anania et al., 2015; Erjavec & Erjavec, 2020). This has been attributed to the strong influence of well-organized farmer lobby groups that shape discourses leading to policy structures (Alons & Zwaan, 2016).

Since the 90s, concrete measures to incentivize conservation as part of farming practices were developed. For instance, studies attribute significant potential of Agri-Environmental and Climate Measures to effectively lead to ecological outcomes; however their effectiveness is conditioned by their design and administration (Batary et al., 2015; Bertoni et al., 2020; Kelemen et al., 2022), Public consultation indicated that farmers and the broader public regard these agri-environmental schemes best suited for addressing environmental challenges (European Commission, 2017).

During the Common Agricultural Policy -reform process in 2003, the European Union has sought to use the win-win-potential of agri-environmental schemes to reduce the former production surplus of the 1990s and to justify societal critique against the Common Agricultural Policy-payments (Lakner et al., 2021). The decoupling and greening of Common Agricultural Policy -subsidies also helped to fulfil the requirements of the GATT-Marrakesh-agreement of 1994 by reducing production distortions and at the same time reduce harmful incentives to the environment, however with few effective policy changes regarding the environment (Guyomard et al., 2000). To date these “green” payments are used to justify governmental spendings in front of the European society, they still received only little attention in the policy mix of the Common Agricultural Policy (Daugbjerg & Swinbank, 2016).

Since 2013, the Greening of Common Agricultural Policy-subsidies became a target of its own within the Common Agricultural Policy and part of the direct payments have been coupled to “greening” obligation, which were however very soft and effectively met by farmers by registering existing landscape elements, crop rotation practices and other elements that had already been part of farming practices (Pe’er et al., 2017).

The new Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-27 introduced eco-schemes and flexibility to address biodiversity and climate targets as a condition for direct payments, however with considerable limitations in sustainability safeguards, such as the indication of pathways for reducing greenhouse gases and in the provision and requirement of area-based measure to meet the 10% conservation target set by the European Union Biodiversity Strategy (Cuadros-

Casanova et al., 2023). Overall, the 2021 Common Agricultural Policy reform does not sufficiently support transition to sustainable agricultural practices. For example, 80% of the European Union's CAP subsidies are allocated to emissions-intensive animal products, such as beef and dairy (Kortleve et al., 2024). Furthermore, the CAP lacks a focus on reducing pesticides, soil and water protection and the unsustainable food production through trade (Cuadros-Casanova et al., 2023). Science-informed proposals to improve Agri-Environmental and Climate Measures have been repeatedly watered down in negotiations in 2013 and 2021 within and between the Commission, the Parliament and the Council as EU policy decision-making bodies (Alonso et al., 2017). Instead of developing new payment formats with high administrative costs and weak ambition, the scholars advocate a more fundamental transformation by phasing out direct payments and replacing them with a targeted payment system that learns from existing experiences for a targeted, ambitious and simplified green architecture of payments for environmental services (Baldock & Bradley, 2023; Guyomard et al., 2023; A. Matthews, 2023; Pe'er et al., 2019).

The history of weak and ineffective reforms has been attributed to the observation that the policy design has been shaped by agricultural bodies in all three organs (Committee for Agriculture and Rural Development in the Parliament, Directorate-General for Agriculture in the Commission, and the Council of Agricultural Ministers), dominated by representatives from the farming sector with other e.g., environmental or social interest groups being underrepresented and outvoted (Brown et al., 2019; Knops et al., 2014; Nischwitz et al., 2019, 2019). Despite compelling evidence questioning the contribution of direct payments to either farmer wellbeing and sustainable land-use, the Common Agricultural Policy maintained its overall structure and is unlikely to change unless decision-making procedures are altered (Kortleve et al., 2024; Pe'er et al., 2019). Even with the structural challenges, the last gradual reforms of the Common Agricultural Policy 2013 and 2021 have led to an increasing representation of environmental or sustainability concerns (Röder et al., 2024). However, the limitations have been attributed to the dominance of certain interest groups in the institutional structures (Daugbjerg & Swinbank, 2016). This was further illustrated in 2024 because of significant farmers protests and increased lobby pressure, a regression in environmental regulation is observed within the Common Agricultural Policy (Lakner & Röder, 2024; Röder et al., 2024), this included the scrapping of the Sustainable Use Regulation that was part of the EU Green Deal and aimed to reduce significantly the risks from pesticide use.

For the terminology of the assessment, we observe that new nature sensitive views gradually emerge on changing targets in this European Union policy on agriculture and rural development, leading to the uptake of new environmental measures supporting conservation practices. Nevertheless, decision-making structures remain dominated by interest groups undermining the transformative potential towards a stronger reform of the Common Agricultural Policy.

Similarly, analysis of governance arrangements in agricultural landscapes in Peru, Uganda, Indonesia and Uganda have shown that a reconfiguration of existing actor constellations, finance flows and incentive systems can mobilize substantial support of sustainable practices and unleash potential for local innovation (Zinngrebe et al., 2020).

Another example is the institutional setting for impact assessments and planning procedures. Insights from Peru have shown that positioning an environmental agency in charge of accompanying assessment and approval procedures has significantly strengthened the regulatory role of Environmental Impact Assessments (Zinngrebe, 2018). In addition to approval roles of Environmental Impact Assessments, strengthening Strategic Environmental Assessments that accompany the planning and optimization of projects throughout the entirety of the project development are essential for successful environmental integration. To strengthen both forms of assessment, institutional support is critical which can be issued through stronger legal and procedural foundation, increase in capacity building and clearer guidelines, as well as active public participation throughout the processes (Kontić & Kontić, 2012; Zhu et al., 2015).

6. Revising existing policies that negatively affect biodiversity

Mitigating direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss requires the adjustment of public and private policies to secure that biodiversity is integrated in policies and plans (Runhaar et al., 2024). An important element is the phase-out of ‘harmful subsidies’ (e.g., agricultural subsidies promoting ongoing intensification) and other measures (see strategy 2) to target sectoral driving forces of biodiversity loss and to support the scaling up of successful conservation pilots. There are several structural factors that facilitate this revision process.

Frequently applied instruments for integrating biodiversity include payment for ecosystem services or certification initiatives (Zinngrebe et al., 2022). Going beyond win-wins of biodiversity policies such as certification or payment for ecosystem services requires changing institutions and laws and positioning biodiversity at the core of planning decisions (Huntley, 2014). Changing the “rules” institutions operate can link action arenas (such as biodiversity and other policy sectors) and change mandates and hence responsibility structures for governing agents (Ostrom, 2009). An increase of climate legislation has reflected and increased implementation activities of governments around the globe after 2000 and has led to new regulations holding governing actors and other accountable for climate action (or inaction) (Eskander et al., 2021). Similarly different options for a stronger biodiversity regulation would increase legal obligations for sectors to act (Henn et al., 2024).

Besides the allocation of resources and the legal mandate, practical solutions for sector specific regulations or standards can be developed in a close collaboration (Runhaar et al., 2024). Friedman et al. (2018) report that the global fishing industry has gradually adopted environmental standards through a continuous dialogue with environmental stakeholders and has also introduced corresponding policies in its own sector. There are now a variety of instruments that can support the integration of biodiversity into economic and political decision-making processes: cross-cutting instruments (e.g., environmental impact assessments); voluntary measures (e.g., standards); financial incentive systems (e.g., payment for ecosystem services) or communicative instruments (e.g., labels) (Runhaar et al., 2024).

In order to identify sector specific actions for biodiversity to be considered by policies, iterative evaluation and learning processes are needed and require adaptive institutional structures (Zinngrebe, 2018; Zinngrebe et al., 2022). Effective revision of policies requires diverse stakeholder involvement, sufficient resources and an underlying legal foundation (Pröbstl et al.,

2023). Sustainable evaluation and monitoring processes require long term planning, with formalised convergence of policymakers and other stakeholders for the revision of policies (see above) and representing multiple knowledge systems (including local and traditional knowledge) (Bisht et al., 2020; Dik et al., 2023; see action 4 below).

To ensure legitimacy of monitoring and subsequent revisions of BPI efforts and sectoral policies, indicators to be included in the monitoring should reflect problem perceptions and concerns of the actors involved (de Queiroz-Stein & Siegel, 2023). The involvement of stakeholders is important for learning and can be facilitated by means of inter-ministerial working groups, partnerships and citizen science (Zinngrebe, 2023).

7. Providing capacities for integrative governance

In particular, the provision of sufficient financial resources and the organization of the financial system is a key lever. Overall, the weak funding of biodiversity measures is documented for many sectors: (see (Sotirov & Storch, 2018) for forestry sector; (Cardona Santos et al., 2023) for NBSAPs). As a result, biodiversity measures often have to make use of external funding or budgets designed for other environmental measures (e.g., climate measures) and seek synergies with these. (Siddiqui, 2013) for instance reported on Bangladesh receiving international funding (e.g., the Green Climate Fund), which was partly also used for biodiversity conservation. From this case study, it is learned that funding itself is not sufficient for Business Process Improvement and subsequent biodiversity conservation, since (Siddiqui, 2013) described how a lack of skilled manpower, corruption, a volatile political system and a lack of data undermine Business Process Improvement efforts. Whereas a lack of financial resources is often mentioned, (Huntley, 2014) also reports that financial institutions are increasingly taking environmental risks into account in financial models and linking this to the overall social risk of poor ecosystem conditions. Further, in the context of the Dutch agri-environmental schemes, (Dik et al., 2023) highlight the importance of sufficient financial and human resources, as well as knowledge transfer and organizational structures for the operationalisation of biodiversity goals by individual farmer collectives. Increased monitoring and demonstrating the added value of biodiversity can also support the provision of financial resources (G. F. Smith & Wolfson, 2004).

8. Making use of external shocks to overcome path dependencies

Options for changing governance can arise in the event of external shock events. The Covid-19 pandemic was a striking example in recent years, which provided some windows of opportunity for more protection of biodiversity and nature. The covid-19 pandemic often led to increased visitation and valuation of green spaces, especially for urban dwellers (Berdejo-Espinola et al., 2021; Kleinschroth et al., 2024; Marconi et al., 2022; Venter et al., 2020) in various parts of the world, with differences where policies were stricter and Gross Domestic Product was lower (Kleinschroth et al., 2024). Bisht et al. (2020) see both negative and positive developments in his example from Covid-19 developments in India.

For example, a potential momentum created by a stronger perception of the value of nature in everyday life during the Covid-19 pandemic ended up in a reduction in agricultural land set aside

for nature conservation in the wake of the subsequent economic reactivation, the Ukraine crisis and potential European food shortages (Pröbstl et al., 2023).

Action 4.2: Engaging diverse actors in inclusive governance to create ownership and broaden legitimacy

1. Engage diverse actors in inclusive governance to create ownership and broaden legitimacy of decisions and actions

The creation of governance structures that represent a plurality of views and voices, as well as practices and knowledge systems are an entry point for strengthening ownership, legitimacy, accountability and equity (Apostolopoulou et al., 2022). Inclusion of all members of society in planning and implementing projects for biodiversity provides numerous opportunities for transformative change. It is thus important to ensure that inclusive governance (e.g., deliberative politics (Dryzek, 2002) is implemented that genuinely navigates diverse visions of transformation and biodiversity (Lövbrand et al., 2015). Strengthening inclusive procedures to broaden legitimacy of decisions and actions, through investing in stakeholder participation, inclusive and deliberate forms of governance and democracy and involving all layers of society through genuine public participation provides opportunities to pivot society in the direction of just transformation (N. Bennett et al., 2019; Huntjens, 2021; Paloniemi et al., 2015; Scoones et al., 2020; Wamsler & Riggers, 2018). As an entry point for inclusive forms of governance that strengthen ownership, accountability and equity (Apostolopoulou et al., 2022), it is crucial to enable a plurality of voices and knowledge systems and engage key stakeholders, such as the private sector, Indigenous Peoples and sub-national authorities always considering social differences along gender, class, age and race and to do so at different governance levels (Akindele et al., 2021; Chandra & Idrisova, 2011; Grumbine & Xu, 2021). For successful implementation it is critical to generate trust and social capital in actor networks (Polman & Slangen, 2008; Zinngrebe et al., 2020).

2. Effective and inclusive collaboration

For successful outcomes of collaborative processes it is critical that all actors (supported by facilitating agents) work on generating trust and social capital in actor networks (Polman & Slangen, 2008; Zinngrebe et al., 2020). Forming multi-stakeholder partnerships that include government, private sector, civil society and community representatives to collaborate on policy development and implementation are essential for realizing transformative change (Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2017; Dentoni et al., 2018, 2018; Eweje et al., 2020). Inclusive governance is considered effective when it leads to natural social contracts or eco-social contracts¹⁸, i.e., collective agreements (at multiple governance levels) among members of a society to cooperate with one another and abide by certain rules or norms targeted at sustainability, equity and justice, with the associated rights and duties of care for the environment and the well-being of others (including future generations and all life on this planet) (Huntjens, 2021; Huntjens et al., 2023).

¹⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

For instance, within the Convention on Biological Diversity process, inclusiveness requires the National focal points (e.g., Environmental Ministries) to include other sectors and stakeholder groups in the preparation of National Reports, as well as in developing and implementing the NBSAPs. This can be supported by community and citizen science in local contexts for monitoring and evaluating biodiversity action (Fritz et al., 2019; Jacobs et al., 2018; Pascual et al., 2017), as well as the evaluation of interventions according to social performance standard, anti-corruption measures and auditing down to the local level (Chan et al., 2017; Douglas, 2020; Pascual et al., 2014). Equally, in the development of National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs), an inclusive process is essential to increase commitment, ownership and awareness of biodiversity values among stakeholders (Cardona Santos et al., 2023; Prip, 2018).

3. Recognize and support the important role of civil society and grassroots actors in bringing about transformative change

Civil society initiatives including grassroots movements (Martinez-Alier et al., 2016), Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Chaplowe & Hejnowicz, 2021; Escobar, 2020; Jasanoff, 2005; Pascual et al., 2021), women collectives (Tran, 2021), urban dwellers (Navas et al., 2022), scientists and international Non-Governmental Organizations (Scheidel et al., 2020) among others have shown to be capable of often challenging power imbalances and inequalities in environmental governance and defend social and environmental rights more broadly. Doing so often puts the burden of transformative change on the most vulnerable (Blythe et al., 2018) and more inclusive governance processes can help alleviate that burden. When actors are not included in governance they may resort to other actions, such as street protest, public campaigns, local consultations, strikes, boycotts and litigation, to diverse disruptive actions such as occupations of public spaces and blockades and many more (Kivimaa et al., 2021; Scheidel et al., 2020).

Bottom-up initiatives can counter power imbalances, accelerating changes in broad values and changing the priorities of powerful actors (Apostolopoulou et al., 2022; Nagendra, 2018). Improved and inclusive common pool resource management (Huntjens et al., 2012; Ostrom, 2008); reductions in fossil fuels use (Thiri et al., 2022), restrictions on polluting activities (Walter & Wagner, 2021), the promotion of agroecology and peasant farming; participatory wildfire governance (Otero, 2022), or the protection of community forests against powerful illegal actors are just a few examples.

Recognizing the potential of bottom-up actions is essential for dismantling harmful practices and supporting new ways of thinking, doing and knowing (E. Bennett et al., 2016). Recent international efforts have been directed to enhance the protection of environmental defenders and could be further entrenched in global and national policies to protect environmental defenders from possible multiple burdens, violence and violations of their rights, which are more frequent in highly unequal societies (Butt et al., 2019; Le Billon & Lujala, 2020; Scheidel et al., 2023; Tran, 2023).

4. Broad stakeholder participation

Broad stakeholder participation generally provides a diverse and more nuanced set of measures needed to address complex issues, which also promotes a social system's capacity to learn (Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2017; Huntjens, 2021; Leventon et al., 2019; Sterling et al., 2017, 2022). However, social learning does not happen by itself and requires effort on the part of all those involved, adequate facilitation and reliable information on issues being discussed (Huntjens, 2021).

Inclusive governance processes can help alleviate the burden of transformative change that falls on the most vulnerable (Blythe et al., 2018). Recent international efforts could be further entrenched in global and national policies to protect environmental defenders from possible multiple burdens, violence and violations of their rights, which are more frequent in highly unequal societies (Butt et al., 2019; Le Billon & Lujala, 2020; Scheidel et al., 2023; Tran, 2023). Governmental efforts to develop corporate due diligence policies and trade agreements conditional upon upholding UNDRIP responsibilities, as well as civil society and Indigenous divestment campaigns targeting corporations involved in rights violations could be an entry point that impact of socio-environmental mobilizations.

5. Different mechanisms and approaches for inclusive biodiversity governance

To summarise action 2, inclusive biodiversity governance involves a variety of mechanisms and approaches designed to engage a broad range of stakeholders in decision-making processes on the protection and sustainable management of biodiversity to ensure that policies and actions reflect a wide range of perspectives and needs. By combining these mechanisms and approaches, inclusive biodiversity governance seeks to create a more equitable and effective framework for conserving biodiversity and ensuring the sustainable use of natural resources. In below table SM.5.9 several key mechanisms and approaches for inclusive biodiversity governance are listed, described and referenced.

Table SM.5.9. Mechanisms and approaches for inclusive biodiversity governance for different participatory settings.

Mechanism	Description	Key references
Public consultation	Engaging citizens through public forums, town hall meetings and online platforms to gather input on policy proposals.	Armitage et al., 2020; Brondízio & Le Tourneau, 2016; Díaz-Reviriego et al., 2019; Kusters et al., 2020; Paloniemi et al., 2015

Mechanism	Description	Key references
Deliberative democracy	Using methods such as citizens' assemblies and deliberative polls to involve a representative sample of the population in discussing and deciding on biodiversity and natural resources management issues.	Baber & Bartlett, 2015; Rask & Worthington, 2015; Stoll-Kleemann & O'Riordan, 2002
Community-based natural resource management (CBNRM)	Involves local communities in managing natural resources, ensuring that those who are directly affected by biodiversity policies have a say in their development and implementation.	Cox et al., 2010; Fabricius, 2004; Leach et al., 1999; Jones & Murphree, 2004
Co-management of natural resources	Shared governance arrangements between governments and local communities or Indigenous groups, facilitating collaborative decision-making processes.	Fischer et al., 2014; Natcher et al., 2005; T. C. Tran et al., 2020; Plummer & Fitzgibbon, 2004; Borrini et al., 2004
Biodiversity councils and committees	Establishing multi-stakeholder councils or committees at various levels (local, regional, national) to provide platforms for dialogue and coordination among different interest groups.	Chandra & Idrisova, 2011; Lee, 2005
Education and awareness campaigns	Raising public awareness about the importance of biodiversity and how individuals and communities can contribute to its conservation.	Navarro-perez & Tidball, 2012; Singh & Rahman, 2012; Verissimo et al., 2018

Mechanism	Description	Key references
Capacity building programmes	Providing training and resources to local communities, NGOs and government officials to enhance their ability to engage in biodiversity conservation and natural resource management.	Coffey et al., 2023; Sterling et al., 2022; Y. S. Rawat, 2017
Citizen Science Programmes & participatory monitoring	Involving citizens and community groups in monitoring biodiversity and the implementation and impact of related policies and programmes through data collection initiatives that contribute to scientific research and policymaking.	Couvet & Prevoet, 2015; Pocock et al., 2018; Palma et al., 2024
Transparent Reporting Mechanisms	Establishing systems for regular reporting on biodiversity status and trends, ensuring that information is accessible and understandable to all stakeholders.	Gupta & Mason, 2014; Gupta et al., 2020
Stakeholder Consultations	Conducting thorough consultations with all relevant stakeholders, including marginalized groups, to ensure that biodiversity policies reflect a diverse range of perspectives and needs.	Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2017; Leventon et al., 2019; Sterling et al., 2017, 2022
Multi-Stakeholder Partnerships	Forming partnerships that include government, private sector, civil society and community representatives to collaborate on policy development and implementation.	Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2012, 2023; Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2017; Dentoni et al., 2018; Eweje et al., 2020

Mechanism	Description	Key references
Gender-Responsive Approaches	Recognizing and addressing the different ways that biodiversity issues impact men and women, ensuring that policies promote gender equity.	Lambrou & Laub, 2007; Pierce Colfer et al., 2013; UN Women, 2018
Rights-Based Approach	Ensuring that governance frameworks respect and promote human rights, providing legal protections for participation and non-discrimination. The protection of environmental defenders from possible multiple burdens, violence and violations of their rights, which are more frequent in highly unequal societies	Campese et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2020; Morgera, 2019; Walters et al., 2019
Recognition of Indigenous Rights	Ensuring that the rights of Indigenous peoples to their lands and resources are recognized and respected, often leading to more effective and sustainable biodiversity conservation.	Reyes-García, Fernández-Llamazares, et al., 2022; Goolmeer et al., 2022
Inclusive Legislation	Crafting biodiversity laws and regulation that mandate the inclusion of diverse groups in governance processes, such as quotas for women or marginalized communities in political bodies.	Armitage et al., 2020; Suškevičs, 2012; Ison & Wallis, 2017
Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS)	Implementing mechanisms that ensure fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of genetic resources, often involving local and indigenous communities.	Tsioumani, 2018; Laird et al., 2020; Richerzhagen, 2011; Robinson, 2014; Siebenhuener et al., 2005

Mechanism	Description	Key references
Decentralisation	Devolving decision-making authority to local governments to ensure that policies are more responsive to local needs and conditions	Leventon et al., 2019; Pittman, 2019; Larson & Soto, 2008; Ring, 2008; Sullivan, 2019
E-Governance Platforms	Utilizing digital platforms to facilitate citizen engagement, provide services and enhance transparency in biodiversity governance processes.	Møller et al., 2019; Soni et al., 2017; Steen Møller & Stahl Olafsson, 2018; P. Rawat & Yusuf, 2020

Action 4.3. Securing collaboration and accountability through multi-lateral governance to address global interdependencies.

In an increasingly interconnected globalized economy, actions in one place can have (often hidden) effects in distant places. Transformative change therefore requires international collaboration through bilateral and multilateral action within and beyond formal negotiation and decision-making procedures. Bilateral and multilateral trade agreements have a large transformative potential by and can be utilised as a leverage point to strengthening environmental standards (Postnikov, 2018). By including elements that address environmental concerns such as deforestation, pollution and climate change, bilateral or multilateral trade agreements can encourage responsible production and consumption patterns. There are multiple examples of bilateral agreements that have increased environmental standards, in particular through European Union trade agreements (Postnikov, 2018).

At the same time, there is increasing institutional and organizational complexity and fragmentation in bilateral and multilateral agreements, for instance surrounding the international financing mechanism REDD+ (reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation in developing countries and related forest activities; Gupta et al., 2016; van Asselt, 2011; Young, 2019; Zawahri & Mitchell, 2011) as well as in international climate finance (Pickering et al., 2017). Many existing bilateral and multilateral agreements are fragmented leading to continued environmental degradation. Action 3 expands on key considerations in the redesigning agreements and the agreement making processes, including inclusive planning, monitoring and evaluation and adaptive learning required for governing in complexity of global value chains. Global value chains are interconnected and require shared responsibilities between producing and consuming countries which can be enhanced by polycentric network governance that connects actors across social spheres, sectors, places and scales. High consumption countries have a specific power and responsibility to act and ensure that the proposed interventions are fair and equitable in both producing and consuming countries.

1. Changing arrangements and procedures in current multilateral environmental agreements

In international and national assessments and reports such as in the U.S. National Nature Assessment, broader concepts such as "nature" can provide a more integrated perspective of biodiversity with other interrelated social-ecological components, such as climate, water, economy and society (Carroll et al., 2023). Although challenging, cross scalar governance integration in coordinating biodiversity assessments and policy (both horizontal and vertical) is seen as pivotal for enhancing implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity. This might include the use of standardised biodiversity variables to integrate global, national and subnational efforts, as well as a co-design of reviews and assessments among countries. Apart from the recognition that there is difficulty in integrating biodiversity policies into various sectors, the reviewed documents barely touched integration.

States have signed and ratified more than 3000 bilateral and multilateral environmental agreements (Mitchell et al., 2020) leading to a fragmented landscape of international environmental law and rising complexity in the agreement landscape. This can lead to actors favouring the regulatory context that suits them the most, which can work against effective environmental outcomes (Alter & Raustiala, 2018; Busch, 2007; Helfer, 2004; Raustiala & Victor, 2004). The resultant institutional, political and cognitive barriers created limits integration across agreements (Velázquez Gomar, 2016) and ultimately multilateralism becomes contested (Morse & Keohane, 2014).

The designs of bi- and multi-lateral agreements are byproducts of state interest, transaction costs and distribution of power (Kanie et al., 2014; Zawahri & Mitchell, 2011). Redesigning them to become more fit for addressing global commons and other global challenges therefore requires significant changes in these factors. State interests can be broadened by recognizing the principles of global commons and common heritage of humankind and the transnational character of the drivers of biodiversity loss (Stern, 2011; Vadrot et al., 2022). Transaction costs can be lowered by consolidating MEAs related to similar issues, including their secretariats (Biermann, 2002; Jinnah, 2014) and reporting frameworks (Urho et al., 2019) and institutionalized conflict resolution mechanisms (De Bruyne & Fischhendler, 2013). Power distribution can be addressed by e.g., changing decision-making rules such as moving from consensus to qualified majority voting (P. S. Chasek, 2011; Szell, 1996), redistributing resources and capacities (P. Chasek & Rajamani, 2003; Okereke, 2006; Albin & Druckman, 2017; Tolochko & Vadrot, 2021); new forms of political representation (Harden-Davies et al., 2020; Susskind et al., 2014, p. 201); and creating a better balance between science and policy (Susskind et al., 2014, p. 201). Redesigning agreement making around these factors (state interest, transaction cost and power distribution) will require developing transformative governance processes that pay attention to relationality, what values are being privileged over others and inclusive, intersectional engagement (Wamsler et al., 2020).

2. Inclusive representation in planning, monitoring, evaluation and review

Inclusiveness is a key unresolved challenge in many review and reporting mechanisms for multilateral environmental agreements (Carroll et al., 2023). Inclusiveness implies not only the

active participation of a diverse and representative portfolio of actors, stakeholders, organizations and sectors throughout the process, but also the in the global stocktake of the Paris Agreement. Such provisions are perhaps even more relevant explicit consideration of a plurality of valuation systems and the fostering of community and citizen science in local and regional contexts for monitoring and evaluating biodiversity and the actions taken for conservation (Pascual et al., 2017) valuing; (Jacobs et al., 2016) new; (Fritz et al., 2019) citizen). For many Multilateral Environmental Agreements, national reports are the main instrument for monitoring and reviewing the implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity including of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD. DEC.15/6). The Conference of the Parties is responsible for reviewing the implementation of the convention (Article 23) and for that purpose, the syntheses of national reports prepared by the Secretariat and Global Biodiversity Outlook are used. GBOs are based on a range of indicators, research studies and assessments (the IPBES Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services), as well as the national reports. As such, inclusiveness in the development of the national reports largely depends on each party's drafting process. Any MEA decision making body (COP) can strengthen inclusiveness in monitoring and review both by opening its own process for submissions by e.g., scientists, civil society, Indigenous Peoples and local communities and urge countries to do the same at the national level in its reporting guidelines. This would align with the principle of access to environmental information, decision-making and justice, which was established first in the Rio Declaration and since then reiterated in many UN conferences as well as two multilateral treaties – the Aarhus Convention and the Escazu Agreement (UN, 2018; UNECE, 1998). Civil society actors, international secretariats and a number of governments have actively supported the implementation of this principle in MEAs (Duyck, 2015). This has had real impact such as welcoming submissions from all non-state actors for biodiversity-related agreements that consider the valuable knowledge of Indigenous Peoples and local communities who live in close relationship with nature. Indeed, the Convention on Biological Diversity Secretariat supports the Indigenous Peoples and local communities publication the Local Biodiversity Outlooks, its first edition was welcomed by COP13 of the Convention on Biological Diversity who requested a second edition. Participatory processes around biosphere reserves have shown that governments and other actors increasingly recognize the abilities of biospheres for co-existence of humans and their different interests (Bouamrane & Dogné, 2019). Participatory implementation of biosphere reserves is targeted at engaging stakeholders and assure human wellbeing while contributing to biodiversity conservation (Bridgewater & Babin, 2017).

3. Informed procedures for adaptive learning

Transformation implies a journey towards a new state, a new paradigm, something which per definition means both the goal and journey are uncertain (Bouvier et al., 2014). For governance at all levels, including at the global level, this calls for institutions that enable continuous collaborative learning and channelling such learning into adjusted governance arrangements, indeed making governance adaptive (Berkes, 2017). This stands in contrast to global governance and international law being known for its resistance to (fast) change. Nonetheless, there are many efforts to learn in global environmental and biodiversity governance, but we do not know much about their impact (S. I. S. E. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen & Dahl, 2021) and the institutional frameworks to enable learning between international environmental institutions are weak (Oberthür, 2009). What is required are the design of institutional frameworks that can reform

themselves (Brousseau et al., 2012), which in turn needs processes of learning and reflexivity that go deeper because “we cannot expect to be able to continue thinking and behaving within the same frameworks and action patterns that are causing the very thing that we want to change.” (Bouvier et al., 2014).

The review of implementation processes in MEAs can serve compliance in several ways, for example by providing information about barriers for implementation due to lack of capacities or providing evidence for effective policies. Parties can then collectively decide on measures to provide resources, capacity building and encouraging learning from successful examples. The review can also serve accountability (discussed below). However, this requires that reports can be individually reviewed. In some cases, such as the Convention on Biological Diversity, there is no review of individual reports with the specific information about one Party’s situation. There are only synthesis reports and GBO summaries presenting biodiversity and/or policy trends based on the collection of national reports, which often is also not complete due to late submissions (ref, see above).

Furthermore assessments and reports should be periodically updated to reflect changing conditions, despite possible political obstacles (Carroll et al., 2023). Using standardised methods and approaches is key to facilitate the periodicity and enable comparability across spatial and temporal scales.

An appropriate knowledge system in place that ensures relevant information flows providing learning from a rapidly changing environment, from past experience and from feedback between earlier multilateral actions and the environment needs to be followed by collective deliberation and decision-making. In order to be transformative, the latter could entail what has been referred to as ‘meta-deliberation’ where actors are able to reflect on the structure of the governance system itself and if necessary take steps to change its structure (Dryzek & Stevenson, 2011) and in a context where participants have no “preconceived notions that limit the possibilities for change” (Bouvier et al., 2014). Setting up the institutional framework for such meta-deliberation could be done in individual MEAs or in cross-cutting contexts such as the United Nations Environmental Assembly.

4. Strengthening accountability

The ability to hold actors in power to account has become considered an essential part of good governance and when it concerns adhering to law closely related to the rule of law. There is a general expectation that accountability mechanisms lead to more action (implementation/compliance; Dubnick, 2014). The rule of law in turn has been repeatedly endorsed at all levels including the international level, including in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development” under SDG16 (United Nations General Assembly, 2015). In national contexts the accountability relationships – who is entitled to hold who to account – are often clearly formalised and of a principal-agent type (e.g., citizens vs. parliament, parliament vs. executive government) even if also here informal accountability dynamics come into play as well (civil society organizations and media vs. power wielders). In global governance it is more complex. Due to the principle of national sovereignty States as Parties to a Multilateral Environmental Agreement have equal status thus any accountability mechanisms, they establish

are based primarily on a horizontal accountability relationship from peer to peer. They could delegate substantive authority to a court or compliance committee that would involve more hierarchical accountability. The latter they seldom do particularly not in multilateral environmental agreements. Consensus decision-making slows down decision-making and has allowed resisting countries to block stronger follow up and review. A primary example is the Convention on Biological Diversity where there is no accountability mechanism for individual states' implementation and compliance. There is no discussion of individual country reports and only an invitation to join a voluntary peer review mechanism which so far has been used by only a handful of countries. The “enhanced multidimensional approach” to planning, monitoring, reporting and review of implementation only feeds into a global collective review based on national reports adopted by COP15 in 2022 (CBD/COP/DEC/15/6). This is many steps behind for example the Paris Agreement where individual biannual reports are subject to technical review and scrutiny by other states and there is an implementation and compliance committee (A. M. Ulloa et al., 2018).

States can choose to strengthen the accountability mechanisms in biodiversity related MEAs. (Koh et al., 2022) for example suggest that compliance strategies like those featuring in human rights review mechanisms could be incorporated in the Convention on Biological Diversity, such as mutual learning (where states review each other's records and engage in a collective dialogue) or engaging with civil society (as civil society organizations can provide specific, timely and solution-oriented input to governments).

Under the current institutional arrangements in the Convention on Biological Diversity there are still several actions that could strengthen state accountability for made commitments. One is to encourage as many Parties as possible to voluntarily engage in the peer review (A. Ulloa, 2017) and to continuously evaluate and improve the process and impact of such review, drawing on experiences from other international peer reviews, see for example (Lehtonen, 2020). A diverse set of non-state actors including scientists and civil society organizations can take a more active role in informal account holding both at domestic and international levels – fostering transformative potential through constructive criticism (Ulloa, 2023; Ulloa et al., 2018). This can entail carrying out independent reviews involving, for instance, expert advisory boards and independent scientific and civil society organizations. Countries like Canada, Australia and Ireland have begun to broaden their accountability (for international biodiversity commitments) scope to include independent sectors (Carroll et al., 2023). At the global level non-state actors could establish a shadow evaluation process or council including holders of Indigenous and local knowledge, a consortium of scientists and civil society organizations (S. I. S. E. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen & Dahl, 2021). The High-Level Advisory Board on Effective Multilateralism has highlighted the need to strengthen public accountability for global environmental commitments across multilateral environmental agreements and suggested a UNEP-supported platform containing publicly available information, capacity-building support for low and middle-income countries, information-sharing around best practices and an annual reporting requirement to the UNGA for all agreements. Such a platform, they Advisory Board argues, would enable States to be publicly accountable and support States in their efforts “to reach the core goals of net-zero carbon emissions, biodiversity protection and restoration and a pollution-free planet.”(High-Level Advisory Board, 2024).

Box SM.5.4. Example of the UN BBNJ as unique opportunity to save the world’s marine biodiversity

An international opportunity to consider the lessons learned outlined above is the 2023 agreement on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of areas Beyond National Jurisdiction under the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea. This treaty applies to about two-thirds of the ocean and includes a provision to conserve biodiversity by using legal tools to design, implement and manage Marine Protected Areas. However, while the main drivers of marine biodiversity erosion are fishing and sea use change (IPBES, 2019a), the new Treaty cannot undermine existing instruments, frameworks and bodies. Fishing remains within the scope of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations of the UN Food and Agriculture Organization and seabed mining with the UN International Seabed Authority. The power to ensure that the High Seas Treaty realizes its full potential and becomes a tool of coherence rests with states who should seek to have integrated decisions and mainstream biodiversity across governing bodies (Claudet et al., 2020).

5. Interdependencies of distant production and consumption systems

Economic and societal processes link biodiversity threats and ecological degradation to economic benefits on other scales and in other places (Liu & Liu, 2009). Many direct drivers of biodiversity loss, such as land-use change or resource exploitation, are increasingly driven by international markets, trade flows and corporations (IPBES, 2019a; Jung et al., 2019). The resulting “telecoupled” agricultural systems connect social-ecological dynamics in production and consumption systems with a diverse set of connecting trade flows and feedback loops (Garrett et al., 2019; Liu & Liu, 2009; **figure SM.5.09**). For instance, Amazonian deforestation is not only linked to the European Union through international value chains (Pendrill et al., 2019), but also through bilateral agreements (Viola & Basso, 2014), discourses (Selbmann & Ide, 2015) and other linkages (**figure SM.5.10**).

Figure SM.5.9. Distant social-ecological systems can be telecoupled by flows and feedback loops.

6. Shared responsibilities between producing and consuming systems

In producing systems, existing regulatory systems, finance mechanisms and trade demands prioritize non-sustainable agricultural practices (Zinngrebe et al., 2020, 2021). The resulting regulatory challenges include uncertain land ownership, weak monitoring and secondary dynamics such as migration and encroachment that are central requirements for holding actors accountable and enforcing laws (Gaveau et al., 2017). Strong power dynamics, guided by extractivist and rent-seeking interests linked to production of e.g., oil, mining or illegal drug economies undermine the ability of a sustainable governance in producing systems (Bebbington, 2015). Considering globalizing markets and market forces, there are limitations of unilateral solutions due to limited state power in producing systems and legitimacy conflicts with global economic rules advocating liberalised markets (Lenschow et al., 2016). Instead, they require case-specific bilateral or multilateral solutions that assure transparency and complementary institutional settings (ibid). Instead of relying only on the producing state as “protector” of the environment, the consuming system has a specific role which includes regulations or voluntary measure to assure sustainable consumption in consuming system, which also includes the facilitation of networks of non-state actors and private companies to develop effective solutions (ibid). Products with multiple uses, such as palm oil, sugar, soy, or corn, but also metals, result in complex global value chains comprising different actor groups in many countries, who jointly govern standards and sustainability (Oberlack et al., 2018).

7. Solutions depend on polycentric network governance

Polycentric governance networks connect actors such as governments, investors, consumers, social movements and companies in both producing and consuming systems to jointly produce outcomes related to land-use and resource use (Oberlack et al., 2018; Ponte, 2019). Actors differ in their role and the way they execute power in network arrangements and can have an indirect

influence; for instance workers unions or civil society initiatives can force a government to change regulations or standards in one place that will then influence resource use in another (Ponte, 2019). This means that social processes - such as those based on social movements, civil society initiatives or the actions of governments or private actors - can establish values and standards for value chains that then will have an effect on cultural, ecological and socioeconomic outcomes (Eakin et al., 2017). These effects can be positive or negative and differentially affect different actor groups.

Therefore, solutions for integrated value chains need to consider different actor groups and power asymmetries. For instance, powerful actors such as traders can dominate value chains and potential solutions will require disclosing their providers and sources in order to trace potential effects (Grabs & Carodenuto, 2021). Likewise, different responsibilities of investors and financing agents need to be considered for effective governance of transnational value chains (Lehmann, 2016).

Acknowledging colonial power-inequalities, policies in accordance with the principles of transformative change will have to be mindful of secondary effects in other places and be responsive so that new standards do not have negative trade-offs or spill-over effects in distant systems (Kattan et al., 2006). These trade-offs between values and eventual outcomes can also appear across scales, raising questions of justice and legitimacy of regulation and other influences (Newig & Moss, 2017). The embedded nature of Social-Ecological Systems implies that powerful actor groups can control institutional interventions, project selection and knowledge flows into local systems (Yates, 2012), reflecting power disparities and inequalities. Hence, regulatory agents cannot design effective solutions independently and will depend on complementary regulatory networks that spread beyond their own direct area of influence. Being aware of these interdependencies and evaluating and learning in adaptive governance appears to be the most useful way of coping with this complexity and improving the effectiveness of solutions (Cosens et al., 2021).

8. Specific power and responsibility of countries with high consumption

Large consuming economies in high income countries and in transition economies have a strong potential to establish sustainability regulations and standards that are likely to diffuse along value chains. They therefore have a stronger responsibility for taking into account potential secondary effects in producing systems – particularly in low and least developed countries (Zinngrebe et al., 2024). The mismatches between political sustainability targets and existing legal frameworks in large consuming economies like the European Union result in the “export” of environmental damage, particularly to tropical forests (Fuchs et al., 2020). Experiences also show that large scale, more powerful actors in these producing countries blame smallholders or unregulated actors for not meeting no-deforestation targets (Gaveau et al., 2017).

Experiences with mining for instance have shown that infrastructures, construction and the production of electronics and machinery, specifically in the economically strongest final markets, such as China, India, USA, Japan and the US, drive consumption of mining products in distant countries and thus the related biodiversity impacts. These actors therefore have a strong influence and responsibility in mitigating effects on the production system, such as mining sites

(Cabernard & Pfister, 2022). Soy production and its related effects on deforestation and land-use change in South America have been connected to global support by the World Bank and national policies of consuming markets, such as preferential trade access and coupled support for animal production (Zinngrebe et al., 2024). These powerful actors also have a specific role. The European Union for instance has shown a decisive leadership role in global environmental governance through agenda setting, facilitation, finance, international agreements and developing cooperation (Schreurs, 2018; Schreurs & Economy, 1997). Just as in trade regulation, establishing additional standards in final markets can pose barriers for poorer smallholders from the global South, e.g., when high transaction costs of compliance reporting excludes them (T. J. Matthews, 2014). While some countries (specifically countries in economic transition) might benefit from reducing trade barriers, poor or least developed countries might lose because of less advantages and rents from a preferential trade access into final markets (Li et al., 2016). Assuring workers' rights and providing for local smallholders needs beyond market demands is an important element to secure support for e.g., deforestation free production (Kooijman et al., 2017). These initiatives require partnerships and collaborative settings connecting both private and governmental actors, paying attention to the needs of vulnerable people who may be affected and stretching between both consuming and producing systems. Hence, social issues and global inequality are central elements for the transformative governance of transnational or global production and consumption patterns related to biodiversity loss.

9. Effective solutions require policy coherence complementary solutions

When addressing biodiversity effects and other sustainability issues linked to consumption, different governance systems are interdependent. (Ulibarri et al., 2020) emphasize that in telecoupled systems, the governance responding to a telecoupled problem is not necessarily the same system as the one inducing or the one coordinating it. The example of anti-drug policies in Latin America have shown that a general targeted support for farmers to change from a more area efficient cocaine production to other less area efficient agricultural production has led to production booms, deforestation and hence threats to biodiversity (Dávalos et al., 2016). These policies are incoherent with anti-deforestation governance and the governance of the commodity chains farmers might produce for (Fukumi, 2016). Hence, solutions will have to consider different policies and governance processes in order to transform unsustainable trajectories. In order to manage these interdependencies and assure coherence for policies, a systematic monitoring and assessment is indispensable (Carbone & Keijzer, 2016). Linking monitoring and regulation processes in clear administrative hierarchies can help for individual actors to organize in complex governance systems and reduce transaction costs in order to identify new needs for collaborative arrangements and potential (Ramanujam et al., 2012).

Efforts of multilateral approaches to establish environmental safeguards in the provisions of the World Trade Organization have been discussed in the “Doha round”, but not lead to tangible results (IPBES 2019). Bilateral trade-agreements have shown potential to push environmental issues onto policy agendas, however with little effective protection for biodiversity resulting from it. For instance, the North American Trade Agreement has been connected with positive developments around urban air quality, potable water access, and access to sanitation, but have

also driven agricultural intensification, land degradation¹⁹ and water issues (Gladstone et al., 2021) The European Union MERCOSUR agreement has explicitly addressed issues of deforestation and biodiversity loss but has, at the same time, led to agricultural intensification and land-use changes (Kehoe et al., 2020). Studies recommend a strong and explicit consideration of biodiversity in trade agreements, including the specification of responsibilities across governments and large agribusiness, a transparent monitoring of land-use impacts, as well as stronger legal responses and enforcement (Cesar de Oliveira et al., 2024; Green et al., 2019; Kehoe et al., 2020).

Action 4.4: Strengthen learning processes with responsive structures and diverse knowledge systems

1. Promote adaptive learning by creating structures that respond to iterative processes of planning, monitoring, reporting and review

Within the governance of biodiversity conservation, there are multi-level tensions and contradictions between the open-endedness of complex social-ecological systems and societal ambitions to manage and control these systems towards stated objectives (Frantzeskaki et al., 2012). In response, adaptive management and planning requires social learning strategies that can be adjusted as circumstances change, offering spaces for experimentation, evaluation and multi-stakeholder deliberation (Ahern et al., 2006; Frantzeskaki et al., 2012; Huntjens et al., 2012). Social learning is a transdisciplinary process that accepts the inherent uncertainties and risks associated with biodiversity conservation and management interventions, focussing on the quality of the decision-making processes rather than fixed goals (Bagheri & Hjorth, 2007; Wamsler et al., 2020). Adaptive and responsive governance approaches that incorporate participatory exercises of “envisioning, negotiating, experimenting and learning” are therefore required to deliberately orient towards more sustainable system states, recognizing that sustainability is a moving target - inherently ambiguous and contested, requiring open-ended innovation processes (Frantzeskaki et al., 2012). In practice, adaptive management (Norton et al., 2006) requires diverse streams of knowledge, information and data to inform the timely adjustment of sustainable development pathways at different levels of organization (e.g., (Davidson-Hunt & Berkes, 2003; Folke et al., 2005; Rodriguez et al., 2018)). For example, while far from perfect (Reyes-García, Tofighi-Niaki, et al., 2022; Turreira-García et al., 2018) participatory monitoring through citizen science has been shown to produce valuable scientific data to evaluate progress, while also raising public awareness of the practical relevance of research outcomes (Bammer, 2017; Bergmann & Jahn, 2017; C. Hummel et al., 2017), leading to the emergence of structured, reflexive and problem-oriented social learning processes (Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Raymond et al., 2010; Rodriguez et al., 2018). Further, collaborative efforts to communicate knowledge across ontological systems has been shown to change power dynamics and enhance reflexivity in biodiversity governance (Badry et al., 2023; Badry & Hickey, 2022).

The logic of iterative processes of planning, acting, monitoring, evaluating/reviewing and adjusting has been taken up by various governance processes including Convention on

¹⁹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Biological Diversity, i.e., NBSAPs, the development, implementation and monitoring of biodiversity projects, compiling national reports and global reviews of implementation. Adopting adaptive management strategies in the assessment of biodiversity projects requires participating actors to feel responsible and willing to learn from failures. Efforts to assemble new actor constellations through inclusive and creative learning processes have been shown to facilitate the reframing of problem perceptions to overcome institutional lock-ins (Battilana et al., 2009; Hoogstraaten et al., 2020).

2. Monitoring and Evaluation to learn lessons from experimentation

A core component of adaptive management and planning is receiving timely feedback on the progress, success and failures of interventions through transparent, iterative and inclusive monitoring and evaluation processes. To guide targeted action, monitoring and evaluation must go beyond the final impact of interventions on biodiversity to also assess strengths and shortcomings in decision-making processes. Transparency and inclusive review processes are necessary so that all stakeholder and rightsholder groups can participate, respond to findings and learn from each other. (Pisupati & Prip, 2015) found that a second generation of NBSAPs put a higher emphasis on mainstreaming and were better prepared regarding monitoring and reporting. However, iterative evaluation processes are no guarantee for adaptive learning. For example, (Lakner et al., 2020) found that the repeated evaluation cycles of the European Common Agricultural Policy iteratively lead to the same shortfalls in policy design. Also, adaptive learning can be supported by collaborative arrangements and leadership encouraging cross-sectoral and cross-level learning (Zinngrebe et al., 2022). To this end, an increasingly popular innovation strategy has been the development of Living Labs (Almirall et al., 2012; Hossain et al., 2019), designed to enable collaborative learning among diverse policy actors in a ‘real-life’ environment where end-user needs are central (Almirall et al., 2012; Hossain et al., 2019; Van Geenhuizen, 2018). For Living Labs to facilitate collaborative learning among diverse interest groups and organizations with different policy aims and agendas, boundary-spanning activities are required to create common language, build trust, identify interdependencies and ensure joint commitment, with a major focus on monitoring and evaluation (Van Geenhuizen, 2018). Boundary-spanning activities aim to create a more comprehensive and inclusive knowledge exchange process between local and traditional knowledge, scientific knowledge and bureaucratic knowledge by facilitating dialogue, learning and agreement actors with different interests, values and beliefs. As a result, they become a valuable focal point of consensus and contestations over knowledge and the potential political and societal implications of that knowledge (Stern, 2011; Vadrot et al., 2022).

3. Strengthening positive coordination to achieve collaborative arrangements

Strengthening positive coordination between different administrative and political units is a key component to foster support for adaptive governance in non-environmental sectors. Achieving acceptance for change and being able to respond appropriately to evaluations requires the willingness of actors concerned to adapt objectives, implement new measures and mobilize additional resources. Positive coordination, i.e., early and comprehensive involvement of stakeholders in decision-making processes, can be an important lever here as it strengthens not

only the willingness to participate in the development of objectives, but also the will to adapt positions and implementation. (Cardona Santos et al., 2023; Pröbstl et al., 2023). Beyond simply bringing people into a room and ticking a box and effective process depends on the active involvement of people in the co-design of the elements. Positive coordination can be supported by institutional adjustments (e.g., merging ministries and departments) to improve institutional interplay (Schröder et al., 2020). However, a spatial or thematic merging of units (e.g., environmental and non-environmental ministries) must not obscure the fact that previously existing lines of conflict between individual persons and units are not automatically eliminated as a result (Peters et al., 2015). Rather, the quality of the corresponding coordination formats and framework conditions for the individual actors must continue to be taken into consideration, even in the case of spatial consolidation (Peters et al., 2015)

Less hierarchical integration sometimes has the advantage that structures and procedures can be adapted more flexibly due to reduced threats to autonomy and reduced potential for vertical and horizontal conflicts during integration (Nunan et al., 2012). This provides the opportunity to provide administrative units with more freedom to embody a networked system based on exchange, reciprocity and inter-personal relationships, which finds more scope for cooperation with cross-sectoral organizational units. (Nunan et al., 2012).

In contrast, strong accountability is also an important factor in the system's response to potential feedback. For example, Nunan et al. (2012) emphasize that the success of individual working groups depends on which department or actor leads them. However, environmental ministries are often not sufficiently strongly positioned in the administrative context (Nunan et al., 2012). However, Sarkki et al. (2016) emphasize that even soft accountability processes (e.g., non-binding evaluations) can encourage individuals and departments to reflect their procedures and enable political learning.

4. Support from knowledge brokers and policy entrepreneurs

Policy entrepreneurship involves a person, or a small group of people, who cooperate with others to move a particular issue up the agenda to a position of enactment (Kingdon, 1984). These policy actors can attempt to affect public policy at, or across, local, regional, national and transnational levels (Frisch Aviram et al., 2020). Successful policy entrepreneurship heavily depends on nuanced networking and team building strategies to engage diverse (often conflicting) actors and navigate complexity using different dimensions of trust, persuasive argumentation and social acuity when engaging in policy conversations to understand other points of view (Frisch Aviram et al., 2020). Policy entrepreneurs and knowledge brokers can support the change of institutional habits and initiate cross-sectoral learning processes by transferring ideas within and across sectoral units, different administrative cultures and languages (Suarez et al., 2023). In this way, these actors support the reflection and adaptation of established policies, as well as inter-departmental networks (Mintrom & Norman, 2009). This interaction can take place through institutionalized formats (e.g., inter-ministerial working groups) or unofficial channels (e.g., personal contacts). These actors can be located both at the positions of experts and key political positions (Cejudo & Trein, 2023) as well as at lower administrative levels and in the form of lower-level employees (Peters et al., 2015). Especially in

the absence of a strong political mandate, the ambitions of these actors correspond with their individual resources, internal power relations and situational opportunities.

5. Transform science to support transformative change

Given the insufficient role science has played to date in revealing, questioning and transforming existing power relations that perpetuate widespread environmental degradation and social injustices, it is crucial to explore how science can play a more transformative role. Social science and humanities research in particular offer a useful analytical lens with which to understand the root dynamics that reinforce the status quo, including the many explicit and implicit forms of power that narrow public imagination and debate over alternatives (Castree, 2015; Stoddard et al., 2021). As a result, there have been calls to open up biodiversity and climate change science to more critical social science and humanities perspectives and develop the language and literacy needed to bridge this gap (Deutsch et al., 2023; Hulme, 2011; Tadaki et al., 2015). An openness to genuine pluralism and contestation is now recognized as critical to create conditions for meaningful inclusion (Pascual et al., 2021; Turnhout et al., 2021). This means challenging traditional notions of expertise, towards more reflexive, critical and constructive roles (Lidskog et al., 2022), as well as giving space to explore diverse knowledge systems and frictions and power differentials among them (Ludwig & El-Hani, 2020; Nicole & Meehan, 2015; Tengö et al., 2014). Approaches that help understand and navigate tensions in more reflexive ways is crucial for fostering transformative pathways in ways that go beyond initial goals, towards collective emergent goals that are the product of fundamental shifts in perspectives, relations and power (Chambers et al., 2022; Soininen et al., 2022). Bridging knowledge systems means directing scientific practices toward the societal arenas in which sustainability problems are being tackled (Cornell et al., 2013).

Yet many challenges remain in furthering the potential for science to contribute to transformative change. Beyond attention to pluralism and power, it is crucial to explore how to decentre western ways of knowing, connect the dominant emphasis on knowledge to equal focus on action and find ways to push the boundaries of collective imagination (M. Daly, 2021). For example, a new research paradigm of open team science interlinks open science and community-based participatory research (Kondo, 2021), which can promote adaptive learning and action. This also means weaving knowledge production into social movements and processes of change, thereby engaging in the deeper question of ‘how’ transformation occurs, linked to values, emotions and relationships (Bentz et al., 2022).

For example, sustainability research is seen as most effective when ‘co-produced’ by academics and non-academics in order to address the complex nature of sustainability challenges (Norström et al., 2020). A “knowledge democracy” highlights the relationship between science and the rest of society. The two sides of this coin are 1) the scientization of politics and the 2) politicization of science. Scientization of politics refers to governance as being transformed by the mass creation and availability of knowledge. The politicization of science denotes democratic ideals in the production and use of knowledge (Bednarek et al., 2018; Cornell et al., 2013). Finally, there is a need to go beyond navigating perspectives of existing problems towards better navigate divergent hopes and dreams for the future (Levitas, 2013; Olufemi, 2021). This necessitates

attention to both critical analysis and exploring alternatives, while stitching together action from local to global scales (Massarella et al., 2021).

Supporting material for Table SM.5.1

National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) are central to the Convention on Biological Diversity implementation, translating the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework into actionable steps at the national level and ensuring ongoing progress evaluation (COP15-decision 4,6). This way, NBSAPs are not just a policy instrument but an ongoing process that can foster learning and strengthen implementation. By adhering to the conceptual framework, a well-designed NBSAP can indicate how to transform views, practices and structures.

1. Action 4.1 – Strengthening biodiversity related values and interest groups in integrated governance.

National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans are pivotal in reinforcing biodiversity-related values and promoting diverse stakeholder interests within integrated decision-making frameworks, breaking up silos and addressing power imbalances (action 1). This requires co-designing and adopting NBSAPs, ensuring broad representation from all relevant sectors and civil society, including Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Cardona Santos et al., 2023), whose knowledge is key, particularly for policy integration at the local level (Ogawa et al., 2021). Such an inclusive approach allows integrating diverse perspectives and knowledge systems into biodiversity governance (Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021; Wittmer et al., 2021) and can allow to shift power relations, which is crucial for transformative change (Bush et al., 2022). Increasing public awareness of NBSAPs is essential for successful implementation (Akindele et al., 2021). Additionally, quantifying the financial costs and benefits of action versus no-action scenarios can improve the base for political decisions and mobilize support and capacity for implementation (Meyerhoff et al., 2012; Wuestemann et al., 2014).

National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans foster collaborative actions to address global environmental concerns, if they are both relevant and visible across levels and sectors, facilitated by effective communication strategies (Cardona Santos et al., 2023) and cross-referencing to related agendas (Pe'er et al., 2019; Zinngrebe, 2018). NBSAPs seek to guide sector policies, like environmental impact assessments and agricultural policies and address all policies impacting biodiversity (Zinngrebe, 2023). To be transformative, NBSAPs would address all policies that regulate activities with an impact on biodiversity and indicate what harmful subsidies and regulations to phase out and support innovative solutions (Alblas & van Zeven, 2023; S. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen et al., 2017). Linking all sector-specific biodiversity targets to the respective NBSAP and ensuring that existing policies support biodiversity goals is necessary for coherent implementation (Pe'er et al., 2019; Whitehorn et al., 2019; Zinngrebe, 2018). Furthermore, conditioning governmental support and funding on NBSAP compliance incentivizes adherence to biodiversity goals and ensures that financial resources are effectively utilized to support conservation efforts and sustainable development (Prip et al., 2010; Sarkki et al., 2016).

2. Action 4.2 – Engage diverse actors in inclusive governance to create ownership.

Reflecting societal diversity in National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (action 2) and linking them to the different social and economic realities of the groups they target (Cardona Santos et al., 2023; Pisupati & Prip, 2015) is key to ensure inclusive and thus transformative governance (Bulkeley et al., 2020). For example, the added value of biodiversity can be communicated to farmers via bridging concepts such as ecosystem services in a NBSAP process (Pröbstl et al., 2023). Inclusivity can bring in new perspectives for innovative solutions and increase ownership among stakeholders (Prip, & Pisupati, 2018). Therefore, it extends beyond simply exchanging information to encompass designing implementation actions, addressing trade-offs and negotiating potential solutions (Apte, 2007; Chandra & Idrisova, 2011). Engaging a variety of actors is crucial not only during the planning phase, but also for implementing, monitoring, reporting and reviewing goals and implementation measures (Göpfert et al., 2019; Sotirov & Storch, 2018). Involving multiple sectors can foster trust and credibility, as it demonstrates a commitment to accountability (Whitehorn et al., 2019).

National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans can further enhance inclusive governance through the establishment of intersectoral committees and coordination structures to facilitate collaborative decision-making, ensuring that all relevant sectors are actively involved and committed to biodiversity goals (Sarkki et al., 2016). Regularly convening national fora and thematic events, including those focused on Indigenous Peoples and local communities can mobilize key multipliers and stakeholders and serve as platforms for knowledge exchange, capacity building and the promotion of inclusive participation in biodiversity governance (Baldauf, 2020; Crowley et al., 2020). Establishing mediation processes to address and resolve intersectoral competition for funds and resources is also key to facilitate dialogue and negotiation to help overcome turf battles and promote cooperative efforts towards shared biodiversity objectives (Sarvasova et al., 2013; Jiren et al., 2021).

3. Action 4.3 – Global interdependencies require coordinated multi-lateral governance

Effectively addressing global interdependencies requires coordinated multi-lateral governance (see subsection on action 3 above). The integration of National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans with other sector strategies and reports from various multilateral environmental agreements - such as national strategies for sustainable development - facilitates a stronger integration of biodiversity, a stronger perceived responsibility across sectors, levels and non-political actors and cross-institutional collaboration for developing internationally and nationally coherent solutions (Rogalla Von Bieberstein et al., 2019; Velázquez Gomar, 2016). Promoting joint reporting to international processes across sectors through MEA integration can encourage leadership to adjust sectoral policies in alignment with biodiversity targets, which is key to fostering a unified effort towards global conservation (Sarkki et al., 2015).

Utilizing the Convention on Biological Diversity voluntary peer review as a tool to assess NBSAPs quality and implementation can support inter-country learning and continuous improvement, particularly within the same regions (Koh et al., 2022; A. Ulloa, 2017).

Additionally, addressing external effects on biodiversity within domestic NBSAPs entails regulating consumption impacting deforestation or other drivers of biodiversity loss elsewhere as it will mitigate global repercussions of local actions (Henders et al., 2018). Despite the articulated need for integrated solutions, related topics such as biodiversity, poverty and health remain as fragmented policy fields (Downs et al., 2017; Romanelli et al., 2014; Roe et al., 2013). Fragmented global agendas however have been found to be an obstacle for integrated national agendas as they reproduce international policy sectors (Zinngrebe, 2023). Integrated solutions on the international level with clear mainstreaming agendas are also a central lever for directing development funding (Brörken et al., 2022). Successful mainstreaming of the international level can lead to larger investments, capacities and stronger partnerships for synergistic implementation (Friedman et al., 2018).

4. Action 4.4 – Strengthening learning through accountable, informed and adaptive governance based diverse knowledge systems

National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans can strengthen learning through accountable, informed and adaptive governance based on diverse knowledge systems. This requires establishing robust information disclosure and provision practices for governments, businesses and other actors, alongside enhancing science-policy interactions (Redford et al., 2015). Transdisciplinary science is necessary for identifying policies, arguing their impacts and monitoring their phase out (Chandra & Idrisova, 2011; Onial et al., 2018). Enhanced cross-sectoral cooperation and science communication can enable NBSAPs to steer sectoral policy change (Rogalla Von Bieberstein et al., 2019).

Implementing a legal mandate that assigns clear responsibilities beyond the environmental sector (Sarkki et al., 2015; Zinngrebe, 2018) and combines hard and soft law will ensure accountability and adaptability. This approach will foster a comprehensive understanding of biodiversity challenges and solutions, enabling continuous learning and improvement of the effectiveness of integrated governance solutions (Roe et al., 2013). Though it may face challenges from non-environmental ministries due to differing core topics and clientele (Pröbstl et al., 2023) processes could address those responsible for sectoral impacts on biodiversity and indicate accountability for harmful activities (A. M. Ulloa et al., 2018)

Establishing specific, time-bound, actionable, realistic and measurable targets, coherent across policy levels (e.g., in combination with additional sub-national biodiversity strategies and action plans), can effectively engage stakeholders (Cardona Santos et al., 2023). Consistent and comparable indicators along with sufficient biodiversity data are key to mainstreaming biodiversity (Brörken et al., 2022), as well as using Environmental Impact Assessments as a biodiversity mainstreaming tool (Hugé et al., 2020).

Enhancing learning processes with responsive structures and diverse knowledge systems requires consistent legal frameworks across sectors and adaptive institutional learning arrangements (e.g., intersectoral committees; Zinngrebe, 2018). NBSAPs and related policies and financial flows can be co-evaluated with key stakeholders across sectors to foster accountability (Koh et al., 2022). Continuous evaluation and public visibility position NBSAPs as vehicles for societal learning. Stakeholders can align their activities, define indicators and collaborate on evaluations to

improve biodiversity performance by using existing collaborative structures and councils to coordinate them (Zinngrebe, 2023). Visual tools and maps have significant potential in facilitating the dialogue between stakeholders and linking them to specific land-use decisions (Rendón et al., 2022). Carroll and No Long-term stakeholder integration, supported by a robust legal mandate and integration into the broader policy landscape, is crucial for unlocking NBSAPs' full potential.

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Annex 5.6. Strategy 5

For more information on the inner-outer transformation model, see Wamsler et al. (2021). The components of the model show that: 1) clusters of transformative qualities/capacities; and 2) associated intermediary factors relate to; 3) certain worldviews, beliefs and values that delineate our relationships (with ourselves, others, work, the environment and future generations). These influence, in turn, the three dimensions of agency at individual and collective level: interbeing, inter-thinking and interacting.

Osberg et al. (2024) provide important insights into the interplay between people's motivation, sense of agency and social paradigms, with direct implications for policy and practice.

Through a leverage points²⁰ approach, Richardson et al. (2020) focuses on reducing domination to the 5 positive relationships from Kellert's typology - care, meaning (narrative), emotion, beauty and senses.

The move to a society of care, wellbeing and interdependencies is what is highlighted and described in the inner-outer transformation model in Wamsler et al. (2021). And these aspects are highlighted in the IMAGINE model/flower described in Ives et al. (2023).

Action 5.1: Increase nature connectedness

1. Case study: The Green Minds project

The Green Minds project in the city of Plymouth, UK, aims to put nature at the heart of decision making and inspire a new wave of investment in nature-based solutions. This meant fundamentally challenging existing attitudes and behaviours towards nature: how people think about it; how people engage with it; how people work with it. The project aimed to:

- Inspire people to connect with nature through delivering rewilding and nature-based projects on the ground that increase habitats and species diversity
- Experiment with different delivery and management approaches that support community stewardship and green enterprise, creating 'green mindsets'
- Use science and creative digital tools to make nature visible and exciting

A systems approach and pathways to nature connectedness theory were used to design audience engagement, community participation activities, nature-based enterprise, improvements to green/blue spaces, community stewardship and a nature-based leadership programme for professional audiences. Other examples of activities informed by the pathways included nature-based land management training, citizen science, place-making through infrastructure, communications, a series of creative commissions and social prescribing programme.

The case study demonstrates the value of applying and combining systems approaches and focused inner transformations for changing people's feelings, minds, attitudes towards nature to

²⁰ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

meet sustainable land use goals. It exemplifies the transformative potential of increasing the recognition of nature connectedness and creating new narratives. A large, urban local authority led the project, embedding green and blue infrastructure into the cities growth strategy to maximize benefits for health and wellbeing, community cohesion, biodiversity, economy and climate resilience. Key actors supporting the work were non-governmental conservation organizations, social enterprises and researchers.

2. Renegotiating social contracts for ecological and social justice through eco-social contracts

A social contract is an implicit or explicit agreement among members of a society, comprising a web of relationships that bind citizens, communities, institutions and governments into a coherent society. These contracts often reflect dominant social paradigms rooted in anthropocentric views, emphasizing human mastery over nature and prioritizing human rights and interests to maintain social order and promote justice (Mohamed & Huntjens, 2023). Traditional economic models, advocating for growth and private ownership, reinforce these views, often neglecting the intrinsic value of nature (Huntjens, 2021; K. O'Brien et al., 2009). Despite the rise of new economic models that advocate for ecological regeneration and widespread justice, many still privilege human well-being over ecological sustainability (Mohamed & Huntjens, 2023).

Recent scholarship suggests that due to escalating climate risks, ongoing ecological crises and deepening inequalities, there is a pressing need to renegotiate these contracts (Adger et al., 2013; Huntjens, 2021; K. O'Brien et al., 2009) towards a more eco-social framing. Scholars highlight the need for new roles for states and governance that acknowledge the multifaceted nature of these crises, moving beyond traditional governance models that often exclude marginalized voices and are susceptible to exploitation by powerful, undemocratic interests (Dryzek, 2002; Wamsler & Riggers, 2018; Weale, 2011).

The call for a fundamental renegotiation of social contracts and economies is urgent, aiming for a sustainable, healthy and just global society. This requires a profound restructuring of our societal goals and a rethinking of humanity's relationship with nature (Mohamed & Huntjens, 2023). Emerging from this discourse is the concept of a Natural Social Contract or Eco-Social Contract, envisioned as a shift from an anthropocentric to an ecocentric worldview, promoting a philosophy where human behaviour aligns with ecological and social well-being (Huntjens, 2021; UNRISD, 2022).

This new type of social contract is championed by platforms like the Global Research and Action Platform for a New Eco-Social Contract, supported by over 200 organizations, which seeks to establish economies that serve all life forms, not just human interests (Huntjens et al., 2023). These contracts aim to integrate ecological preservation with social equity, recognizing that solutions to environmental degradation also address social injustices. They advocate for a society where humans naturally engage in mutual aid, cooperation and reciprocity—qualities essential for sustainable and equitable global development (Huntjens, 2021).

By fostering collaboration across different sectors and governance levels, these new social contracts strive to cultivate societies that are not only sustainable but also just and equitable, aligning with the collective need for an ecologically interconnected and socially fair world.

3. Integrating nature into everyday life: pathways, practices and perspectives

- **Pathways to nature connectedness:**

The concept of nature connectedness underscores a significant shift in how we engage with our environment. It employs a structured approach through sensory and emotional involvement, urging us to notice and appreciate nature's intrinsic beauty and meanings. This connection is not only about periodic encounters but involves a deep, continuous interaction that influences various societal domains including education, health, urban planning and more. Efforts to integrate these pathways into daily life are recommended to effect a cultural reset in our interactions with nature, overcoming what has been called nature deficit disorder²¹ (Louv, 2005, 2012), suggesting a transformational shift in educational policies and urban designs that foster durable relationships with the natural world (Lumber et al., 2017; Richardson et al., 2020; SEI & CEEW, 2022; Sheffield et al., 2022).

- **Traditional plant medicines:**

The use of traditional plant medicines offers profound insights into our relationship with nature, impacting how we view ourselves and our community within the ecological system. These practices are rooted in Indigenous and local traditions and have been recognized for their potential to foster significant psychological and environmental transformations. Through the therapeutic use of these medicines, individuals can experience shifts in perception that enhance personal and ecological well-being, potentially addressing psychological challenges and promoting sustainability-oriented behaviours (Abson et al., 2017; Forstmann & Sagioglou, 2017; Irvine et al., 2023; Lyons & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Sagioglou & Forstmann, 2022; Watts et al., 2022).

- **Indigenous and regenerative economics:**

Integrating Indigenous perspectives into economic systems highlights a relational approach to sustainability, emphasizing the importance of ecological and cultural values. This perspective is particularly potent when considering the valuation of ecosystems, where Indigenous insights can reshape economic frameworks to recognize and conserve the interconnected nature of human and ecological health. This shift requires a nuanced appreciation of various capitals—social, cultural, ecological—and their roles in fostering sustainable economies that transcend traditional capitalist constraints (Normyle et al., 2023; Shannon et al., 2022).

- **The role of nature documentaries:**

²¹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Nature documentaries have evolved from mere visual spectacles to active educational tools that influence public perceptions and behaviours towards conservation. By moving beyond the portrayal of nature as an untouched wilderness, these documentaries now play a critical role in highlighting the interconnectedness of human activities and natural ecosystems, shaping public discourse on environmental responsibility and conservation strategies (Jones, Thomas-Walters, et al., 2019).

These varied elements—pathways to nature connectedness, traditional medicinal practices, regenerative economic principles and transformative media—collectively illustrate a multifaceted approach to understanding and enhancing our relationship with the environment. Each aspect not only supports individual and community growth but also contributes to a broader cultural shift towards sustainability and ecological awareness. This integration of knowledge and practices across different realms of life invites people to rethink and reshape our interactions with the world, aiming for a harmonious coexistence with nature. The following table (table SM.5.10) provides concrete examples of initiatives that embody these strategies, illustrating how they can influence consumer behaviour and political decision-making over time.

Table SM.5.10. Examples of Initiatives Promoting Nature Connectedness and Sustainable Worldviews.

Example	Key actors	References
<p>The Work That Reconnects: provides practices and perspectives drawn from systems science, Deep Ecology and many spiritual traditions that elicit our existential connectivity with the web of life through space and time. This interactive group process was developed by Joanna Macy. It draws on Systems Thinking²², Deep Ecology and Deep Time, Spiritual Traditions and Undoing Oppression. “The Work That Reconnects helps people discover and experience their innate connections with each other and the self-healing powers of the web of life, transforming despair and overwhelm into inspired, collaborative action.”</p> <p>– Joanna Macy</p>	<p>Civil society, NGOs</p>	<p>(Eaton & Hamilton, 2023; Hollis-Walker, 2012; Macy, 2007; Macy & Brown, 2014; Seymour & Levin, 2004)</p>
<p>Interfaith Rainforest Initiative and UNEP’s Faith for Earth Initiative: a multi-faith alliance that works to bring moral urgency and faith-based leadership to global efforts to end tropical deforestation. Provides training to spiritual leaders in delivering messages about stewardship.</p>	<p>Faith-based organizations</p>	<p>Caldwell et al., 2022; Ives et al., 2018; UNEP, 2018, 2019a, 2020; Wamsler et al., 2018; Woiwode et al., 2021</p>

²² See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Example	Key actors	References
Extinction Rebellion: A decentralised, international and politically non-partisan movement using non-violent direct action and civil disobedience to persuade governments to act justly on the Climate and Ecological Emergency.	Civil society, NGOs, activists	Berglund & Schmidt, 2020; Gardner et al., 2022; Gunningham, 2019; Westwell & Bunting, 2020

Action 5.2: Create new narratives and imaginaries

1. Shifting cultural narratives

A constellation of deep cultural beliefs and values supports and justifies human exploitation of non-human nature, working against a vision of harmony between all living beings on Earth (Berzonsky & Moser, 2017; Figueroa Helland & Lindgren, 2016; Lent, 2017). These commitments which constrain imaginations include: a belief in human separation from and dominion over nature (Berzonsky & Moser, 2017; Eisenstein, 2018; Scott et al., 2021; White, 1967); a dominant economic narrative of neoliberal capitalism that eulogises notions of economic growth, private ownership and accumulation, individualism²³, entrepreneurship and small government (Hickel, 2022; Huntjens, 2021; Raworth, 2017; Riedy, 2020); market values of individualism, and consumerism (IPBES, 2022a) which curb the expression of alternative imaginaries (Fisher, 2009) and values such as ethics of care (IPBES, 2022a); and the cultural legacies of colonialism, which have often normalized unjust relations between low and high income countries. These pervasive cultural narratives combine to justify ecological and social exploitation in the pursuit of economic growth (German, 2022; Healey & Barish, 2019; Korten, 2015; Lovins et al., 2018; Monbiot, 2016; Waddock, 2016), with devastating impacts for biodiversity.

One of the most powerful leverage points (Meadows, 1999) for realizing a vision of harmony between human and non-human nature is to transform culture – changing the paradigms, mindsets and intents (Abson et al., 2017; Meadows, 1999; Woiwode et al., 2021) that constrain the story of what it means to be human on this planet. Culture has many definitions but is used here in the sociological sense to refer to ‘processes of meaning-making’, revealed through ‘rituals, symbols, evaluations, norms and categories’ (Spillman, 2020). Scholars of transformation have begun to explore how to catalyse transformation of meanings at individual, group and civilisational scales (Milkoreit, 2017; M.-L. Moore & Milkoreit, 2020; Riedy, 2022; Riedy & Waddock, 2022; P. Smith & Howe, 2015; Wamsler, Bristow, et al., 2022).

Culture is continually reproduced by individuals as they share their own experiences with others, respond to perceived social norms and react to the broader landscape of meaning in which they are immersed. Culture is not static; when individuals reproduce culture, they have some (limited) agency to shape and change culture by emphasizing the meanings that matter to them. If many individuals start to express and live by care for and connection to, non-human nature, those

²³ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

meanings can start to take root in culture. Thus, transformation of personal meanings and values is one pathway to cultural transformation. It has been well-established that individuals holding certain values or meanings are more likely to take actions consistent with transformative change (Brink & Wamsler, 2019; Crompton, 2010; Stern, 2000). For example, values research indicates that those operating from intrinsic ‘bigger than self’ values are more likely to adopt and sustain behaviours consistent with addressing sustainability challenges (Crompton, 2010; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021). Further, research in adult learning and developmental psychology shows that the meanings and capacities that allow individuals to recognize and act on sustainability challenges need to be developed.

Related questions have been taken up and addressed by the emergent field of inner transformation for sustainability (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021). It is a dynamic field that has attracted professionals from many disciplines and domains and is thus conceptualized using various terms (including inner-outer transformation, inner transition, existential resilience and existential sustainability) (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021). Inner transformation for sustainability aims is to support integrative approaches that link inner and outer dimensions of transformation across sectors and levels to, consequently, enhance individual, collective and planetary wellbeing and regeneration (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021; Wamsler & Bristow, 2022). Inner dimensions are in this context defined as individual and collective consciousness, mindsets, beliefs, values, worldviews and associated inner capacities/qualities (cognitive, emotional, relational) (Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021, 2022). The concept recognizes that inner and outer dimensions are never separate but are co-created (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021). On this basis, inner transformation involves changes in the sphere of human inner dimensions and refers to all kinds of actions at individual, collective and system levels that support integrative changes in views, structures and practices, which address the impacts, drivers and causes of today’s polycrisis²⁴, including biodiversity loss (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021).

The scholarly work that has emerged from the field of inner transformation for sustainability has also been taken up in practice. Examples include The Inner Development Goals Initiative, The UNDP Conscious Food Systems Alliance, The Inner Green Deal and the Contemplative Sustainable Futures Program with its vast network and outreach activities (Janss et al., 2023; Jordan, 2021; Wamsler, 2019; Wamsler et al., 2024; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2022). These initiatives support integrative inner-outer transformation across all sectors and levels to ‘rattle’ unsustainable practices, norms, cultures and power structures. Related work involves, amongst other things, the creation of educational initiatives (Rupprecht & Wamsler, 2023; Wamsler et al., 2024), capacity development and communities of practice to create fields of change by nurturing transformative (individual and collective) capacities (Wamsler et al., 2020; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021).

The Inner Development Goals framework was co-designed by thousands of experts, practitioners and scientists (Inner Development Goals, 2021) and is linked to other scientific models, such as the inner-outer transformation model (Inner Development Goals, 2021; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021, 2022). The framework is a communication tool that advocates for transformative capacities²⁴ that can help accelerate work towards the achievement of the 2030 Agenda for

²⁴ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Sustainable Development (SDGs). It has been increasingly taken up by private-sector and non-profit organizations, as well as educational and governmental bodies.

The key question for cultural transformation is how to help a sufficiently large number of people to develop transformative capacities, ‘wake up’ (Chris Riedy & Chris Riedy, 2016; Riedy, 2013; Riedy & Waddock, 2022) to the impact humans are having on the rest of nature and become motivated to take action to eliminate this impact.

One of the most promising practices for transforming inner meanings is transformative learning (Bentz & O’Brien, 2019; Freire, 1974; Linnér & Wibeck, 2021; Mezirow, 1997; E. W. Taylor & Cranton, 2012). Transformative learning aims to effect change in the habits of mind and points of view that individuals hold (Mezirow, 1997). In other words, it seeks to transform the meanings that individuals carry. Transformative learning typically employs dialogic and experiential pedagogies, aimed at triggering ‘disorienting dilemmas’ that shake learners out of the comfortable meanings they hold to be true and open them up to new meanings.

The dialogic approach of transformative learning points to the importance of social learning in cultural transformation. It is often through exposure to different values and meanings held by others that learners start to question their own values. Further, finding ways to live the new meanings you have adopted can be facilitated by the support of others who are already living those meanings. This is where ‘communities of practice’ can play a crucial role in cultural transformation. A community of practice is a group of people with a shared interest or passion for a practice, who learn how to do it better through regular interaction (Cundill et al., 2015; Riedy et al., 2018; Wenger, 2011). While individual meaning transformation is crucial to cultural transformation, it is only when individuals share those meanings with others that new narratives start to take hold that have the power to effect cultural change.

This points to another opportunity for facilitating cultural transformation, which is to actively disseminate new meanings that can form the basis for new narratives, discourses and imaginaries (M.-L. Moore & Milkoreit, 2020; Osberg et al., 2024; Riedy, 2022; Riedy & Waddock, 2022; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2022). Challenging the dominant narratives of human separation from nature, neoliberal capitalism and colonialism requires doing more than critiquing; new, positive, inspiring alternatives also need to be imagined and articulated (M.-L. Moore & Milkoreit, 2020). Currently, the most prominent popular cultural narratives about the future promoted by Hollywood films, fiction²⁵ and gaming are relentlessly dystopian (Bulfin, 2017). While such narratives get attention, they can lead to despair if not coupled with hopeful visions and a sense of agency. The meanings that could form the basis for new hopeful cultural narratives are gradually becoming clearer – a systems perspective, harmony with nature, social justice and equality, regenerative goals, human awakening, compassion and cooperation, wellbeing and pluralism (Riedy, 2020; Riedy & Waddock, 2022; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021). There have been some efforts to encode such meanings in cultural objects, including novels (K. S. Robinson, 2020), short story collections (K. O’Brien et al., 2019) and films (e.g., Damon Gameau’s *2040*). However, if cultural transformation is to support a vision of harmony between all living beings on Earth, efforts to share these new meanings will need to greatly accelerate and be taken on by all kinds of actors.

²⁵ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

2. Cultural transformation through art and festivals

The power of arts in shaping new meanings and narratives is increasingly recognized as a transformative force within cultural discourses. The most prominent cultural narratives, often disseminated through Hollywood films, fiction and gaming, frequently depict dystopian futures that can lead to despair (Bulfin, 2017). Such narratives, unless paired with hopeful visions and a sense of agency (E. Bennett et al., 2016), may stifle proactive engagement with environmental and social issues. To counter this, there is a growing emphasis on nurturing narratives that promote ecological connectivity, harmony with nature, social justice and equality (Durán et al., 2023; Riedy, 2020; Riedy & Waddock, 2022).

Artistic endeavours across various disciplines—such as novels (J. Robinson, 2020), short story collections (K. O'Brien et al., 2019) and films—play a pivotal role in crafting these new cultural narratives. Such works not only foster a sense of interconnectedness with nature but also make previously invisible relationships visible, linking personal experiences to broader ecological and social scales (Galafassi, 2023; J. W. Moore, 2014). This burgeoning area of art and science collaboration is vital for comprehending and addressing the complexities of contemporary crises (Heras et al., 2021; Shrivastava et al., 2012).

Festivals, as dynamic platforms for transformative learning, combine elements of science and the arts, including narrative storytelling, dance, music and visual arts (Bentz, 2020; Sandercock & Attili, 2010). They are designed to be creative, inspiring and engaging, moving away from didactic and risk-oriented formats to more inclusive and empathetic approaches (Bentz, 2020; Pereira et al., 2018; M. Reed et al., 2018). These events are particularly effective in enhancing community resilience by fostering inner capacities like self-efficacy, courage and trust (R. Fischer et al., 2014; Moser, 2013; Pisters et al., 2019; Wamsler et al., 2020; Yudkin et al., 2022; Zygmunt et al., 2018).

Moreover, festivals can serve as catalysts for addressing and healing collective traumas and rebuilding connections—both within communities and with the natural environment (N. Hopkins et al., 2016; Volkas, 2014; Walsh et al., 2020). They provide rich opportunities for communal engagement in settings that are already valued by the community, such as county fairs, summer concert series and food festivals (Findlay & Williams, Jordan, 2014; Lopez, 2021). These events often involve ritualized activities which can significantly enhance communal empathy and solidarity (R. Fischer et al., 2014; Müller et al., 2023).

Evidence suggests that locally oriented transformative community events or festivals can effectively shift paradigms, promote environmental stewardship and foster new community values (Findlay & Williams, Jordan, 2014; Lopez, 2021). They enhance community cohesion and guide communal orientation towards sustainable futures, effectively linking individual participation with broader environmental planning and policymaking processes (Kavanagh et al., 2020; Lopez, 2021). Such festivals not only enhance nature connectedness but also strengthen community bonds and individual commitments to environmental and social values (R. Fischer et al., 2014; Forstmann et al., 2020; N. Hopkins et al., 2016; Queiroz et al., 2018).

Festivals also provide a platform for marginalized and underrepresented groups, enabling their voices to be heard in formal environmental planning processes (Hügel & Davies, 2020; Lamb et al., 2019; Lipiec et al., 2018; Lucia, 2020; Sarkissian & Wenman, 2010). By integrating

Indigenous perspectives on nature-connectedness, festivals can broaden the scope of transformational possibilities and address collective traumas, enriching the community's cultural and environmental engagement (Müller et al., 2023; Volkas, 2014).

In summary, the integration of arts within community festivals and public celebrations not only fosters a renewed connection with nature and community but also empowers individuals and groups to actively participate in shaping a resilient and sustainable future. These activities underscore the importance of cultural narratives and artistic expressions in driving transformative change, making them essential components in the journey towards a more just and sustainable world.

Action 5.3: Shift social norms regarding production and consumption

1. Integrating inner dimensions and civil actions for systemic change

Institutionalizing inner dimensions involves embedding transformative capacities and intrinsic values deeply within institutional and political systems to create sustainable narratives across various sectors (Wamsler & Osberg, 2022). This strategic integration requires revising organizational vision statements, communication tools, project management frameworks, working structures, policies and regulations (Gordon, 2023; Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021; Wamsler & Osberg, 2022). Institutionalizing inner dimensions involves embedding transformative capacities and intrinsic values deeply within institutional and political systems to create sustainable narratives across various sectors (Wamsler & Osberg, 2022). This strategic integration requires revising organizational vision statements, communication tools, project management frameworks, working structures, policies and regulations (Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021; Wamsler, Bristow, et al., 2022). It also involves adjusting the allocation of human and financial resources, enhancing learning infrastructures and fostering collaborations (Gordon, 2023; Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021; Wamsler, Mundaca, et al., 2022; Wamsler & Osberg, 2022). Such systemic changes are aimed at addressing the root causes of sustainability crises by shifting the dominant social paradigms and mindsets that underpin unsustainable practices.

The role of civil society in changing social norms is pivotal. Individual and collective behaviours, such as consumer choices in mobility, diet and energy use, significantly impact social norms. Beyond personal choices, civic and political actions—including participation in social movements, voting behaviours and discussions about environmental issues—can catalyse broader societal shifts. These actions influence policies and contribute to the collective action necessary to foster environmental concern and support for sustainable policies (Geiger & Swim, 2016).

Social movements play a critical role in creating new norms and practices that challenge the status quo and bring urgent issues to public attention. By fostering complex contagions of new norms, these movements can initiate significant changes. The success of such movements often hinges on the support of a diverse network of allies who amplify their message across different communities. Research indicates that when a small percentage of the population engages in sustained, non-violent actions, they can achieve considerable political success (Chenoweth & Stephan, 2012; Engels et al., 2023; IPCC, 2023; Muñoz et al., 2018; Nisbett & Spaiser, 2023;

Wasow, 2020). The threshold for social movement mobilization necessary to achieve broader social change is relatively low. Research conducted by Chenoweth and Stephan (2012) analyzed 323 campaigns and found that nonviolent resistance campaigns were significantly more likely to achieve their political demands when at least 3.5% of the population actively participated. Diverse allies can reinforce and multiply the messages of the movement, by introducing it to communities external to the movement's direct spheres of influence²⁶ (Nardini et al., 2021; Nisbett & Spaiser, 2023).

Together, the systematic institutional changes and the dynamic influence of civil society and social movements illustrate a powerful dual approach to fostering deep, sustainable change. By aligning internal organizational transformations with robust external civil action, societies can effectively address and mitigate the underlying causes of environmental and sustainability crises.

2. Spread of social norms through Complex Contagion

The propagation of new social norms, ideas, or behaviours often occurs through complex contagion processes within social networks, where an individual's adoption likelihood increases if a significant number of their peers have already embraced the new norm (Becken et al., 2021; Fink et al., 2021; Lehmann & Ahn, 2018). This contagion typically starts slowly and gradually until it reaches a critical mass of early adopters, at which point it becomes self-reinforcing and accelerates the transition of the social system towards the new norm or behaviour. Factors influencing complex contagion include the similarity among interacting individuals, the alignment of new norms with existing values and the practicality of the behaviours being promoted (Kaaronen & Strelkovskii, 2020; Lehmann & Ahn, 2018; Nyborg et al., 2016; Schaumberg & Skowronek, 2022; Séré De Lanauze & Siadou-Martin, 2019; Woodly, 2015). Networks with clusters of strong local ties are particularly effective at facilitating and speeding up this process (Centola et al., 2018; O'Sullivan et al., 2015).

3. Sectors for the spread of social norms: Policy, business, education and knowledge systems

Transformative change in societal norms and behaviours is a multifaceted process influenced by policy interventions, business innovations, educational practices and shifts in knowledge systems, mindsets and understandings. This synthesis explores how different sectors contribute to shaping sustainable social norms and practices, emphasizing the need for an integrated approach to foster meaningful societal transformation.

- Role of policy interventions in changing social norms:

Policy interventions have historically played a crucial role in transforming societal norms and behaviours. By increasing the visibility of desired behaviours, policies help establish and propagate new norms (Constantino et al., 2022; C. R. Schneider & Van Der Linden, 2023). For example, smoking bans in public spaces have shifted social practices towards non-smoking norms even in unregulated areas (Nyborg & Rege, 2003). Moreover, policies that signal the value of nature, promote sustainable practices over material consumption, invest in infrastructure

²⁶ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

like bike lanes and strengthen environmental education can catalyze widespread behavioural change (Akenji et al., 2021; Galafassi et al., 2018; Haberl et al., 2020; Yoeli et al., 2013).

- Role of business in changing social norms:

Businesses also play a pivotal role, with some firms leading the way by adopting and promoting sustainable technologies such as solar and wind power and battery electric mobility (International Energy Agency, 2023; Nijssse et al., 2023; SYSTEMIQ, 2023). These initiatives not only contribute to the uptake of sustainable options but also influence broader social norms towards environmental sustainability.

- Role of education in changing social norms:

Education is another critical lever for social change. Transformative educational processes that connect students with local actors like farmers and entrepreneurs can enhance agency and foster sustainability practices (Jenkin, 2014; Macintyre et al., 2018). Moreover, engaging students in real-world projects and building their skills can empower them to act collectively against climate challenges (Centola et al., 2018; Centola & Macy, 2007; Lenton, 2020; Lenton et al., 2022; Törnberg, 2018). Programmes that address eco-anxiety through 'active hope' activities also play a significant role, enabling young people to shape a sustainable future (Macy & Johnstone, 2012).

- Role of knowledge systems in changing social norms:

Knowledge systems that transform 'noise' into meaningful signals can trigger sustainable changes in social norms and behaviours (E. O'Brien & Klein, 2017; W. O'Brien & Yazdani Aliabadi, 2020; Tàbara & Chabay, 2013). This transformation requires advanced learning abilities and a shift in societal values and practices, potentially leading to a restorative worldview that prioritizes a thriving future for humanity (Fazey et al., 2020; Tàbara, 2023).

Effective societal transformation requires a synergistic approach that integrates policy, business innovation, education and knowledge systems. By leveraging these interconnected domains, we can more rapidly instigate and sustain shifts in social norms and behaviours that are critical for achieving environmental sustainability and social equity. This collective approach ensures that each sector reinforces the others, creating a robust foundation for enduring change.

4. Social dynamics and policy instruments for the spread of new social norms

Understanding the mechanisms behind the spread of new social norms, ideas and behaviours is crucial for designing effective strategies that encourage societal transformation. This analysis delves into the complex contagion processes within social networks and explores the necessary conditions and policy interventions that facilitate the adoption and sustainability of new practices.

- Spread of social norms through complex contagion

The propagation of new social norms, ideas, or behaviours often occurs through complex contagion processes within social networks, where an individual's likelihood of adoption increases significantly if many of their peers have already embraced the new norm (Becken et al., 2021; Fink et al., 2021; Lehmann & Ahn, 2018). This spread is initially slow and gradual but gains momentum once a critical mass of early adopters is reached, turning the contagion self-reinforcing and accelerating the transition of the social system towards the new norm or

behaviour. Influential factors include the similarity among interacting individuals, the alignment of new norms with existing values and the practicality of the behaviours being promoted (Kaaronen & Strelkovskii, 2020; Lehmann & Ahn, 2018; Nyborg et al., 2016; Schaumberg & Skowronek, 2022; Séré De Lanauze & Siadou-Martin, 2019; Woodly, 2015). Particularly, networks characterized by clusters of strong local ties can significantly facilitate and expedite this process (Centola et al., 2018; O’Sullivan et al., 2015).

- Need for coordination and visibility in behaviour change

Furthermore, behaviours that are easily observable, such as smoking or mask-wearing, are more likely to spread due to the prominent role of social norms and visible sanctioning (Nyborg et al., 2016). Increasing the visibility of a behaviour can significantly enhance compliance, outperforming even financial incentives (Shrum, 2021; Yoeli et al., 2013). Techniques like climate shaming through public rankings, ratings, labelling and disclosures of corporate climate performance have proven quite effective in modifying behaviours (Yadin, 2023). As transitioning to new behaviours often involves significant costs, supportive policies such as taxes, fees, subsidies, or infrastructure investments are essential (Nyborg et al., 2016; Stiglitz et al., 2017). For instance, public investments like bicycle lanes not only improve infrastructure but also shift societal expectations and norms, signaling that incentives (and potentially social norms) have changed for everyone (Nyborg et al., 2016). This interaction between social, economic and other feedback mechanisms suggests that creating synergies between self-reinforcing feedbacks²⁷ across multiple domains can strategically assist policymakers in fostering conditions conducive to change (Fesenfeld, 2022; Pahle et al., 2018)

Effective behavioural change hinges on a nuanced understanding of social contagion and policy incentives. By strategically enhancing the visibility of desired behaviours and deploying targeted policy measures, it is possible to catalyze and sustain new social norms. This approach underscores the importance of integrating social dynamics with policy interventions to facilitate transformative changes within communities, ultimately fostering more sustainable and adaptive social systems.

Action 5.4: Facilitate transformative learning processes and spaces

1. Transformative learning

Indigenous cultures often sustain a deep connection between biodiverse ecosystems and human well-being and so protecting biodiversity can be inseparable from sustaining Indigenous cultures, knowledge and livelihoods. This section extends this logic to include non-Indigenous cultures by suggesting that there are ways to nurture transformations in values, worldviews and core narratives – often informed by Indigenous nature-cultures - that enhance both individual agency and collective capacity to sustain biodiverse social-ecological systems. This “transformative learning” can take place in both formal and informal spaces (Bentz & O’Brien, 2019; Freire, 1974; Linnér & Wibeck, 2021; Mezirow, 1997; E. W. Taylor & Cranton, 2012) and can be supported, trained and developed across individual, organizational and societal levels

²⁷ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

(Ramstetter et al., 2023; Rupprecht & Wamsler, 2023; Wamsler, 2019, 2020; Wamsler, Bristow, et al., 2022; Wamsler et al., 2024).

Transformative learning is a dynamic process that prompts individuals to rethink and potentially change their deeply rooted perspectives and behaviours. The concept captures how people process challenging situations that disrupt their usual way of thinking, leading them to adopt new values and worldviews (Mezirow, 1997, 2009). It involves a deep psychological change in self-understanding, belief systems and actions, which can also influence broader societal and environmental changes (Wamsler, Bristow, et al., 2022; Wamsler, Hertog, et al., 2021). This idea resonates with what Argyris and Schön (1974) call generative learning, where individuals learn to look beyond the surface of problems and challenge established norms. Senge (1990) describes a significant shift in mindset as essential to this deeper learning and (Scharmer, 2016) applied this idea to a process of 'learning from the future,' involving stages of sensing, being fully present and realizing new possibilities. This approach emphasizes commitment and open inquiry over mere adaptation to the current situation (Argyris & Schön, 1974). Moreover, transformative learning reflects key dynamics within entire social-ecological systems, especially at the 'edge of chaos,' a state where order and disorder are balanced (Packard, 1988). This delicate equilibrium is crucial for fostering creativity and innovation in these systems. Some suggest that this transitional phase is vital for learning and self-organization, leading to new, emergent orders in these systems (Gell-Mann, 1994; Stacey, 1995). Disorder, rather than being a negative aspect, is a necessary element for openness, curiosity, empowerment, joy and hope (Goldstein et al., 2023), supporting the idea that life and social-ecological systems flourish in this balance between order and disorder, maximizing innovation and creativity (Kauffman, 1993; Waldrop, 1993).

Surely all cultures have ways to foster transformative learning in individuals, a process that is essential for personal and societal growth and often contributes to transformative capacity. Awe-inspiring experiences related to nature can ignite biophilic emotions, leading to personal development and pro-social behaviours (Gosnell, 2022; Shiota, 2021; Walsh et al., 2020). Art and cultural expressions can play a significant role in transformative learning. Art spaces and experiences in various societal spheres stimulate imagination, sense-making, spiritual connection and emotional resilience, critical for cultural worldview transformations (Galafassi et al., 2018; Mesch, 1996; J. Robinson, 2020). Festivals can blend sciences and arts, incorporating narrative storytelling, dance, music and visual arts to create potent venues for transformative learning (Bentz, 2020; Sandercock & Attili, 2010). Even ordinary events like county fairs, summer concert series and food festivals can offer immersive experiences that align with UNESCO's (2021) concept of transformative education by engaging people with their world, fostering a sense of value, safety and inclusion in their community. These diverse cultural practices demonstrate the potential for transformative learning in different societies. While transformative learning offers profound opportunities for growth, it also carries risks and challenges, necessitating careful nurturing and support. Profound shifts in worldview can alienate individuals from their original social groups, triggering existential crises as they navigate between old and new perspectives. It is crucial to not only facilitate transformative learning experiences but also provide ongoing support to individuals during their transition, helping them find new communities where their changed perspectives can be consolidated and nurtured (Bridges, 2009).

Transformative change practitioners have reported that transformative learning was pivotal in their own professional development, often through association with non-western cultures and

Indigenous and local communities that led them to “unlearn” their sense of what counts as useful knowledge (B. E. Goldstein et al., 2022). Reflecting this recognition, systems change educators often seek to support transformative learning opportunities as a core element of their curriculum, enabling learners to navigate discomfort in a trusted setting that enables them to gain new insights (E. W. Taylor, 2007). These educational programmes aim to support personal paradigm shifts while enabling students to do the same for others, as they drive transformative changes in communities and systems (Bess et al., 2010; O. Gill et al., 2022; G. M. Henderson, 2002; Perkins et al., 2007). These pedagogic efforts are challenging, since they involve sustaining disorder, instability and discomfort as essential elements of a creative pedagogy (Stacey, 1995; Symes & Wheatley, 2019) that can have no uniform approach due to widely varying learning contexts and diverse life experiences of the learners themselves (Boiral et al., 2009; Growth that Matters, 2021; Hochachka, 2019; Rooke & Torbert, 2005). The challenges of both facilitating transformative learning within curricula and enabling students to integrate these changes into their lives are significant (Bryant et al., 2023; E. Taylor & Cranton, 2013; Wamsler, 2019, 2020).

In the pursuit of sustainability, transformative learning at an organizational scale is essential but presents distinct challenges beyond individual paradigm shifts. While societies resist changes to their prevailing paradigms more than they resist anything else (Meadows, 1999), systems practitioners aim to overcome systemic rigidity and institutional constraints by designing novel organizational structures that facilitate transformative learning (Bess et al., 2010; B. E. Goldstein et al., 2022; G. M. Henderson, 2002). Organizational learning, more complex than the sum of individual learnings (Crossan et al., 1999), embeds learning within an organization's structure, strategy, routines and practices (Chiva et al., 2010). Targeted interventions are vital for addressing the uneven distribution of biodiversity degradation (Cusworth et al., 2023) and promoting social equity, especially for historically marginalized groups such as many Indigenous Peoples (Leach et al., 2010, 2018; J. W. Moore, 2014; Tuckey et al., 2023). Transformative organizations break conventional knowledge silos, integrating diverse knowledge systems, including Western scientific and Indigenous perspectives, to enable transdisciplinary knowledge co-creation to address systemic issues (Loorbach et al., 2017; Olsson et al., 2004, 2006; Tengö et al., 2014; Westley et al., 2013; Wolfram, 2016).

Several types of organizations – or “transformation catalysts” (Waddock, 2022; Waddock & Waddell, 2021)– can play this crucial role of supporting collective transformative learning. Translocal networks support multiple communities, connecting them to resources and spreading innovation and shared narratives and imaginaries across time and space (B. E. Goldstein & Butler, 2010; Loorbach et al., 2020; Tuckey et al., 2023). Networks can also operate at centres of decision-making, as shown by efforts to engage artists within climate and biodiversity international negotiations and mobilizations, such as ArtCOP around COP15. Additionally, learning spaces like transformation labs or ‘solutions spaces’ provide safe environments for experimenting with new sustainable practices, rules and paradigms (M.-L. Moore et al., 2018; Pereira et al., 2018; Riddell, 2015). These spaces can serve as an ‘imagination infrastructure,’ using social innovation lab methodologies (Westley et al., 2017) to imagine positive pathways and futures (R. Hopkins, 2019; Mulgan, 2022). Transformation catalysts can serve as powerful organizational engines for transformative learning and demand specific skills and attention. Systems change practitioners play a crucial role in creating “safe enough” spaces that support the disruption needed for transformative learning and balance the need for individual freedom to experiment with innovative ideas and practices while promoting effective collective action. They

need training and experience in engaging communities in transdisciplinary knowledge co-creation and understanding how to support redressing systemic injustices and confronting powerful actors who are resistant to sustainable and equitable futures, while also enabling the translation of groupwork into practical and policy-relevant outputs. To accomplish this, practitioners need to develop leadership skills that include emotional intelligence and experience in participatory co-design (Coops et al., 2022; Gaziulusoy & Erdoğan Öztekin, 2019; B. E. Goldstein et al., 2022).

Additionally, the importance of focusing transformative learning efforts on specific economic and trade systems, including financial and currency frameworks, global trade rules and high-impact sectors like food/agriculture and direct exploitation of organisms, is emphasized as essential for fostering regenerative worldviews and systemic changes. These areas are pinpointed as key drivers of biodiversity loss and therefore crucial targets for implementing interconnected health and future-oriented sustainability practices (Bentz & O'Brien, 2019; Mezirow, 1997). The role of experiential learning activities, such as participation in microscope clubs that enhance appreciation for the microbiome, is also highlighted as a vital component of transformative learning. These activities are shown to motivate pro-social and pro-environmental behaviours, effectively linking inner transformation with broader ecological consciousness (Gosnell, 2022; Shiota, 2021; Walsh et al., 2020). Examples of transformative learning initiatives that engage with biodiversity loss are detailed in table SM.5.11.

Table SM.5.11. Examples of targeted transformative learning and change spaces in systems where biodiversity loss is taking place.

Example	Key actors	References
Great Bear Rainforest: Personal transformations led to shifts in relationships and enabled conflicted sectors in government, forest companies and Indigenous Nations to collaborate – stabilizing and embedding a shared vision of ecosystem-based management led by Indigenous communities in the coastal temperate rainforest of Canada (<i>Great Bear Rainforest Agreement Highlights - Province of British Columbia</i> , n.d.).	Indigenous Peoples and local communities; civil society; private sector; government; forest industry	(Riddell, 2015; Riddell et al., 2012)
Conscious Food Systems Alliance (COFSA): A movement of food, agriculture and consciousness practitioners, convened by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) to support people from across food and agriculture systems to cultivate the inner capacities that activate systemic change and regeneration (UNDP, n.d.).	Farmers; scientific sector; national governments; intergovernmental organizations	(Wamsler, Bristow, et al., 2022)
The Sustainability Schools programme in Uganda: led by the National Association of Professional Environmentalists (NAPE), exemplifies transformative learning through its	Education sector	(Westoby & Lyons, 2017)

Example	Key actors	References
emphasis on social learning and community mobilization. The programme fosters a network of social relations that enable collective learning, dialogue and critical thinking; addressing significant social, ecological and economic challenges posed by resource conflicts and displacement (<i>National Association of Professional Environmentalists - NAPE</i> , 2024).		
Action Research Plus Network (AR+): a global community of practice for action-oriented scholar practitioners to find community and developmental support as they work on action-oriented research for transformation. The network provides coaching, co-labs and workshops that help scholar-practitioners to take the next steps in their own developmental learning (Action Research Plus Network, n.d.).	Scientific sector; civil society	(Bradbury et al., 2019)

2. Integrating transformative learning and transformations

Transformative learning spaces and networks serve as pivotal platforms for fostering systemic change. These environments are designed to cultivate shared learning, innovative practices and the development of new values. This synthesis explores how these transformative spaces, along with the role of communities of practice and governance arrangements, contribute to a deeper understanding and reshaping of complex systemic issues, paving the way for a sustainable integration of human and non-human nature.

Emerging governance arrangements, economic incentives and policies are increasingly guided by worldviews that prioritize nature, circularity and responsibilities toward nature. These perspectives are often derived from both systemic/complex worldviews and Indigenous and traditional cultures, which maintain practices for living in harmony with nature, exemplified by initiatives like the ICCA Consortium and Territories of Life movement. Furthermore, connecting people with important ideas to build shared visions and link them to new resources across sectors is crucial to generate momentum for change and root new worldviews in systems driving biodiversity loss.

Communities of practice play a significant role in cultural transformation by facilitating social learning, where individuals share meanings through regular interaction, challenging and refining their values (Cundill et al., 2015; Riedy et al., 2018; Wenger, 2011). These communities help individuals live out new meanings by providing support and exposure to diverse values and practices.

Scholars of transformation explore how to catalyze change of meanings on individual, group and global scales, identifying gaps in research that should include Indigenous and local knowledge to develop more plural understandings of transformations (Lam et al., 2020; Milkoreit, 2017;

Milkoreit et al., 2020; Riedy, 2022; Riedy & Waddock, 2022; P. Smith & Howe, 2015). Transformative learning also occurs through navigating conflicts among diverse actors, as demonstrated in the conservation efforts in the Great Bear Rainforest, where facilitated processes led to agreements protecting significant areas of the rainforest (Riddell, 2015; Riddell et al., 2012).

Finally, research underscores that individual, collective and system changes are deeply interconnected (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler, Osberg, et al., 2021). A shift in individual values toward caring for non-human nature can precipitate broader cultural transformations, with actor coalitions working together over time to institutionalize new dominant paradigms. This highlights the complex interplay between individual actions, collective efforts, institutional responses and societal structures in driving sustainable transformations.

Action 5.5: Knowledge co-creation

Principles of good practice in designing and managing co-creation interventions vary according to the theoretical framework applied, with some principles being well-established within the literature (Goldman et al., 2018). These principles often refer to various stages of the co-creation process, including co-design, co-creation and co-dissemination (Mauser et al., 2013). Principles of knowledge co-creation include:

- **Equity:** Co-creation emphasizes equity and justice, prioritizing the needs and interests of marginalized groups to facilitate transformative interventions (Chambers et al., 2022; Norström et al., 2020). These approaches seek to counteract epistemic injustices created by market-driven knowledge production, which can lead to violations of rights, autonomy, dependencies, clientelism and the loss of social capital (Oreskes & Conway, 2011; Proctor & Schiebinger, 2008).
- **Respect:** Co-creation processes respect diverse worldviews and are attentive to various ways of knowing and understanding reality (Gilio-Whitaker, 2019; Rigolot, 2020; Whyte, 2017; K. J. Wilson et al., 2020). This respect is cultivated through ongoing actions and interactions aimed at addressing and resolving longstanding conflicts and historical injustices, building intersubjective understanding and promoting norms and behaviours that mitigate power inequalities (Álvarez & Coolsaet, 2020).
- **Recognition:** Co-creation processes recognize the plurality of values and worldviews and the full agency and autonomy of different groups and actors. Recognition extends to valuing diverse forms of knowledge beyond the written and scientific, ensuring attentive and constructive engagement despite differences in understanding facts, values and interpretations (Jasanoff, 2004; Martin et al., 2016; Orlove et al., 2023).
- **Collaboration:** Co-creation fosters collaborative relationships among individuals, communities and organizations, emphasizing partnerships based on mutual responsibilities and ongoing ties rather than temporary joint efforts (Lam et al., 2021).
- **Nested Frameworks:** Co-creation recognizes the importance of nested frameworks that connect individual actors and interventions to broader institutions, governance systems and sociocultural norms. These frameworks shape how knowledge is produced and how decisions about sustainable development are made (Pascual et al., 2022).

Implementing these principles requires significant capacity building to foster mutual understanding, which is essential for initiating and sustaining co-creation partnerships. This

involves developing skills to navigate complex situations of conflict and disagreement to achieve beneficial outcomes (Caniglia et al., 2023; Van Kerkhoff & Lebel, 2015). Adhering to these principles in knowledge co-creation ensures that the process is inclusive, respectful and effective, contributing to the broader goals of systems transformations through integrated and equitable participation. To different degrees, these principles have been adopted by diverse, yet interconnected approaches aimed at strengthening the link between knowledge creation and action by institutionalizing knowledge co-creation across various contexts and cultures, highlighting both existing tools and proposals for future development. Co-creation approaches, are increasingly seen as effective tools for driving practical changes toward sustainable futures (Norström et al., 2020). There is now a vast array of terminologies, framings and methodologies related to knowledge co-creation (C. A. Miller & Wyborn, 2020), some of the most prominent include:

- **Participatory action research:** This approach involves researchers and stakeholders—those who can affect or are affected by the issue—collaborating in iterative cycles of action, reflection and research (Schubotz, 2020). Together, they define a future goal and implement actions that expand knowledge, enhance skills and address challenges, integrating these activities into the research process and promoting reflection on them (Vaughn & Jacquez, 2020). The degree of stakeholder participation can range from minimal (informing) to maximal (empowering) (Vaughn & Jacquez, 2020).
- **Mode-2 knowledge production:** Mode-2 knowledge production redefines the relationship between the governance and production of research (C. A. Miller & Wyborn, 2020). It characterizes knowledge production as socially distributed, action-oriented, transdisciplinary and accountable to multiple stakeholders. In this model, information flows bidirectionally, with science engaging with society and vice versa.
- **Transdisciplinary research:** Definitions of transdisciplinary research typically reference the integration of multiple scientific disciplines with non-scientific perspectives. Such research addresses societally relevant problems, fosters learning across disciplines and societal actors and generates knowledge that is scientifically credible, socially robust and practically applicable (Chambers et al., 2022). Transdisciplinary sustainability science involves scholars and societal actors collaboratively working toward transformative change, embracing context-specific, pluralistic, goal-oriented and interactive approaches (Norström et al., 2020). This type of research underscores the importance of diverse knowledge types—strategic for designing actions, empowering for enhancing agency and situated for practical application (Caniglia et al., 2020). It often requires navigating conflicting values and power dynamics to understand differing perspectives on change—who it serves and who drives it (Turnhout et al., 2020).
- **Post-normal science:** Post-normal science addresses complex problems in situations characterized by high stakes, significant uncertainties, disputed values and the urgent need for decisions. In these contexts, scientific knowledge alone cannot provide clear and uncontested solutions (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993). Central to post-normal science are debates about values and desired futures, requiring a dialogue among diverse, legitimate perspectives to foster mutual respect and facilitate learning, which supports informed decision-making.
- **Civic science:** Civic science encompasses various forms of public involvement in the scientific process, such as participatory, civil, civic, stakeholder and democratic science (C. A. Miller & Wyborn, 2020). These terms reflect the evolving relationship between the public

and scientific experts. The goals of civic science vary, including diversifying scientific representation, increasing citizen participation and democratizing the science-policy process. These aims focus on the stakes that the public and citizens have in scientific activities and their outcomes at the science-policy interface. An example of civic science in action is citizen science (Wamsler & Riggers, 2018).

- **Multiple-evidence based approaches:** International organizations and platforms like IPBES, IPCC and UNESCO employ multiple-evidence based approaches to generate knowledge for addressing global issues such as climate change and biodiversity loss (Tengö et al., 2017). These approaches highlight the value of integrating diverse knowledge systems, especially Indigenous and local knowledge systems that link deeply with nature and culture, which are vital for effective environmental management (Petzold et al., 2020; Tengö et al., 2017). For instance, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, influenced by this method, strongly advocates for the rights of Indigenous Peoples, acknowledges their territories and encourages the inclusion of their knowledge and participation in its implementation.
- **Plural co-existence approaches:** Increasingly, there is recognition that Indigenous knowledge possesses unique characteristics absent in scientific knowledge. Greg Cajete (2000) described this as the "metaphoric mind," encompassing imagination, art, creativity and dreaming. Indigenous knowledge is intimately involved with the phenomena under study, rooted in a deep ethical respect and a duty to ensure the well-being and abundance of natural ecosystems, exemplified by practices like the "honorable harvest" (Kimmerer, 2013) and recognizing that one lives in a moral landscape (Wienhues et al., 2023). Indigenous knowledge does not align with a single way of knowing, it is contextually situated, with knowledge plurality reflecting different landscapes and peoples. Grounded in this recognition, Indigenous scholars advocate for co-creation approaches that respect Indigenous ontologies and address the dominance of Eurocentric thinking in natural resource management (Howitt & Suchet-Pearson, 2006; Zanotti & Palomino-Schalscha, 2016). Several frameworks have emerged to foster this pluralistic co-creation:
 - *Etuaptmumk*²⁸ ("Two-Eyed Seeing" in Mi'kmaw, USA): Developed by Mi'kmaw Indigenous Peoples, this approach emphasizes the integration of Indigenous and mainstream knowledge systems, viewing them as complementary rather than contradictory (Bartlett et al., 2012). Elder Dr. Albert Marshall describes it as using "one eye with the strengths of Indigenous knowledges and ways of knowing and the other eye with the strengths of mainstream knowledges," to benefit all. Central to this approach is the belief that knowledge changes the holder, who then has a responsibility to act on that knowledge wisely. Two-Eyed Seeing promotes a pluralistic coexistence, where Indigenous knowledge systems are valued along with Western scientific insights, aiming for equitable and sustainable outcomes (Reid et al., 2020). This approach moves beyond the dialogue of integrating, combining or incorporating (commonly used as euphemisms for assimilating) other knowledges and ways of knowing *into* Western science and instead builds an ethic of knowledge coexistence and complementarity in knowledge generation.
 - *Waka Taurua*²⁸ ("Double Canoe" in Māori, New Zealand): A conceptual framework that symbolizes the unity of Western and Māori knowledges, characterized as two canoes

²⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

lashed together, each maintaining its distinct values and perspectives while striving for a common goal (Maxwell et al., 2020). This model emphasizes mutual respect and reciprocal care between the Indigenous-Māori community and their environment.

- *Ganma*²⁸ (“Two Ways” in Yolngu, Australia): Describes a dialectical relationship where distinct knowledge systems—like freshwater and saltwater—meet and mix without losing their individual characteristics (Muller et al., 2012). *Ganma* represents a dialectical method of engaging in meaningful two-way collaborations in which two opposed patterns of ideas complement, interact and relate to one another in ways that respect and preserve the distinctiveness of each knowledge system as separate and opposed parts of one whole.
- **Indigenous methodologies approach:** Indigenous Peoples and local communities are active creators of knowledge and co-creation processes should support this foundational activity. In Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshops, Indigenous Peoples and local communities have expressed a desire for scientists and other participants to engage directly in their cultural practices, such as hunting or community camps, to facilitate mutual learning. This approach focuses on community goals through research, aiming to revitalize dynamic knowledge systems, strengthen community cohesion and support intergenerational bonding through activities like elders and youth experiencing the land together. These activities are centred on creating and revitalizing knowledge, skills and experiences rather than merely producing data for reports or academic papers. For instance, during the third IPBES nexus assessment²⁹ workshop on Indigenous and local knowledge (2023b), it was noted that some Indigenous groups are applying modern techniques to enhance traditional agricultural practices, exemplifying practical co-creation tailored to Indigenous objectives. Co-creation approaches in this context support activities meaningful to the community rather than solely generating scientifically usable knowledge.
- **Epistemic justice approach:** Epistemic justice emphasizes the full and fair integration of diverse knowledge systems into governance processes, addressing both procedural and distributive justice (Rarai et al., 2022). This perspective strongly opposes extractive methods that reduce Indigenous knowledge to mere data, which can be abstractly analysed and universally applied (Latulippe & Klenk, 2020). Advocates of epistemic justice argue that Indigenous knowledge is inseparable from the specific landscapes, cultural and spiritual practices that define communities of humans, animals and spirits. These communities are characterized by deep relationships of recognition and care and their knowledge is deeply intertwined with Indigenous self-determination. Such knowledge cannot simply be extracted, packaged and transferred without consideration of its origins and implications. Essential to epistemic justice are the recognition of Indigenous land rights, the affirmation of self-determination and the enhancement of local capacities to manage and govern their own lands.

Across the different approaches, specific policy instruments have been designed to enable knowledge co-creation, primarily focusing on collaborations with Indigenous Peoples and local communities. These instruments form building blocks to create environments conducive to transformative change, although their effectiveness can vary based on implementation and the influence of power dynamics (Kasdan et al., 2021; Orlove et al., 2023). Instruments for knowledge co-creation include:

- **Full consultation:** This instrument promotes the inclusion of Indigenous Peoples and local communities throughout all stages of projects and programmes, supporting their

²⁹ To be considered at IPBES-11

rights to participation and self-governance. It is recognized by the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples' Convention (International Labor Organization, 1989) and policies from entities such as the Convention on Biological Diversity and the World Bank. Countries like India, Chile and Brazil have implemented this approach (Carmona Yost, 2022; Eimer & Bartels, 2020; Tormos-Aponte, 2021).

- **Free, Prior and Informed Consent:** FPIC is a more potent instrument than full consultation, requiring the voluntary agreement of Indigenous Peoples before implementing projects that affect them. It is supported by the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UN General Assembly, 2007) and has been adopted in various regions worldwide (Godden & Tehan, 2016; Papillon & Rodon, 2017; Williams & Hardison, 2013).
- **Recognition of customary law:** This grants legal status to the cultural rules and institutions that govern communal land and resource use, respecting the values and relational dynamics within Indigenous and local knowledge systems. Supported by legislation in countries like Nepal, the Philippines and Mexico, it also acknowledges traditional practices (Eräsaari, 2015; Rénique, 2007; Sherpa et al., 2013).
- **Intellectual property rights:** This instrument ensures the recognition of knowledge ownership, supported by the Nagoya Protocol on Biodiversity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2014). While it provides rights to knowledge holders, its implementation is not always comprehensive or effective. Examples of its application can be seen in Tanzania and the United States (Lusiru & Malekela, 2022).
- **Indigenous data sovereignty:** Extending intellectual property rights, this instrument covers broader knowledge systems, ensuring Indigenous Peoples' rights to protect their knowledge as stipulated by the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. It has seen significant advancements in New Zealand (Cormack & Kukutai, 2022; Reeves et al., 2022).
- **Preservation and promotion of Indigenous languages:** Assuring the vitality and autonomy of languages crucial to Indigenous knowledge systems, this instrument is often paired with educational initiatives to ensure language transmission. It is supported internationally, including in Peru and Fiji (Eräsaari, 2015; Hornberger, 2014; Linares, 2017).

1. Combating disinformation

Disinformation has been ranked first as the most severe global risk by more than a thousand experts in an international survey in 2024 (World Economic Forum, 2024). While known to be a threat to democracy and public health, clearly visible during the COVID-19 pandemic (World Health Organization, 2020), it has also deeply impacted biodiversity and the environment through several ways, e.g., by affecting and delaying policy processes regarding highly concerning topics such as the ozone hole, acid rain, tropical deforestation, and climate change (Farrell et al., 2019; Oreskes & Conway, 2011; Rajão et al., 2022).

Origins of the production and funding of environmental disinformation frequently involve influential think-tanks, large corporations, and political forces (Oreskes & Conway, 2011; G. Reed et al., 2021). For these actors to succeed on affecting society through disinformation, they frequently adopt strategies of various kinds: hiring scientists of questionable background to

“fabricate data” and to distort narratives in favour of their interests (Oreskes & Conway, 2011), via ad hominem attacks to scientists whose research goes against their economic gains (Coan et al., 2021; Farrell et al., 2019), by using the “scientific authority” of misguided scientists to dismantle environmental policies (Rajão et al., 2022), among other tactics (G. Reed et al., 2021). Once disinformation is out for spreading via traditional, digital and social media, its impacts are incalculable since it creates long-standing narratives, fuels existing misunderstandings, and reduces public support for transformative change on biodiversity and environmental matters.

Technology plays a pivotal role on this process. It can be a fundamental means for collective action and social engagement of environmental movements (Ackland & O’Neil, 2011), e.g., the case of “Fridays for Future” (Beckh & Limmer, 2022), but it has also been able to speed up the pace to the pervasive and massive exposure of citizens to disinformation that directly threatens biodiversity and the environment (Lazer et al., 2018; Treen et al., 2020), even more now in times of artificial intelligence (Bontridder & Poulet, 2021). The fast speed of disinformation spread via communication technology outpaces our capacity to counteract it via conventional solutions such as fact-checking and requires not only a multidisciplinary effort (Lazer et al., 2018), but rather co-created strategies in which different expertise and knowledge holders are jointly working for combined solutions. These strategies, such as the creation of environmental networks involving Indigenous people, non-governmental organizations, scientists, and journalists (Observatório do Clima, 2024), and science and media literacy programmes by teachers, psychologists, and journalists (Cooper, 2011) have been showing the promising path of co-creation for tackling disinformation from multiple fronts.

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Annex 5.7. Transformative pathways and agroecology

Visions from chapter 2 associated with agroecology

1. Agroecological resources space (L'Era Associació)

It is an organization made up of peasant women and men, small gardeners, technicians, neo-rurals, students and also sensitive people interested in the peasantry. It was founded in 1999 in Spain under the impulse of the team of teachers and people from the environment of the Agrarian School of Manresa. Its purpose is an agricultural sector with greater recognition by society, capable of contributing to the food sovereignty of its territory and that can establish fair trade relations between the sphere of consumption and production and also between countries. They believe in a peasantry that works according to a holistic concept, integrating the environment and people's rights, to move towards a truly agroecological agriculture.

L'era envisions a society that respects and cares for the Earth, fostering agroecological practices that prioritize the health of ecosystems and communities. They aim to create a world where agricultural systems are based on agroecology, promoting sustainable and resilient food production that nurtures biodiversity, cultural heritage and social justice. L'era seeks to develop agroecological models that promote autonomy, local economies and food sovereignty, while addressing the environmental, social and economic challenges of our time.

Their vision emphasizes the importance of agroecology as a transformative approach to agriculture that integrates ecological principles, local knowledge and social equity. They envision a shift towards agroecological practices that protect and restore ecosystems, promote resilient and diversified farming systems and ensure the well-being and empowerment of farmers and communities.

They publish informative material on any medium, provide assistance and technical advice services, promote training in ecological production and energy sustainability and education in critical and ecological consumption. They have projects about ecological production practices and techniques, renewable energy, bioconstruction and self-sufficiency; preserve and disseminate the local varieties that are typical of their territory.

2. Latin American Agroecological Society (SOCLA)

It's a regional organization dedicated to promoting agroecology to achieve rural development and sustainable food systems in Latin America. It was established as a regional association governed by the Statute approved in the founding General Assembly held in El Carmen de Viboral, Antioquia, Colombia, on August 15, 2007. They don't have their explicit vision in their webpage but in their statutes (*Estatuto Orgánico de La Sociedad Científica Latinoamericana de Agroecología (SOCLA)*, 2022) they mention “*SOCLA is a non-profit, non-partisan and secular association, dedicated to promoting agroecology from different forms of knowledge and through the dialogue of knowledge as a strategy to achieve the sustainability of peoples and food systems in Latin America, emphasizing the values of Good Living / Living Well; food sovereignty; the restoration, health and integrity of ecosystems and socio-ecological systems; the protection,*

conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; the revaluation of biocultural heritage and traditional knowledge; and strengthening of integral well-being". Their goals are to promote, coordinate and facilitate research, teaching and the diffusion of the multiple aspects related to agroecology for sustainability, food sovereignty and socio-ecological resilience to climate change. They seek to respond to the needs and demands of farmers, peasants and indigenous organizations, too. They make publications about green agriculture, transgenic plants, agroecology as a strategy for social transformation, among others. Their webpage does not include a description of the envisioned future in terms of who is doing what, where, why and its implications for nature and people, but some of these actions are implicitly promoted regionally. The scope of the vision is multinational because it includes many countries such as Argentina, Chile, Brazil, Colombia, El Salvador, among others. It's an intent transformative change because they propose a paradigm change in the food systems, but also in trade and human health.

Transformative change: an iterative process

Deliberate transformative change is an iterative, self-amplifying, often political process involving ever increasing numbers of actors engaging in holistic and simultaneous actions to reconsider values, practices and institutions collectively (Pahl-Wostl & Patterson, 2021). This requires forms of deliberative and inclusive governance that can achieve pathways to steward nature while considering diverse values and needs (Lövbrand et al., 2015). Such processes can increase societal learning about transformative change but also offer opportunities to revise assumptions driving underlying theories of transformative change (Holland, 2013). These iterative processes of ongoing reassessment often take place amid emerging concerns of social movements, changing contexts (e.g., structures/institutions) and underlying beliefs and values that influence how individuals and groups perceive and relate to self, others, nature, politics and the future (Bentz et al., 2022). Participation in governance and decision making should allow genuine dialogue with beneficiaries, as well as acknowledging structural causes of social exclusion, such as authoritarianism or exclusionary economic transitions, or indeed tensions between local and donor-driven objectives (Forsyth, 2018; Stein & Valters, 2012; C. H. Weiss, 1995).

1. The critical role of monitoring, evaluation and learning

Given the complexity, uncertainty and ambiguity associated with emergent transformative change, the effectiveness of deliberate interventions aimed at transformative change will hinge on ongoing monitoring, evaluation and learning³⁰. Monitoring, evaluation and learning integrates information from different disciplines, theoretical frameworks and knowledge systems, potentially leading to tensions and trade-offs (Méral et al., 2022). Monitoring depends largely on how evaluators interpret transformability, their objectives, or the networks and cross-scale regulation of outputs, outcomes and impacts (Tittonell, 2014). Evaluations, therefore, need to have flexible and context-specific scopes, which can use transdisciplinary processes, knowledge exchange and reflection, especially when drivers can act at long distances in telecoupled ways (Lang et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2013; Silva et al., 2021). Conventional approaches to monitoring,

³⁰ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

evaluation and learning have not sufficed to embed learning in substantive change trajectories. An assessment of the literature shows an increase in monitoring and evaluation through processes of randomized control trials (RCTs – 82 documents retrieved from Scopus). These forms of monitoring and evaluation are often derived from Logical Framework (logframe) approaches, which identify targets in terms of desired outcomes (such as restored biodiversity) and the outputs (or pathways) needed to achieve outcomes (van de Water et al., 2023). A randomized control trials approach seeks to compare large-n datasets of locations where different pathways have been attempted to assess empirical evidence for the success of different pathways. These randomized control trials approaches have been pioneered in fields such as the testing of pharmaceuticals and are attractive because they offer quantitative analysis sometimes based on long-term experience.

RCT-based approaches have come under criticism for being reductionistic and unable to shed light on underlying mechanisms (Börner et al., 2017). For example, using forest restoration might be a pathway for achieving the outcome of a number of planted trees as proxy for protecting biodiversity, while disregarding other qualities of biodiversity such as ecosystem functions and species diversity. Instead, it could even assign positive evaluations to some forms of tree planting (such as monocultures) that might actually undermine the desired outcome. These approaches fail to recognize that transformative change is a dynamic process, taking place often over extended periods, exhibiting non-linear trajectories, emergent properties, critical thresholds and cross-scale feedback (Tittonell, 2014).

The assessed literature on monitoring, evaluation and learning emphasizes the importance of considering social-ecological aspects and values in the assessment of pathways and suggests that inclusive societal learning, rather than a singular focus on technology and data collection, is integral to transformative change and should be built into any effort to monitor and evaluate it (265 documents retrieved from Scopus).

Some monitoring, evaluation and learning analysts have urged that monitoring and evaluation of progress towards biodiversity objectives also needs to assess the validity of the underlying theories of change (Forsyth, 2018). Theories of change are the justifications used by development organizations to connect their activities with intended outcomes (Brooks & Fisher, 2014). Including assessment of theories of change in monitoring, evaluation and learning means questioning the basic, underlying assumptions that link proposed pathways to desired outcomes. Referring to the wide range of theories of transformative change that were discussed in chapter 3, how these can contribute to a more transformative theory of change through robust monitoring, evaluation and learning processes is identified here.

2. A theory of change or a change of theory?

Recognizing that failed implementation of past biodiversity targets (e.g., the 2020 Aichi targets; Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 2020) is linked in part to a focus on single instruments and actions and direct drivers of biodiversity loss, an alternative approach to monitoring, evaluation and learning might focus on progress in addressing the underlying causes of biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019). This would involve monitoring, evaluating and learning from activity in two broad areas: 1) “unlocking” and phasing out regimes, views, structures and practices that maintain and reinforce unsustainable path dependencies and unequal power relations, while 2) nurturing, expanding and embedding new practices and structures

underpinned by views and values that emphasise the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, good quality of life and regenerative thinking (Buckton et al., 2023; Huntjens et al., 2023; Loorbach & Oxenaar, 2018; Wittmer et al., 2021). This task is represented in **figure SM.5.11**, loosely inspired by the Three Horizons framework (Sharpe et al., 2016) – see also **chapter 3** and the X Diagram (Loorbach & Oxenaar, 2018). This figure emphasizes that transformative change involves an ongoing process of revisitation, examination, evaluation and when needed, revision, of theories of change.

Figure SM.5.10. The process of transformative change. X-curve highlighting the dual need to dismantle undesirable views, structures and practices while nurturing those that support a shift towards just and sustainable futures. Along the way, certain initially promising options may eventually fade out, while unexpected options may emerge because of reflective learning. Flexibility, inclusiveness and non-linearity characterize the different phases of this theory of transformative change. TC: Theory of change cycles; coil arrows represent learning processes.

Effective monitoring, evaluation and learning to support transformative change requires a new theory of change, away from linear and unidirectional approaches. A theory of transformative change should recognize progressive phases and feedback (yellow cycles in **figure SM.5.11**), throughout the different stages of the transformative processes in which learning (coil arrows) informs the next steps. The space and time scales (extent, frequency); the relevant actors; and the monitoring, evaluation and learning indicators will differ between the three phases represented in **figure SM.5.11**, as well as between the alternative trajectories.

The societal learning required for transformative change is dynamic and involves awareness of and responsiveness to social and ecological changes and feedbacks (Fougères et al., 2022). Effective transformation leverages uncertainty and unpredictability as catalysts to reveal and address hidden social barriers and inequalities. This perspective highlights the importance of inclusivity and equity in driving transformative change (Nightingale et al., 2020).

Accordingly, monitoring, evaluation and learning processes for transformative change need to adopt principles of adaptive learning to reflect and use diverse views and pathways rather than rely on predefined normative theories of change (Sullivan & Stewart, 2006; Vogel, 2012).

Table SM.5.12. Contribution of agroecological transitions (and principles) to achieving specific actions across the five strategies for transformative change.

Agroecological transition	Agroecology principles (FAO)	Strategies and actions
Agroecology provides the knowledge and ways of learning to redesign food production landscapes that harbor biodiversity, relying on its associated ecosystem services to replace non-renewable resources and environmentally harmful chemicals.	Diversity Efficiency Recycling Resilience Synergies	Strategy 1, action 1.4 Shifting from extractive to regenerative systems
Agroecological transitions are taking place in both the large scale and family farming sectors, albeit adverse subsidy credit and regulatory systems. Redirecting subsidies, incentives and research/innovation investments towards sustainable forms of farming will accelerate the transition to agroecology	Circular and solidarity economy	Strategy 3, action 3.1 Mainstreaming innovative economic tools
Metrics used to assess performance of agroecology (e.g., TAPE) differ from those used in conventional farming, not just in their biophysical dimension (e.g., efficiency, diversity and recycling indices) but fundamentally in their social and environmental ones	The ten principles of agroecology	Strategy 3, action 3.4 Adopting new metrics of success
In agroecology, knowledge is co-created through a dialogue of wisdoms, integrating Indigenous and local knowledge with science and practice. It concerns not only knowledge systems but ways of learning, classical extension services are replaced by co-innovation platforms	Co-creation and sharing of knowledge	Strategy 4, action 4.4 Strengthening learning through informed, accountable and adaptive governance
Agroecology has strong political and activist dimensions, its social movements advocate for necessary shifts in the values and worldviews that shape current food systems, as a prerequisite for any large-scale agroecological transition (with current consumption patterns agroecology has limited chance to restore biodiversity). These shifts need to	Human and social values Culture and food traditions Responsible governance	Strategy 5, action 5.3 Changing social norms Strategy 5, action 5.4 Facilitating transformative learning

Agroecological transition	Agroecology principles (FAO)	Strategies and actions
operate in all spheres of the food system, including farmers, consumers, the industry, retailers and policy makers.	Co-creation and sharing of knowledge	

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